

Serialisability in Formal Argumentation (Preprint)

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Abstract

We consider serialisability of argumentation semantics, which is a non-deterministic construction scheme for extensions, where non-empty, minimal admissible sets (also called initial sets) are selected iteratively to resolve atomic conflicts of the argumentation framework. This yields a procedural perspective on semantics in formal argumentation, where semantical conclusions are represented through series of initial sets, termed *serialisation sequences*, that make explicit the underlying argumentative reasoning process. In this work, we examine the procedural construction scheme of serialisability in detail and develop a principle-based approach to characterise and connect it with established principles for argumentation semantics. Moreover, we introduce initial models and serialisability for abstract dialectical frameworks (ADFs), a powerful generalisation of abstract argumentation frameworks (AFs). To round up our research, we examine the computational complexity of tasks related to initial models and serialisation sequences in both AFs and ADFs and show that working with them is in most cases as computationally hard as the traditional extension-based approach.

Keywords: knowledge representation, formal argumentation, serialisability, semantics

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1. Introduction

Knowledge representation and reasoning is an important area within artificial intelligence (AI) research (Brachman and Levesque, 2004; van Harmelen et al., 2008). Especially with the increasing popularity and adoption of large

5 language models and other black-box AI approaches, the need for transparent
6 and explainable AI has grown even more apparent (Leofante et al., 2024). We
7 are considering *formal argumentation* (Baroni et al., 2018b; Gabbay et al.,
8 2021), which has established itself as one of the major approaches for repre-
9 senting knowledge (Bench-Capon and Dunne, 2007; Atkinson et al., 2017).
10 Formal argumentation is inspired by human reasoning (Antaki and Leudar,
11 1992), making it particularly well-suited for developing explainable and con-
12 testable AI systems (Leofante et al., 2024). Argumentation-based approaches
13 can either be used directly as an intrinsically explainable system or they can
14 be employed to provide post-hoc explanations for black-box models (Cyras
15 et al., 2021).

16 The most important formalism within the field of formal argumentation
17 continues to be the *abstract argumentation framework* (AF) due to Dung
18 (1995). In an abstract argumentation framework, we abstract away the con-
19 tent of the arguments and focus on the conflicts between them, represented as
20 directed attacks within a directed graph. Reasoning in abstract argumenta-
21 tion frameworks is defined via different semantics. The most commonly used
22 approach here are the extension-based semantics, as introduced by Dung
23 (1995), where jointly acceptable sets of arguments, called extensions, are
24 selected according to different criteria.

25 Formal argumentation has found many applications, for instance in law
26 and legal reasoning (Bench-Capon et al., 2009; Prakken and Sartor, 2015).
27 Both legal reasoning and argumentation are closely related to dialectics (Hage
28 et al., 1993; Prakken and Sartor, 1996). Dialectical argumentation empha-
29 sises two fundamental aspects: *procedurality* and the *exchange of arguments*,
30 i. e., the fact that arguments and counterarguments are brought forward one
31 after another in alternating fashion (Rescher, 1977; Hage, 2000). While both
32 of these aspects are modelled well on the syntactic level of AFs via the di-
33 rected attacks, on the semantical layer these elements are somewhat lost (Ver-
34 heij, 1996). Consider, for instance, the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_1 depicted
35 in Figure 1 (we will provide formal definitions in Section 2).

36 We have that a attacks b which in turn attacks c , while c, d, e and f
37 form a cycle of attacks, with d and f additionally contradicting each other.
38 Assume we are interested in understanding why the argument c is acceptable.
39 Intuitively, we can see that c can only be accepted after we have dealt with
40 the attack from b , which we can do by accepting a first. In other words, a
41 defends c against b . Moreover, c is also attacked by f , which can be defended
42 by e , which in turn requires defense by c against d . Meaning, c and e depend

Figure 1: The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_1 . The argument a defends c against the attack of b , while c and e defend each other against d and f .

43 on each other for their defense and both depend on a to defend c against b .
 44 In the classical extension-based semantics, we only represent the semantical
 45 conclusion (in this case the set $\{a, c, e\}$), but the underlying reasoning process
 46 to arrive there is not represented.

47 An approach that addresses the above issue is the notion of *serialisabil-*
 48 *ity* of semantics for AFs (Thimm, 2022). Serialisability describes a non-
 49 deterministic construction scheme for extensions, where *initial sets* of the
 50 AF are selected iteratively. Here, an initial set (Xu and Cayrol, 2018) is de-
 51 fined as a non-empty, minimal admissible set, essentially representing atomic
 52 semantical units that each resolve a single elementary conflict of the argu-
 53 mentation framework. An extension can then be represented by *serialisation*
 54 *sequences*, i. e., sequences of initial sets that represent an order in which the
 55 corresponding extension can be build. Serialisation sequences can then be
 56 understood as an alternative, process-based form of representing semantics
 57 in argumentation frameworks (Bengel, 2025) and is generally more expressive
 58 than the extension-based semantics (Bengel et al., 2024).

59 The present work contains a thorough analysis of *serialisable semantics*,
 60 in particular regarding their formal and computational properties, as well as
 61 their applicability to more general formal frameworks. More concretely, for
 62 the classical extension-based semantics, there exists a well-known principle-
 63 based approach to analyse them in the literature (van der Torre and Vesic,
 64 2018). In this approach, principles for argumentation semantics cover differ-
 65 ent desirable aspects, and provide a structured way to formally investigate
 66 existing and novel semantics, by examining whether they satisfy or violate
 67 the different principles. In this work, we aim to develop a similar approach for
 68 serialisable semantics. For that, we introduce 10 new properties for serialis-
 69 able semantics that directly take into account the intricacies of the underlying
 70 argumentation process of the semantics. This is so far not taken into account
 71 by most argumentation principles. These properties model different aspects

72 of the argumentation process, for instance, the closure property ensures that
73 it always terminates soundly and the Markov property requires that the
74 process is memoryless. Consequently, we establish connections between our
75 novel serialisation properties and the existing argumentation principles from
76 the literature. As it turns out, the closure of the argumentation process is
77 a sufficient criterion for the *Directionality* principle of Baroni and Giacomin
78 (2007) and the Markov property is a sufficient criterion for the *Modularisation*
79 principle of Baumann et al. (2022).

80 While abstract argumentation frameworks are very popular in the liter-
81 ature, particularly due to their simplicity in having only one type of binary
82 relation, they have somewhat limited modelling capabilities as a consequence
83 of this. In the field of formal argumentation, there are many extensions to
84 Dung’s AFs introducing other types of relations and many other enhance-
85 ments, see (Brewka et al., 2014; Gabbay et al., 2021) for an overview. A
86 prominent approach are the *bipolar argumentation frameworks* (BAFs) (Am-
87 goud et al., 2008; Cayrol and Lagasquie-Schiex, 2013) which introduce a sup-
88 port relation between arguments to allow the direct modelling of positive rela-
89 tions between arguments. Another well-researched extension are *argumenta-*
90 *tion frameworks with collective attacks* (SetAFs) (Nielsen and Parsons, 2006)
91 which allows sets of arguments to jointly attack another argument. Many
92 other extensions to AFs exist, for instance, preference-based AFs (Amgoud
93 and Cayrol, 2002), which incorporate a preference relation over arguments,
94 incomplete AFs (Coste-Marquis et al., 2007; Baumeister et al., 2021), which
95 allows the modelling of uncertainty regarding the existence of arguments
96 and attacks, or probabilistic AFs (Hunter et al., 2021), where uncertainty is
97 modelled by a probability distribution over the arguments.

98 Of particular interest to the present work are the *abstract dialectical*
99 *frameworks* (ADFs) (Brewka and Woltran, 2010; Brewka et al., 2013), which
100 have emerged as an especially powerful generalisation of AFs. In an ADF,
101 the relations between the arguments are represented by *acceptance condi-*
102 *tions*, i. e., (propositional) logical formulae that specify the conditions under
103 which the argument may be accepted. This enables the representation of
104 more complex relationships between arguments. That includes support rela-
105 tions as well as collective attacks, which means that, for instance, both BAFs
106 and SetAFs are subsumed by ADFs (Polberg, 2017). Moreover, there exist
107 various practical applications of ADFs in the literature. For instance, Cabrio
108 and Villata (2016) use ADFs for text exploration, while Al-Abdulkarim et al.
109 (2014) apply ADFs in the field of legal reasoning and Strass (2013b) instan-

110 tiates knowledge bases via ADFs. For a general overview on ADFs we refer
111 to Brewka et al. (2018). Formal semantics for ADFs operate on three-valued
112 interpretations and are given through functions that determine acceptable
113 interpretations, also called models. In particular, the classical admissibility-
114 based semantics of Dung have been generalised to ADFs (Brewka et al.,
115 2013).

116 As their name suggests, abstract dialectical frameworks are inspired by
117 dialectics. However, similar to Dung’s argumentation frameworks the procedu-
118 ral nature of dialectical argumentation is only captured on the syntactic
119 level. To address this issue, we introduce initial models as the atomic seman-
120 tical units of abstract dialectical frameworks and subsequently define seriali-
121 sation sequences for many semantics of ADFs, thereby bringing the procedu-
122 ral aspect of dialectical argumentation to the semantical level of ADFs. We
123 further establish that initial models are a proper generalisation of initial sets
124 in this domain. Leveraging the three-valued representation of semantics, we
125 demonstrate that serialisation sequences of ADFs are more expressive than
126 their counterpart in AFs. Crucially, these sequences incorporate both ac-
127 cepted and rejected arguments directly. As a result, serialisation sequences
128 fully embed both procedurality and the exchange of arguments – two fun-
129 damental aspects of dialectical argumentation – into the semantical layer of
130 ADFs.

131 To round up our research in this paper, we analyse the computational
132 complexity of certain tasks wrt. serialisation sequences in AFs and ADFs
133 and initial models in ADFs. Notably, our results reveal that reasoning with
134 serialisation sequences incurs no significant additional computational cost
135 compared to extension- or model-based representations for AFs and the sub-
136 class of bipolar ADFs, while offering a more expressive semantical representa-
137 tion. Regarding initial models, reasoning in general ADFs is computationally
138 harder than reasoning with initial sets in AFs. For bipolar ADFs, however,
139 reasoning tasks related to initial models are computationally equivalent to
140 those for initial sets in AFs.

141 To summarise, the main contributions of this work are as follows:

- 142 1. We introduce a property-based approach to formally analyse serialis-
143 able semantics and relate them to argumentation principles from the
144 literature (Section 4),
- 145 2. We generalise initial models and serialisation sequences to abstract di-
146 alectical frameworks and characterise most admissibility based seman-

147 tics in this way (Section 5),

148 3. We analyse the computational complexity of typical tasks wrt. seri-
149 alisation sequences in AFs as well as initial models and serialisation
150 sequences in ADFs (Section 6).

151 Before that, in Section 2 we introduce the necessary background on ab-
152 stract argumentation frameworks and abstract dialectical frameworks. Fol-
153 lowing that, in Section 3 we recall the notion of serialisability. In Section 7
154 we discuss related work, and Section 8 concludes the paper. The proofs of
155 all technical results can be found in the appendix.

156 ***Disclaimer.*** *This work is based on two conference publications: (Bengel*
157 *and Thimm, 2022) published at COMMA 2022 and (Bengel and Thimm,*
158 *2025) published at IJCAI 2025.*

159 *In (Bengel and Thimm, 2022), we considered only the general relations*
160 *between serialisability and other principles as well the closure property and*
161 *its connection to the Directionality principle. In this work, we expand this*
162 *significantly by introducing 9 additional properties and characterising their*
163 *relationship to argumentation principles.*

164 *In (Bengel and Thimm, 2025), we characterised initial models and seri-*
165 *alisability for ADFs and investigated the computational complexity of tasks*
166 *related to initial models in general ADFs. In this work, we improved the*
167 *presentation of all results and include additional results on the serialisation*
168 *of strong admissibility and stable semantics in ADFs.*

169 *Regarding computational complexity, we added novel results for tasks re-*
170 *lated to initial models in the subclass of bipolar ADFs and we added an anal-*
171 *ysis of the complexity of serialisation sequences in AFs, ADFs and bipolar*
172 *ADFs.*

173 **2. Background**

174 In this section we recall the necessary background for this work. First,
175 in Section 2.1 we recall abstract argumentation frameworks. Following that,
176 in Section 2.2 we review principles for argumentation semantics. Lastly,
177 we introduce the necessary definitions on abstract dialectical frameworks in
178 Section 2.3.

179 *2.1. Abstract Argumentation Frameworks*

180 We consider *abstract argumentation frameworks* due to Dung (1995).

181 **Definition 2.1.** An *(abstract) argumentation framework* (AF) is a tuple
 182 $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, where \mathcal{A} is a finite set of arguments and \mathcal{R} is a relation $\mathcal{R} \subseteq$
 183 $\mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A}$.

184 With \mathbb{A} we denote the universal set of arguments and with \mathbb{AF} the set
 185 of all abstract argumentation frameworks. For two arguments $a, b \in \mathcal{A}$,
 186 the relation $a\mathcal{R}b$ means that a attacks b . For a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we denote by
 187 $\mathcal{F}|_S = (S, \mathcal{R} \cap (S \times S))$ the *projection* of \mathcal{F} onto S . For two argumentation
 188 frameworks $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}), \mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ we say that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}' are *disjunct*
 189 iff $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{A}' = \emptyset$ and we define the *union* of \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}' as the argumentation
 190 framework $\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{R}')$. For a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ we also define

$$S_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm} = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid \exists b \in S : b\mathcal{R}a\}, \quad S_{\mathcal{F}}^{-} = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid \exists b \in S : a\mathcal{R}b\}$$

191 as the set of arguments attacked by and attacking the set S in \mathcal{F} , respectively.
 192 For a singleton set $\{a\}$, we omit brackets for readability, i. e., we write $a_{\mathcal{F}}^{-}$
 193 $(a_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm})$. For two sets S and S' we write $S\mathcal{R}S'$ iff $S' \cap S_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm} \neq \emptyset$. We say that a
 194 set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is *conflict-free* iff for all $a, b \in S$ it is not the case that $a\mathcal{R}b$. We
 195 denote with $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F})$ the conflict-free sets of \mathcal{F} . A set S *defends* an argument
 196 $b \in \mathcal{A}$ iff for all a with $a\mathcal{R}b$ there is $c \in S$ with $c\mathcal{R}a$.

197 We define the *characteristic function* $\Delta_{\mathcal{F}} : 2^{\mathcal{A}} \mapsto 2^{\mathcal{A}}$ of an AF \mathcal{F} as follows

$$\Delta_{\mathcal{F}}(S) = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid S \text{ defends } a\} \tag{1}$$

198 Furthermore, a set S is called *admissible* (**ad**) iff it is conflict-free and S
 199 defends all $a \in S$. We define different semantics by imposing constraints on
 200 admissible sets (Dung, 1995; Baroni et al., 2018a).

201 **Definition 2.2.** Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF. An admissible set $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is a

- 202 • *complete* (**co**) extension iff for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$, if E defends a then $a \in E$,
- 203 • *grounded* (**gr**) extension iff E is complete and there is no complete E'
 204 with $E' \subsetneq E$,
- 205 • *preferred* (**pr**) extension iff there is no admissible E' with $E \subsetneq E'$,
- 206 • *stable* (**st**) extension iff $E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^{\pm} = \mathcal{A}$,

- 207 • *strongly admissible* (**sa**) set iff $E = \emptyset$ or each $a \in E$ is defended by some
 208 strongly admissible $E' \subseteq E \setminus \{a\}$.

209 For the context of this work we consider **ad** to be a semantics itself.
 210 For any semantics $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{ad}, \mathbf{co}, \mathbf{pr}, \mathbf{sa}, \mathbf{gr}, \mathbf{st}\}$, let $\sigma(\mathcal{F})$ denote the set of σ -
 211 extensions of \mathcal{F} .

Figure 2: The AF \mathcal{F}_2 from Examples 2.1, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4.

212 **Example 2.1.** Consider the AF \mathcal{F}_2 depicted in Figure 2. We have that $\{a\}$,
 213 $\{a, d\}$, $\{a, c\}$ and $\{a, c, e\}$ are the complete extensions of \mathcal{F}_2 . The former is
 214 also the unique grounded extension, while $\{a, d\}$ and $\{a, c, e\}$ are \subseteq -maximal
 215 and thus the two preferred extensions of \mathcal{F}_2 . However, only $\{a, c, e\}$ is a stable
 216 extension of \mathcal{F}_2 , because $\{a, d\}$ does neither attack nor include f . Finally,
 217 the empty set and $\{a\}$ are the only strongly admissible sets of \mathcal{F}_2 .

218 Finally, we recall the definition of the reduct (Baumann et al., 2020b).

219 **Definition 2.3.** For $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, the S -reduct \mathcal{F}^S is defined via
 220 $\mathcal{F}^S = \mathcal{F}|_{\mathcal{A} \setminus (S \cup S_{\mathcal{F}}^+)}$.

221 In other words, for some set S the S -reduct of an AF is the AF that
 222 remains after removing all arguments in S and all arguments attacked by S ,
 223 i. e., it contains only arguments not defended against by S .

224 2.2. Principles for Argumentation Semantics

225 We turn to principles for argumentation semantics. First, we recall some
 226 basic definitions. We say that two argumentation frameworks $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$
 227 and $\mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ are *isomorphic*, written as $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\mathbf{m}} \mathcal{F}'$, iff there exists a
 228 bijective function $\mathbf{m} : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \mathcal{A}'$, such that $(a, b) \in \mathcal{R}$ iff $(\mathbf{m}(a), \mathbf{m}(b)) \in \mathcal{R}'$. For
 229 a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we denote with $\mathbf{m}(S)$ the set of arguments where every $a \in S$
 230 is renamed via $\mathbf{m}(a)$. Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework. We
 231 define the set of unattacked sets of \mathcal{F} as $\mathcal{UG}(\mathcal{F}) = \{S \subseteq \mathcal{A} \mid S_{\mathcal{F}}^- \subseteq S\}$.
 232 Furthermore, a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is a *strongly connected component* (SCC) of \mathcal{F} ,
 233 if there is a directed path between any pair $a, b \in S$ in \mathcal{F} and there is no

234 $S' \supset S$ with that property. Let $\text{SCCs}(\mathcal{F})$ denote the set of strongly connected
 235 components of \mathcal{F} . Moreover, for a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, we define $\text{op}_{\mathcal{F}}(S) = S_{\mathcal{F}}^- \setminus S$,
 236 i. e., the set of attackers of S from the outside. Given a set $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and a
 237 strongly connected component $S \in \text{SCCs}(\mathcal{F})$, we define the following three
 238 sets (Baroni et al., 2005).

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E) &= (E \cap \text{op}_{\mathcal{F}}(S))_{\mathcal{F}}^+, \\ P_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E) &= \{a \in S \mid a \notin (E \cap \text{op}_{\mathcal{F}}(S))_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \wedge \exists b \in (a_{\mathcal{F}}^- \cap \text{op}_{\mathcal{F}}(S)) : b \notin E_{\mathcal{F}}^+\}, \\ U_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E) &= S \setminus (D_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E) \cup P_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E)). \end{aligned}$$

239 $D_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E)$ is the set of arguments within S that is attacked by E from
 240 outside of S and $U_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E)$ is the set of arguments within S that are defended
 241 against all outside attackers by E . Lastly, $P_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E)$ is the set of arguments
 242 within S that is neither attacked by E from outside S nor defended by E
 243 against outside attackers. Based on this, we can now define the SCC-recursive
 244 scheme for argumentation semantics (Baroni et al., 2005).

245 **Definition 2.4.** Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and $C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$
 246 is a set of arguments.

- 247 1. A function $\mathcal{BF}(\mathcal{F}, C)$ is called *base function*, if, given an argumentation
 248 framework $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ such that $|\text{SCCs}(\mathcal{F})| = 1$ and a set $C \subseteq \mathcal{A}$,
 249 $\mathcal{BF}(\mathcal{F}, C) \subseteq 2^{\mathcal{A}}$.
- 250 2. Given a base function $\mathcal{BF}(\mathcal{F}, C)$ we define the function $\mathcal{GF}_{\mathcal{BF}}(\mathcal{F}, C) \subseteq$
 251 $2^{\mathcal{A}}$ as follows: for any $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, $E \in \mathcal{GF}(\mathcal{F}, C)$ if and only if
 - 252 • in case $|\text{SCCs}(\mathcal{F})_{\mathcal{F}}| = 1$, we have that $E \in \mathcal{BF}(\mathcal{F}, C)$,
 - 253 • and otherwise, for all $S \in \text{SCCs}(\mathcal{F})$ we have that

$$E \cap S \in \mathcal{GF}_{\mathcal{BF}}(\mathcal{F}|_{S \setminus D_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E)}, U_{\mathcal{F}}(S, E) \cap C).$$

254 We also require the notion of *strong defense* (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007).

255 **Definition 2.5.** Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$
 256 is a set of arguments. We say that an argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ is *strongly defended*
 257 by E (denoted as $\text{sd}(a, E)$) iff for all $b \in \mathcal{A}$ if $b\mathcal{R}a$ then there exists some
 258 $c \in E \setminus \{a\}$ with $c\mathcal{R}b$ and $\text{sd}(c, E \setminus \{a\})$.

259 Finally, we recall the definitions of the different principles from the liter-
 260 ature, that we consider in our analysis. For each principle we include name
 261 and reference, as well as an informal description of the underlying idea and
 262 its formal definition.

263 **Definition 2.6.** A semantics σ satisfies the respective principle iff for every
 264 argumentation framework $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ the respective condition holds:

265 **Language Independence** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *The semantics is*
 266 *independent of argument names.*

For every AF \mathcal{F}' , if $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\mathfrak{m}} \mathcal{F}'$ then $\sigma(\mathcal{F}') = \{\mathfrak{m}(E) \mid E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})\}$.

267 **Conflict-Freeness** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *Every extension of the se-*
 268 *mantics is conflict-free.*

For every $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, E is a conflict-free set in \mathcal{F} .

269 **Defense** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *Every extension of the semantics*
 270 *defends all its arguments.*

For every $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and every $a \in E$, E defends a .

271 **Admissibility** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *Every extension of the seman-*
 272 *tics is admissible.*

For every $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, E is conflict-free and defends itself in \mathcal{F} .

273 **Strong Admissibility** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *No argument of a σ -*
 274 *extension may defend itself.*

For every $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, E strongly defends every $a \in E$.

275 **Reinstatement** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *Every argument defended by*
 276 *a σ -extension is included in it.*

For every $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and every $a \in \mathcal{A}$, if E defends a then $a \in E$.

277 **Naivety** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *If an argument is not in conflict*
 278 *with a σ -extension, then it is included in the extension.*

For every $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, E is conflict-free and there is no conflict-free
 $E' \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ with $E \subsetneq E'$.

279 **Allowing Abstention** (Baroni et al., 2011). *If an argument can be both ac-*
 280 *cepted and rejected, then some σ -extension that does neither exists.*

For every $a \in \mathcal{A}$, if there exist two extensions $E_1, E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ such that $a \in E$ and $a \in E_2^+$ then there exists an extension $E_3 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ such that $a \notin (E_3 \cup E_3^+)$.

281 **I-Maximality** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *No two extensions of the se-*
 282 *mantics are in a subset relationship with each other.*

For every $E_1, E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, if $E_1 \subseteq E_2$ then $E_1 = E_2$.

283 **SCC-Recursiveness** (Baroni et al., 2005). *Every extension of the seman-*
 284 *tics can be constructed by considering the SCCs individually.*

There is a base function \mathcal{BF}_σ such that $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathcal{GF}_{\mathcal{BF}_\sigma}(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{A})$.

285 **Directionality** (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). *The status of a σ -extension*
 286 *only depends on itself and arguments that attack it or its ancestors.*

For every $U \in \mathcal{US}(\mathcal{F})$, we have $\sigma(\mathcal{F}, U) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}|_U)$ with
 $\sigma(\mathcal{F}, U) = \{E \cap U \mid E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})\}$.

287 **Modularisation** (Baumann et al., 2022). *Extensions of the semantics can*
 288 *be combined via the reduct.*

If $E_1 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and $E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{E_1})$ then $E_1 \cup E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$.

289 Table 1 gives an overview over the principles and semantics considered
 290 in this work. All results shown are collected from the literature (Baroni and
 291 Giacomin, 2007; van der Torre and Vesic, 2018; Baumann et al., 2022; Bengel
 292 and Thimm, 2022).

293 Note that there exist further principles in the literature. For instance,
 294 there are the *Weak-* and *CF-Reinstatement* principles. However, they are
 295 generally implied by *Reinstatement* and provide no additional insight for
 296 admissibility-based semantics (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007). Similarly, the
 297 principles of *Reduct Admissibility* and *Semi-Qualified Admissibility*, intro-
 298 duced by Dauphin et al. (2020), are implied by *Admissibility* and thus also
 299 not of interest for this work. Furthermore, there are also *Crash-Resistance*
 300 and *Non-Interference* due to Caminada et al. (2012) which have been shown
 301 to be implied by *Directionality* (Baroni et al., 2011). The same applies to
 302 the two variants *Weak Directionality* and *Semi-Directionality* (van der Torre
 303 and Vesic, 2018). For other well-known properties like *Indirect Conflict-*
 304 *Freeness* (Coste-Marquis et al., 2005), we have that they are typically not
 305 satisfied by any admissibility-based semantics and thus not of interest for our
 306 analysis.

307 We will consider the above introduced principles in Section 4 and relate
 308 them to our novel serialisation properties.

Principle	ad	co	pr	sa	gr	st	uc
<i>Language Independence</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Conflict-Freeness</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Defense</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Admissibility</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Strong Admissibility</i>	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗
<i>Reinstatement</i>	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
<i>Naivety</i>	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
<i>Allowing Abstention</i>	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗
<i>I-Maximality</i>	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
<i>SCC-Recursiveness</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
<i>Directionality</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
<i>Modularisation</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: Overview over the satisfaction of the principles from Definition 2.6 by the semantics considered in this work.

309 *2.3. Abstract Dialectical Frameworks*

310 Finally, we consider the relevant background on abstract dialectical frame-
311 works. For that, we first recall some basics on propositional logics with
312 three-valued semantics. Let \mathbf{At} be a set of propositional atoms and $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{At}}$ the
313 propositional language over \mathbf{At} , closed under the usual connectives \neg , \vee , and
314 \wedge . \top and \perp represent the logical tautology and contradiction respectively. A
315 *three-valued interpretation* $v : \mathbf{At} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is a function that assigns to each
316 atom in \mathbf{At} one of the three truth values *true* (\mathbf{t}), *false* (\mathbf{f}) or *unknown* (\mathbf{u}).
317 Truth evaluation wrt. an interpretation v is extended to arbitrary formulas

318 as follows. For a propositional formula ϕ over At , we define $v(\phi)$ inductively

$$\begin{aligned}
v(\neg\psi) &= \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } v(\psi) = \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } v(\psi) = \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{if } v(\psi) = \mathbf{u} \end{cases} \\
v(\psi_1 \wedge \psi_2) &= \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } v(\psi_1) = v(\psi_2) = \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } v(\psi_1) = \mathbf{f} \text{ or } v(\psi_2) = \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
v(\psi_1 \vee \psi_2) &= \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } v(\psi_1) = \mathbf{t} \text{ or } v(\psi_2) = \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } v(\psi_1) = v(\psi_2) = \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

319 If an interpretation v satisfies a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{At}}$, i. e., it assigns true to
320 ϕ , we may also call v a *model* of ϕ . If a formula ϕ has at least one model it is
321 *satisfiable*. Furthermore, we denote with TAUT_{At} the set of tautologies and
322 with UNSAT_{At} the set of unsatisfiable formulae over At . For some formula
323 $\phi \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{At}}$ and an interpretation $v : \text{At} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ we define $\phi^{[a/x : v(a)=x]}$ to be
324 the formula ϕ where each occurrence of a is substituted by the truth value
325 $x \in \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}\}$ assigned to it by v .

326 Now, an *abstract dialectical framework* (ADF) is a directed graph whose
327 nodes represent arguments and the directed edges represent dependencies
328 between the arguments. These dependencies are modelled via acceptance
329 conditions that are associated with each argument.

330 **Definition 2.7.** An *abstract dialectical framework* (ADF) is a tuple $\mathcal{D} =$
331 $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{C})$ where \mathcal{A} is a set of arguments, $\mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A}$ is a set of links and \mathcal{C} is
332 a set of propositional formulae $\{\phi_a\}_{a \in \mathcal{A}}$ over \mathcal{A} , called *acceptance conditions*¹.

333 We denote with ADF the set of all ADFs. In general, the links \mathcal{L} can
334 easily be inferred from the acceptance conditions, so it is not necessary to
335 include them in \mathcal{D} explicitly. For that reason, we will typically represent
336 an ADF as a pair $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$, with \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{C} defined as above and \mathcal{L} follows

¹In the original definition of ADFs (Brewka et al., 2013), acceptance conditions are given as total functions $C_a : 2^{\text{par}(a)} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}\}$ over the parents $\text{par}(a)$ of each a . In our work, we exclusively use the representation as propositional formulae for convenience. Note that both representations are functionally equivalent.

337 implicitly as $(a, b) \in \mathcal{L}$ iff a appears in the acceptance condition ϕ_b (Brewka
 338 et al., 2018). We also denote with $par(a)$ the set of arguments that appear
 339 in the acceptance condition of $a \in \mathcal{A}$, i. e., the parents of a in \mathcal{D} .

340 Reasoning in ADFs is performed via three-valued propositional interpreta-
 341 tions that satisfy all acceptance conditions². Given some interpretation v ,
 342 we also consider the inverse function $v^{-1} : \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\} \mapsto 2^{\mathcal{A}}$, meaning we denote
 343 with $v^{-1}(x)$ the set of arguments that is assigned the truth value x by the
 344 interpretation v , for all $x \in \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$. We may also write $a \mapsto x$ instead of
 345 $v(a) = x$ for readability. To simplify representation, we will sometimes omit
 346 assignments to \mathbf{u} , e. g., instead of $v = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}$ we may only write
 347 $v = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ if the set of arguments \mathcal{A} is clear from context. We denote with
 348 $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ the trivial three-valued interpretation that assigns \mathbf{u} to all $a \in \mathcal{A}$.

349 We consider the following partial order \leq_i according to information con-
 350 tent: $\mathbf{u} <_i \mathbf{t}$, $\mathbf{u} <_i \mathbf{f}$ and no other pair in $<_i$, i. e., the classical truth values
 351 \mathbf{t} and \mathbf{f} contain more information than the truth value unknown (\mathbf{u}). For a
 352 pair of three-valued interpretations $v_1, v_2 : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ we define

$$v_1 \leq_i v_2 \quad \text{iff } v_1(a) \leq_i v_2(a) \text{ for all } a \in \mathcal{A}.$$

353 The *consensus operator* \sqcap combines two interpretations v_1 and v_2 into a
 354 new interpretation v_3 , that coincides with v_1 and v_2 wherever both interpreta-
 355 tions coincide and assigns \mathbf{u} otherwise. We define $v_3 = v_1 \sqcap v_2$ as

$$v_3(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } v_1(a) = v_2(a) = \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } v_1(a) = v_2(a) = \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

356 for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$.

357 **Example 2.2.** Consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_1 depicted in Figure 3. We have, for

²Note that Brewka et al. (2013) define the notion of a *three-valued model* v such that $v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ implies $v(a) = v(\phi_a)$ according to Kleene’s three-valued logic (Kleene, 1952). As shown by Heyninck et al. (2022) this notion is not well-defined, i. e. admissible models are not actually three-valued models. Instead, the underlying logic of these models is possibilistic logic. Since the semantical evaluation via the characteristic operator is anyway independent of this, we refrain from using three-valued models in our work.

Figure 3: The ADF \mathcal{D}_1 from Examples 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4.

358 instance the three-valued interpretations

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_1 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \\
 v_2 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}, \\
 v_3 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

359 Note that v_1 satisfies all acceptance conditions of \mathcal{D}_1 while v_2 and v_3 do
 360 not satisfy the acceptance condition ϕ_d (v_3 also does not satisfy ϕ_e). We
 361 have, for instance, $v_1^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) = \{a, d, e\}$ and it is easy to see that $v_2 \leq_i v_1$ and
 362 $v_2 \leq_i v_3$. v_1 and v_3 are not comparable due to the argument d . Furthermore,
 363 the consensus of v_1 and v_2 is v_2 itself, i. e., $v_1 \sqcap v_2 = v_2$. And we also have
 364 $v_1 \sqcap v_3 = v_2$.

365 For some three-valued interpretation v , we define the set of two-valued
 366 *completions* $[v]_2$ as

$$[v]_2 = \{v' \mid v \leq_i v', (v')^{-1}(\mathbf{u}) = \emptyset\} \quad (3)$$

367 The set $[v]_2$ is then essentially the set of all two-valued interpretations that
 368 contain more information than v . For the semantic evaluation of an ADF \mathcal{D}
 369 we then define the *characteristic operator* $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ which computes for a model v
 370 the consensus of all its completions for every argument.

371 **Definition 2.8.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ be a
 372 three-valued interpretation. We define the *characteristic operator* $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ as

$$\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = \bigsqcap \{v'(\phi_a) \mid v' \in [v]_2\}$$

373 for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$.

374 Similar to the characteristic function for AFs, cf. Equation (1), this oper-
 375 ator essentially computes for a given model v which of its truth value assign-
 376 ments are actually justified by v , i. e., whether they satisfy the acceptance
 377 condition of an argument under all possible completions.

378 **Example 2.3.** We continue Example 2.2 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_1 in Figure 3. For
 379 v_3 we have the two two-valued completions

$$v_4 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\},$$

$$v_5 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}.$$

380 We can then compute the characteristic operator as the consensus over all
 381 completions of v_3 and obtain

$$\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_1}(v_3) = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}.$$

382 Here, we have $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_1}(v_3)(d) = v_4(\phi_d) \sqcap v_5(\phi_d) = v_4(\neg b) \sqcap v_5(\neg b) = \mathbf{t} \sqcap \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{t}$.
 383 Similarly, we have $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_1}(v_3)(e) = v_4(\phi_e) \sqcap v_5(\phi_e) = v_4(\neg c \wedge d) \sqcap v_5(\neg c \wedge d) =$
 384 $\mathbf{t} \sqcap \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{u}$.

385 We then utilise the characteristic operator to define the classical admissibility-
 386 based semantics for ADFs (Brewka and Woltran, 2010; Brewka et al., 2013).

387 **Definition 2.9.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF. We define $v_0 = v_{\mathbf{u}}$ and $v_i =$
 388 $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{i-1})$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ be the smallest number with $v_k = v_{k-1}$.
 389 Then v_k is called the *grounded (gr) model* of \mathcal{D} .

390 **Definition 2.10.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF. An interpretation $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto$
 391 $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is called

- 392 • an *admissible (ad) model* of \mathcal{D} , iff $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$,
- 393 • a *complete (co) model* of \mathcal{D} , iff $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$,
- 394 • a *preferred (pr) model* of \mathcal{D} , iff v is complete and there is no complete
 395 model v' with $v \leq_i v'$.

396 We also define the set of all *two-valued models* of \mathcal{D} as the set $\text{val}_2(\mathcal{D}) =$
 397 $\{v \mid \forall a \in \mathcal{A} : v(a) = v(\phi_a) \wedge v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}$. The stable semantics has been
 398 revised in Brewka et al. (2013) compared to its original proposal in Brewka
 399 and Woltran (2010). For that we need the following notion.

400 **Definition 2.11.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is a
 401 two-valued model of \mathcal{D} . We define the *reduced ADF* $\mathcal{D}_{\downarrow v} = (v^{-1}(\mathbf{t}), \mathcal{C}')$ such
 402 that for all $a \in v^{-1}(\mathbf{t})$ and $\phi'_a \in \mathcal{C}'$ we set $\phi'_a = \phi_a^{[b/\mathbf{f} : v(b)=\mathbf{f}]}$.

403 **Example 2.4.** Consider again the ADF \mathcal{D}_1 in Figure 3. We have the two-
 404 valued model

$$v = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$$

405 of \mathcal{D}_1 . For the reduced ADF $\mathcal{D}_{1,\downarrow v} = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{C}')$ we then have $\mathcal{A}' = \{a, d, e\}$ and
 406 $\mathcal{C}' = \{\phi'_a, \phi'_d, \phi'_e\}$ with $\phi'_a = \top$, $\phi'_d = \top$ and $\phi'_e = \top$.

407 The stable semantics for ADFs is then defined as follows.

408 **Definition 2.12.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF. A two-valued model v of \mathcal{D} is
 409 a *stable (st) model* of \mathcal{D} , iff $v^{-1}(\mathbf{t})$ equals $v_{gr}^{-1}(\mathbf{t})$ of the grounded model v_{gr}
 410 of the reduced ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\downarrow v}$.

411 Essentially, in the reduced ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\downarrow v}$, the occurrences of arguments that
 412 are assigned \mathbf{f} by v are replaced by their truth value and it is verified that
 413 the grounded model of this reduct evaluates the same arguments to \mathbf{t} as the
 414 stable model of \mathcal{D} .

415 Finally, we also consider *strong admissibility* as characterised by Ke-
 416 shavarzi Zafarghandi et al. (2022) for ADFs. For that, we first introduce
 417 the notion of *strong justification*³ of an argument wrt. an interpretation in
 418 an ADF.

419 **Definition 2.13.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an
 420 interpretation. An argument a is *strongly justified* in v wrt. the set $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$
 421 iff it holds that either

- 422 • $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$ and there exists $P \subseteq \text{par}(a) \setminus E$, such that $\phi_a^{[p/x : p \in P \wedge v(p) = \mathbf{x}]} \in$
 423 $\text{TAUT}(\mathcal{A})$ and all $p \in P$ are strongly justified in v wrt. $E \cup \{p\}$, or
- 424 • $v(a) = \mathbf{f}$ and there exists $P \subseteq \text{par}(a) \setminus E$, such that $\phi_a^{[p/x : p \in P \wedge v(p) = \mathbf{x}]} \in$
 425 $\text{UNSAT}(\mathcal{A})$ and all $p \in P$ are strongly justified in v wrt. $E \cup \{p\}$.

426 The intuition behind this is the same as that of strong defense in the case
 427 of abstract argumentation frameworks (cf. Definition 2.5): to be strongly

³Following the notation of Keshavarzi Zafarghandi et al. (2022), we use the term *strongly justified* to refer to both accepted as well rejected arguments wrt. some interpretation v . The intuition behind this is that the argument's status is justified in the interpretation, not just its acceptance.

428 justified an argument cannot be involved in its own justification. More specif-
 429 ically, for an argument to be strongly justified in v it must first be assigned
 430 \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} by v . Then, it must be the case that there is a subset P of its parents
 431 such that its acceptance condition, where all occurrences of arguments $p \in P$
 432 are replaced by their truth value, is a tautology, respectively unsatisfiable if
 433 $v(a) = \mathbf{f}$. Finally, each parent $p \in P$ must then be strongly justified in v .
 434 Based on this, the notion of strong admissibility can then be generalised to
 435 ADFs (Keshavarzi Zafarghandi et al., 2022).

436 **Definition 2.14.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF. An interpretation $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto$
 437 $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is called a *strongly admissible (sa) model* of \mathcal{D} iff for each $a \in v^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \cup$
 438 $v^{-1}(\mathbf{f})$ it holds that a is strongly justified in v .

439 With $\sigma(\mathcal{D})$ we denote the set of σ -models of \mathcal{D} for all semantics $\sigma \in$
 440 $\{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{val}_2, \text{st}\}$.

Figure 4: The ADF \mathcal{D}_2 from Example 2.5.

441 **Example 2.5.** Consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_2 in Figure 4. The ADF has the grounded
 442 model

$$v_1 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{f}\},$$

443 and two preferred models

$$v_2 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{f}\},$$

$$v_3 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{t}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}.$$

444 All three models are complete and the latter two are also two-valued models.
 445 However, only v_2 is a stable model. Regarding that, note that in $\mathcal{D}_{2, \downarrow v_3}$ we
 446 have for the grounded model v_{gr} of $\mathcal{D}_{2, \downarrow v_3}$ that $v_{\text{gr}}^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) = \{c\}$ but $v_1^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) =$
 447 $\{a, b, c\}$. The ADF \mathcal{D}_2 also has three strongly admissible models: $v_{\mathbf{u}}$, v_1 and

$$v_4 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}.$$

448 In particular, in v_1 we have that the acceptance condition of c is a tautology
 449 and d is strongly justified in v_1 given c , because substituting c with its truth
 450 value $v_1(c) = \mathbf{t}$ in the acceptance condition of d results in an unsatisfiable
 451 formula.

452 We also establish how to connect AFs with ADFs. For a given argu-
 453 mentation framework $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, we define the corresponding ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ as
 454 follows.

455 **Definition 2.15.** Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF. Then, we define the ADF
 456 $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$, where \mathcal{A} is the same set of arguments and \mathcal{C} is defined as
 457 $\{\phi_a = \bigwedge_{b \in a_{\overline{\mathcal{F}}}} \neg b\}_{a \in \mathcal{A}}$.

458 Furthermore, for some ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and a given interpretation v of
 459 $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, we define the unique extension E_v corresponding to v as

$$E_v = v^{-1}(\mathbf{t}). \quad (4)$$

460 It can then be shown that the admissibility-based semantics for ADFs
 461 defined via the characteristic operator $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ are equivalent to the respective
 462 semantics for AFs.

463 **Theorem 2.1** (Brewka et al. (2013)). *Let \mathcal{F} be an AF, $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corre-
 464 sponding ADF and $\sigma \in \{\mathit{ad}, \mathit{gr}, \mathit{co}, \mathit{pr}\}$ is a semantics. v is a σ -model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$
 465 if and only if E_v is a σ -extension of \mathcal{F} .*

466 In Section 5, we will consider abstract dialectical frameworks in detail
 467 and introduce initial models and serialisation sequences for them.

468 3. Serialisability in Abstract Argumentation

469 We now recall the definition of initial sets (Xu and Cayrol, 2018) and
 470 the notion of serialisability (Thimm, 2022), which is based on them. Seri-
 471 alisability provides a procedural construction scheme for the extensions of
 472 admissibility-based semantics, which we will analyse in detail over the course
 473 of this work.

474 Non-empty minimal admissible sets have been coined *initial sets* by Xu
 475 and Cayrol (2016).

476 **Definition 3.1.** For $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ with $S \neq \emptyset$ is called an *initial*
 477 *set* if S is admissible and there is no admissible $S' \subsetneq S$ with $S' \neq \emptyset$.

478 **Example 3.1.** We continue Example 2.1 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_2
 479 depicted in Figure 2. We have two initial sets $\{a\}$ and $\{d\}$. While a is not
 480 attacked at all, d is attacked by c , but defends itself. Clearly, since both
 481 sets contain only one argument they are \subseteq -minimal among the non-empty
 482 admissible sets.

483 With $\text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ we denote the set of initial sets of \mathcal{F} . Initial sets can also be
 484 understood as resolutions to atomic conflicts in an AF (Thimm, 2022) which
 485 essentially makes them the atomic semantical units of an AF. We differentiate
 486 between three types of initial sets (Thimm, 2022).

487 **Definition 3.2.** For $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$, we say that

- 488 1. S is *unattacked* iff $S_{\mathcal{F}}^- = \emptyset$,
- 489 2. S is *unchallenged* iff $S_{\mathcal{F}}^- \neq \emptyset$ and there is no $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ with $S'\mathcal{R}S$,
- 490 3. S is *challenged* iff there is $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ with $S'\mathcal{R}S$.

491 In the following, we denote with $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$, $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$, and $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})$ the set of
 492 unattacked, unchallenged, and challenged initial sets, respectively.

493 **Example 3.2.** We continue Example 3.1 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_2
 494 depicted in Figure 2. We have that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_2) = \{\{a\}, \{d\}\}$. The set $\{a\}$ is
 495 clearly an unattacked initial set, because a is not attacked in \mathcal{F}_2 . On the
 496 other hand, $\{d\}$ is an unchallenged initial set, because it is attacked by c but
 497 c is not contained in any initial set of \mathcal{F}_2 . Consider now the reduct $\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}$, i. e.,
 498 we remove a and b from \mathcal{F}_2 . In this AF, we have two initial sets, namely $\{c\}$
 499 and $\{d\}$. Both attack each other and thus they are both challenged initial
 500 sets of $\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}$.

501 We recall *serialisability* (Thimm, 2022), which is a property of a semantics
 502 that allows us to characterise extensions in a semi-constructive manner. We
 503 describe this construction scheme in form of a non-deterministic transition
 504 system, called *serialisation system*. A state T of that serialisation system
 505 is a tuple (\mathcal{F}, E) consisting of an argumentation framework \mathcal{F} and a set
 506 of arguments E . The transition from one serialisation state to another is
 507 guided by a *selection function* and a *termination function* defines whether
 508 the current state is final.

509 **Definition 3.3.** A *serialisation state* T is a tuple $T = (\mathcal{F}, E)$ with $\mathcal{F} \in \mathbb{AF}$
 510 and $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}$.

511 **Definition 3.4.** A *selection function* α is any function $\alpha : 2^{2^{\mathbb{A}}} \times 2^{2^{\mathbb{A}}} \times 2^{2^{\mathbb{A}}} \rightarrow$
 512 $2^{2^{\mathbb{A}}}$ with $\alpha(X, Y, Z) \subseteq X \cup Y \cup Z$ for all $X, Y, Z \subseteq 2^{\mathbb{A}}$.

513 We will apply a selection function α in the form $\alpha(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}))$
 514 (for some \mathcal{F}), so α selects a subset of the initial sets as eligible to be selected
 515 in the construction process. We explicitly differentiate the different types of
 516 initial sets as parameters here as a technical convenience.

517 **Definition 3.5.** A *termination function* β is any function $\beta : \mathbb{AF} \times 2^{\mathbb{A}} \rightarrow$
 518 $\{0, 1\}$.

519 A termination function β is used to indicate when a construction of an
 520 extension is finished, which will be the case if $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$.

521 Together, a selection function α and a termination function β induce the
 522 $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system based on the following transition rule:

$$(\mathcal{F}, E) \xrightarrow{S \in \alpha(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}))} (\mathcal{F}^S, E \cup S)$$

523 If (\mathcal{F}', E') can be reached from (\mathcal{F}, E) with the above rule via a finite number
 524 of steps, including no steps at all, we also write $(\mathcal{F}, E) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha} (\mathcal{F}', E')$. Addi-
 525 tionally, if the state (\mathcal{F}', E') also satisfies the termination criterion of β , i. e.,
 526 $\beta(\mathcal{F}', E') = 1$, then we write $(\mathcal{F}, E) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}', E')$.

527 Given an argumentation framework \mathcal{F} and concrete instances of α and β ,
 528 let $\mathcal{E}^{\alpha, \beta}(\mathcal{F})$ be the set of all E such that $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}', E)$.

529 **Definition 3.6.** A semantics σ is *serialisable* if there exists a selection func-
 530 tion α and a termination function β with $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \mathcal{E}^{\alpha, \beta}(\mathcal{F})$ for all AFs \mathcal{F} .

531 It can then be shown that a wide variety of existing admissibility-based
 532 semantics are serialisable.

533 **Theorem 3.1** (Thimm (2022)).

534 *Admissibility is serialisable via*

$$\alpha_{ad}(X, Y, Z) = X \cup Y \cup Z, \quad \beta_{ad}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1.$$

535 *Complete semantics is serialisable via α_{ad} and*

$$\beta_{co}(\mathcal{F}, E) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

536 *Preferred semantics is serialisable via α_{ad} and*

$$\beta_{pr}(\mathcal{F}, E) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } is(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

537 *Strong admissibility is serialisable via α_{gr} and β_{ad} .*

538 *Grounded semantics is serialisable via*

$$\alpha_{gr}(X, Y, Z) = X$$

539 *and β_{co} .*

540 *Stable semantics is serialisable via α_{ad} and*

$$\beta_{st}(\mathcal{F}, E) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mathcal{F} = (\emptyset, \emptyset) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

541 Note that the above functions to serialise these semantics are not nec-
 542 essarily unique, i. e., they may be different ways so serialise these seman-
 543 tics. For instance, one can formulate the termination condition in a different
 544 way to achieve the same result. Alternatively, the selection function may
 545 be modified, for instance, to include some kind of priority order to restrict
 546 the selection, which can still yield the same extensions in the end. We will
 547 however not consider this aspect further in this work. Instead, we will, in
 548 Section 4, develop a property-based approach to analyse which selection and
 549 termination functions are well-behaved.

550 In addition to the above semantics known from the literature, we also
 551 consider the unchallenged semantics (**uc**) which is characterised directly in
 552 terms of serialisability, cf. (Thimm, 2022; Bengel and Thimm, 2022).

553 **Definition 3.7.** Let $\alpha_{uc}(X, Y, Z) = X \cup Y$ and

$$\beta_{uc}(\mathcal{F}, E) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } is^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) \cup is^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

554 We define $uc(\mathcal{F}) = \mathcal{E}^{\alpha_{uc}, \beta_{uc}}(\mathcal{F})$ to be the set of *unchallenged* extensions of \mathcal{F} .

Example 3.3. We continue Example 3.2 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_2 in Figure 2. We consider the complete semantics with the selection function α_{ad} and termination function β_{co} . As shown before, we have $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_2) = \{\{a\}\}$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_2) = \{\{d\}\}$. Thus, it follows that $\alpha_{\text{ad}}(\{\{a\}\}, \{\{d\}\}, \emptyset) = \{\{a\}, \{d\}\}$. We start with the state $(\mathcal{F}_2, \emptyset)$, for which the termination function returns 0, because there is the unattacked initial set $\{a\}$. We select $\{a\}$ from α_{ad} , i. e., we transition

$$(\mathcal{F}_2, \emptyset) \xrightarrow{\{a\}} (\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}, \{a\}).$$

As already shown in Example 3.2, we have $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}) = \{\{c\}, \{d\}\}$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}) = \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}) = \emptyset$. It follows that $\beta_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}, \{a\}) = 1$, i. e., $\{a\}$ is a complete extension of \mathcal{F}_2 . Lets continue by selecting $\{c\}$ and transition

$$(\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}, \{a\}) \xrightarrow{\{c\}} (\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a,c\}}, \{a, c\}).$$

In the reduct $\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a,c\}} = (\{e, f\}, \{(e, f), (f, e), (f, f)\})$, we only have one initial set $\{e\}$, which is unchallenged. That means $\beta_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a,c\}}, \{a, c\}) = 1$ and we can also transition as

$$(\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a,c\}}, \{a, c\}) \xrightarrow{\{e\}} (\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a,c,e\}}, \{a, c, e\}).$$

555 The remaining AF $\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a,c,e\}} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$ is the empty AF and thus β_{co} is satisfied
556 trivially.

557 In Figure 5, the full co-serialisation of \mathcal{F}_2 is shown. For readability, we
558 omit the AF in each step, since it can be reconstructed easily based on the
559 original AF and the constructed set of each serialisation state. In **bold**,
560 we highlight the serialisation states that correspond to co-extensions. Be-
561 sides the above discussed serialisation process, there also exist two further
562 sequences, corresponding to the co-extension $\{a, d\}$. They can be obtained
563 by selecting the initial set $\{d\}$ in either \mathcal{F}_2 or the reduct $\mathcal{F}_2^{\{a\}}$.

564 Finally, Figure 6 depicts the serialisation of \mathcal{F}_2 for the unchallenged se-
565 mantics, which we leave for the reader to verify. The key difference here is
566 that, in contrast to the complete semantics, challenged initial sets cannot be
567 selected by α_{uc} .

568 Sometimes we are only interested in the sequence(s) of selected initial
569 sets in which case the selection and termination functions are not relevant.
570 In those cases we consider the *serialisation sequences* defined as follows, cf.
571 (Blümel and Thimm, 2022).

- 590 • $E \in \mathit{pr}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n)
591 with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and it holds that $\mathit{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$.
- 592 • $E \in \mathit{sa}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n)
593 with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and for all S_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds that
594 $S_i \in \mathit{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$.
- 595 • $E \in \mathit{gr}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n)
596 with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and for all S_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds that
597 $S_i \in \mathit{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ and it holds that $\mathit{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$.
- 598 • $E \in \mathit{st}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n)
599 with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and it holds that $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.
- 600 • $E \in \mathit{uc}(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if there is a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n)
601 with $E = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$ and for all S_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, it holds that $S_i \in$
602 $\mathit{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}) \cup \mathit{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$ and it holds that $\mathit{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) \cup$
603 $\mathit{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}) = \emptyset$.

604 We denote with $\Sigma_s = \{\mathit{ad}, \mathit{co}, \mathit{pr}, \mathit{sa}, \mathit{gr}, \mathit{st}, \mathit{uc}\}$ the set of *serialisable* seman-
605 tics, with their corresponding selection and termination function as described
606 in Theorem 3.1 and Definition 3.7. For an argumentation framework \mathcal{F} , we
607 denote with $\mathfrak{S}_\sigma(\mathcal{F})$ the set of all σ -serialisation sequences of \mathcal{F} .

608 **Example 3.4.** We continue Example 3.3 and consider again the AF \mathcal{F}_2 in
609 Figure 2. For the complete semantics, we have the **co**-serialisation sequences
610 $(\{a\})$, $(\{a\}, \{c\})$, $(\{a\}, \{d\})$, $(\{d\}, \{a\})$ and $(\{a\}, \{c\}, \{e\})$. In particular,
611 $(\{a\}, \{d\})$ and $(\{d\}, \{a\})$ correspond to the same **co**-extension, representing
612 two different way to arrive there, while for the other **co**-extensions only a
613 single order of construction exists. The latter three sequences are also **pr**-
614 serialisation sequences. Finally, only $(\{a\})$ and $(\{d\}, \{a\})$ are **uc**-serialisation
615 sequences. One may also verify this via the graphical representation of the
616 serialisation for **co** and **uc** depicted in Figures 5 and 6. Here, a serialisation
617 sequence corresponds to the sequence of edge labels of a directed path starting
618 from \emptyset and ending at some node marked in bold font.

619 4. A Formal Analysis of Serialisable Semantics

620 Serialisability serves as an alternative view on argumentation semantics.
621 In the classical extension-based approach as introduced by Dung (1995), the

622 semantic results are simply represented as a set of accepted arguments. One
623 can then infer that all other arguments are rejected which gives us a simple bi-
624 nary classification of arguments. A bit more granular are the labeling-based
625 semantics (Jakobovits and Vermeir, 1999; Caminada and Gabbay, 2009),
626 where arguments are classified into accepted, rejected, and undecided argu-
627 ments. However, what both of these approaches have in common is that
628 they represent a merely static viewpoint of the semantics. In particular, it is
629 not possible to discern in which way arguments of the extension or labeling
630 defend each other and whether they have to be accepted in a specific order,
631 because of these dependencies. On the other hand, serialisability enables a
632 sequence-based representation for the semantics which allows us to encode
633 this kind of information directly into the semantic representation.

634 **Example 4.1.** Recall the motivating argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_1 in Fig-
635 ure 1. There is only one preferred extension of \mathcal{F}_1 , namely $\{a, c, e\}$. From this
636 set alone, we are unable to infer anything about the underlying reasoning pro-
637 cess that lead to this conclusion. Conversely, using the serialisation system
638 for the preferred semantics yields the pr-serialisation sequence $(\{a\}, \{c, e\})$.
639 This sequence explicitly contains the information that a is accepted before
640 c and e and subsequently that c and e can only be accepted together since
641 they require each other for their defense.

642 In the literature, the principle-based approach to evaluate argumentation
643 semantics has long been established (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007; van der
644 Torre and Vesic, 2018). There exist many different principles for semantics
645 which cover different desirable aspects of semantics. For instance, there is
646 the principle of *I-Maximality* which states that no extensions should be in
647 a strict subset relation with each other. Notably, these principles are gen-
648 erally defined with the extension-based or labeling-based approach in mind.
649 Meaning, they do not consider the procedural aspect of argumentation. An
650 example for that is the already mentioned *I-Maximality* principle, where the
651 maximality of the extensions is simply defined via \subseteq -maximality, which is
652 not really meaningful in the context of an argumentative reasoning process.

653 To address the above issues and to enhance the scope of analysis for
654 argumentation semantics, our contribution in this section is twofold. First,
655 in Section 4.1, we establish properties for serialisable semantics that allow
656 us to formalise different aspects of the argumentative process modelled by
657 a serialisation system. Subsequently, we investigate in detail the relation

658 between serialisation properties and known argumentation principles from
 659 the literature in Section 4.2.

660 4.1. Properties for Serialisable Semantics

661 In the following, we will thoroughly investigate serialisable semantics and
 662 the behaviour of the underlying extension construction process. For that, we
 663 introduce properties for selection and termination functions of the seman-
 664 tics⁴. These properties then allow us to further characterise the serialisation
 665 systems of the different semantics and we will relate them to correspond-
 666 ing principles for the extension-based view on semantics in the subsequent
 667 section.

668 As in the case of extension-based semantics, there are some basic proper-
 669 ties that we want any serialisable semantics to satisfy. The first property that
 670 we introduce is $\alpha\beta$ -abstraction, which simply states that every decision made
 671 by selection and termination functions must be independent of the names of
 672 arguments and thus only depend solely on the structure of the argumentation
 673 framework. This corresponds directly to the well established Language Inde-
 674 pendence principle (also sometimes called Abstraction) for extension-based
 675 (van der Torre and Vesic, 2018) and ranking semantics (Bonzon et al., 2016).

676 **Property 1.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We say
 677 that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *abstract*, if and only if for all argumenta-
 678 tion frameworks $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}'$ and $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ it holds that $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\mathbf{m}} \mathcal{F}'$ implies

$$\alpha(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}'), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}'), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}')) = \{\mathbf{m}(S) \mid S \in \alpha(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}))\}$$

679 and $\beta(\mathcal{F}', \mathbf{m}(E)) = \beta(\mathcal{F}, E)$.

680 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -abstract if there exist α and
 681 β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is abstract.

682 **Example 4.2.** Consider the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_3 in Figure 7. We
 683 have that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_3) = \{\{e\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, d\}\}$. Consider the selection function

$$\alpha_a(X, Y, Z) = \{S \in X \cup Y \cup Z \mid a \in S\}$$

⁴We explicitly call them (serialisation) properties to distinguish them from the princi-
 ples for extension-based semantics introduced in Section 2.2.

Figure 7: The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_3 from Examples 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4.

684 which returns all initial sets that contain the argument a . Thus, we have that
 685 $\alpha_a(\emptyset, \emptyset, \{\{e\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, d\}\}) = \{\{a, c\}\}$. It is then easy to see, that α_a is not
 686 abstract because renaming the arguments would change the outcome of α_a .
 687 In contrast to that, all of the selection and termination functions introduced
 688 in Theorem 3.1 are abstract.

689 Let us focus now on the selection function. To ensure a well-formed
 690 construction of extensions, we want some form of consistency when applying
 691 the selection function to consecutive reducts. More specifically, if some set
 692 S is an initial set of a specific type in the argumentation framework \mathcal{F} and
 693 selectable by α in \mathcal{F} , then it should be selectable via α in every AF where S
 694 is the same type of initial set.

695 **Property 2.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We say
 696 that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *monotonous*, if and only if for all argumen-
 697 tation frameworks $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}'$ and every $S \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ such that $S \in \tau(\mathcal{F})$ and $S \in \tau(\mathcal{F}')$
 698 with $\tau \in \{\text{is}^\neq, \text{is}^{\neq}, \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}\}$ it holds that $S \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}))$ implies
 699 $S \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}'), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}'), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}'))$.

700 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -monotonous if there exist α
 701 and β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is monotonous. This
 702 property ensures that the selection criteria is independent of arbitrary or
 703 meta-level criteria.

704 **Example 4.3.** Consider again the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_3 in Figure 7.
 705 For instance, consider the selection function

$$\alpha_m(X, Y, Z) = \{S \in X \cup Y \cup Z \mid \forall S' \in X \cup Y \cup Z : |S| \leq |S'|\}$$

706 that returns the cardinality minimal sets for each argumentation framework.
 707 Let us first consider the restriction $\mathcal{F}_3|_{\{a,b,c,d\}}$. For $\mathcal{F}_3|_{\{a,b,c,d\}}$, we then have

708 $\alpha_m(\emptyset, \emptyset, \{\{a, c\}, \{b, d\}\}) = \{\{a, c\}, \{b, d\}\}$. In contrast to that, for \mathcal{F}_3 we
709 have $\alpha_m(\emptyset, \emptyset, \{\{e\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, d\}\}) = \{\{e\}\}$, even though $\{a, c\}$ and $\{b, d\}$ are
710 challenged initial sets of both argumentation frameworks. It follows that α_m
711 is not monotonous. On the other hand, any selection function, e. g., α_{gr} or
712 α_{ad} , that simply returns all unattacked, unchallenged or challenged initial
713 sets (or a combination of them) is clearly monotonous because this decision
714 does not depend on a comparison to other initial sets.

715 We turn now towards basic properties that are concerned with the ter-
716 mination function in particular. The first property that we consider is $\alpha\beta$ -
717 *composability*. Essentially, this property ensures that if the termination func-
718 tion returns true for two disjunct argumentation frameworks, then it must
719 also return true for the composition of these two argumentation frameworks.

720 **Property 3.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We say
721 that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *composable*, if and only if for all argumen-
722 tation frameworks $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}'$ and $E, E' \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ such that \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}' are disjunct it
723 holds that if $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ and $\beta(\mathcal{F}', E') = 1$, then $\beta(\mathcal{F} \sqcup \mathcal{F}', E \cup E') = 1$.

724 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -composable if there exist α and
725 β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is composable. Similarly to
726 α -monotonicity, this ensures that the termination function does not decide
727 based on arbitrary meta-level criteria, e. g., the number of arguments in the
728 argumentation frameworks.

729 **Example 4.4.** Consider again the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_3 in Figure 7.
730 Let β_c be a termination function defined as $\beta_c((\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}), E) = 1$ if $|\mathcal{A}| = 1$
731 and $\beta_c(\mathcal{F}, E) = 0$ otherwise. We then have $\beta_c(\mathcal{F}_3^{\{b, d\}}, \{b, d\}) = 1$ and also
732 $\beta_c(\mathcal{F}_3^{\{d, e\}}, \{d, e\}) = 1$. It is easy to see that $\mathcal{F}_3^{\{b, d\}}$ and $\mathcal{F}_3^{\{d, e\}}$ are disjunct.
733 However, after combining both, we have $\beta_c(\mathcal{F}_3^{\{b, d\}} \sqcup \mathcal{F}_3^{\{d, e\}}, \{b, d, e\}) = 0$,
734 because the resulting argumentation framework does not have exactly one
735 argument any more, hence β_c is not composable. In contrast to that, for
736 instance, the termination function β_{st} is composable since the union of two
737 empty argumentation frameworks is still the empty framework which leaves
738 the termination criterion intact.

739 Finally, we also need to consider that the serialisable semantics represent
740 a process. A central aspect of many processes (in particular in a compu-
741 tational context) is the Markov property (Dynkin, 1965), which states that

742 each step of a process must be independent of the previous steps. While orig-
 743 inally introduced for stochastic processes, it has been adapted to many other
 744 formalisms including abstract argumentation (Rienstra et al., 2020). While
 745 that work introduced a Markov property in the context of the SCCs of an
 746 argumentation framework, we define here a version specifically tailored to the
 747 serialisation process. Essentially, the $\alpha\beta$ -Markov property states that decid-
 748 ing the termination of a state (\mathcal{F}, E) is independent of E , which contains the
 749 information about the previous serialisation steps.

750 **Property 4.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We
 751 say that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *Markovian*, if and only if for all argu-
 752 mentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ it holds that $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ implies
 753 $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E') = 1$ for all $E' \subseteq \mathbb{A}$.

754 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -Markovian if there exist α and
 755 β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is Markovian. It should also
 756 be noted that the selection function is naturally independent of previous steps
 757 as it only receives the initial sets of the current argumentation framework as
 758 input.

759 **Example 4.5.** Consider some termination function β_m defined as $\beta_m(\mathcal{F}, E) =$
 760 1 if $|E| < 2$ and $\beta_m(\mathcal{F}, E) = 0$ otherwise. Let \mathcal{F} be some arbitrary argu-
 761 mentation framework. We have that $\beta_m(\mathcal{F}, \{a\}) = 1$, but clearly for any set
 762 S with $|S| > 1$ we have $\beta_m(\mathcal{F}, S) = 0$ and thus β_m is not Markovian. In
 763 contrast to that, the termination functions of Theorem 3.1 only depend on
 764 the given argumentation framework and are therefore Markovian.

765 As the following result shows, all of these basic properties for selection
 766 and termination functions are indeed satisfied by every existing serialisable
 767 semantics.

768 **Theorem 4.1.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
 769 *rem 3.1. Then the following statements hold*

- 770 1. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -abstract,
- 771 2. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -Markovian,
- 772 3. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -monotonous,
- 773 4. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -composable.

Proof: P. 77

Figure 8: The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_4 from Examples 4.6, 4.7 and 4.8.

774 In the following, we will assume that every serialisable semantics satisfies
 775 the above introduced properties. We will also refer to a serialisable semantics
 776 σ that satisfies Properties 1–4 as *properly serialisable*.

777 While the above introduced properties should be uncontroversial and it is
 778 fair to assume that every well-behaved semantics should satisfy them, we will
 779 now consider further properties, that are desirable but might not generally be
 780 considered necessary for all semantics. The first such property is $\alpha\beta$ -closure.
 781 Intuitively, a serialisable semantics satisfies $\alpha\beta$ -closure iff every path of the
 782 serialisation system eventually leads to a terminating state, i. e., some σ -
 783 extension. In other words, the extension construction cannot run into any
 784 dead-ends.

785 **Property 5.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We say
 786 that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *closed*, iff for all argumentation frame-
 787 works \mathcal{F} and every state (\mathcal{F}', E') with $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}', E')$ it holds that
 788 $\alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}'), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}'), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}')) = \emptyset$ implies $\beta(\mathcal{F}', E') = 1$.

789 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed if there exist α and β
 790 that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is closed. As the following
 791 result shows $\alpha\beta$ -closure is satisfied by most serialisable semantics.

792 **Theorem 4.2.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
 793 *rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{uc}\}$. Proof: P. 78*

794 This property is not satisfied by the stable semantics, as shown in the
 795 following example.

796 **Example 4.6.** Consider the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_4 in Figure 8. The
 797 serialisation of \mathcal{F}_4 wrt. stable semantics is depicted in Figure 9. As we can
 798 see, in \mathcal{F}_4 the selection function gives us two options: $\{a\}$ and $\{d\}$. However,
 799 only if we select $\{d\}$ here will the serialisation be able to reach a terminat-
 800 ing state, i. e., a stable extension. Otherwise, we may only reach the set

Figure 9: The st-serialisation of \mathcal{F}_4 from Example 4.6.

801 $\{a, d\}$, for which the selection function wrt. $\mathcal{F}^{\{a, d\}}$ is empty, but we have
 802 that $\beta(\mathcal{F}^{\{a, d\}}, \{a, d\}) = 0$.

803 The next property that we introduce for serialisable semantics is $\alpha\beta$ -
 804 maximality. Related to that is the *I-Maximality* principle for extension-
 805 based semantics, which is generally considered to be an important property
 806 and satisfied by many semantics (van der Torre and Vesic, 2018). Thus is
 807 makes sense to adapt this idea to our process-based approach to semantics.
 808 A serialisation system for functions α and β is then considered maximal,
 809 iff the termination of a state implies that there exists no further transition
 810 wrt. α .

811 **Property 6.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We
 812 say that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *maximal*, if and only if for all ar-
 813 gumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ it holds that $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ implies
 814 $\alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) = \emptyset$.

815 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal if there exist α and
 816 β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is maximal. This property
 817 is satisfied by preferred, grounded, stable and unchallenged semantics, which
 818 is fairly easy to see from their respective termination functions.

819 **Theorem 4.3.** Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-
 820 rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}\}$. *Proof:* P. 80

821 For (strongly) admissible sets it is easy to see that the property is not
 822 satisfied because the termination function returns true for every state. For
 823 the complete semantics consider the following example.

824 **Example 4.7.** Consider again the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_4 in Figure 8.
 825 The serialisation of \mathcal{F}_4 wrt. complete semantics is depicted in Figure 10. For
 826 the set $\{d\}$ we have $\beta_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}_4^{\{d\}}, \{d\}) = 1$, i. e., $\{d\}$ is a complete extension of \mathcal{F}_4 .
 827 However, we have $\alpha_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}_4^{\{d\}}) = \{\{a\}, \{b\}\}$ and thus co is not $\alpha\beta$ -maximal.

Figure 10: The co-serialisation of \mathcal{F}_4 from Example 4.7.

828 Another prominent principle for extension-based semantics is *Reinstatement*
 829 (van der Torre and Vesic, 2018). It states that every argument defended
 830 by any σ -extension should be included in that extension. This can be trans-
 831 lated to serialisation quite neatly by considering the unattacked initial sets
 832 of the reduct wrt. some set S . If there is no unattacked initial set in the
 833 S -reduct, then there is no defended argument that is not included in S . This
 834 is formulated as the $\alpha\beta$ -reinstatement property as follows.

835 **Property 7.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We
 836 say that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *reinstating*, if and only if for all ar-
 837 gumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} and $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ it holds that $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ implies
 838 $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$.

839 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating if there exist α
 840 and β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is reinstating. As one
 841 might expect, this property is satisfied by complete, preferred, grounded,
 842 stable and unchallenged semantics, which are exactly the semantics that also
 843 satisfy the *Reinstatement* principle.

844 **Theorem 4.4.** Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-
 845 rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}\}$. *Proof:* P. 81

846 **Example 4.8.** Consider again the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_4 in Figure 8.
 847 The serialisation wrt. complete semantics is shown in Figure 10. In all three
 848 states where the termination function β_{co} returns 1, i. e., for $\{d\}$, $\{a, d\}$
 849 and $\{b, d\}$ it is easy to see, that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}') = \emptyset$ with \mathcal{F}' being the respec-
 850 tive reduct. On the other hand, for the (strongly) admissible sets, we also
 851 have $\beta_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) = 1$ but clearly $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}) = \{\{d\}\}$ and thus **ad (sa)** is not $\alpha\beta$ -
 852 reinstating.

853 Recall that we have the possibility to distinguish between three types of
 854 initial sets within the selection function. In particular, challenged initial sets

855 represent controversial viewpoints, since there exists by definition another ac-
 856 ceptable set that challenges it. Thus, accepting such a set inherently means
 857 a decision is made that will also explicitly rule out other arguments from
 858 acceptance. This might not always be desirable, e. g., the grounded seman-
 859 tics represents essentially the least common ground of acceptable arguments
 860 in the argumentation framework. To capture this difference, we introduce
 861 the property of $\alpha\beta$ -cautiousness which requires a semantics to never select
 862 controversial sets.

863 **Property 8.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We say
 864 that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *cautious*, if and only if for all argumenta-
 865 tion frameworks \mathcal{F} it holds that $\alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) \cap \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$.

866 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -cautious if there exist α and β
 867 that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is cautious. It is easy to see,
 868 that strong admissibility as well as the grounded and unchallenged semantics
 869 satisfy $\alpha\beta$ -cautiousness and all other semantics do not.

870 **Theorem 4.5.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
 871 *rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -cautious for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{uc}\}$. *Proof: P. 81**

872 For all other serialisable semantics, the statement does not hold as illus-
 873 trated by the following example.

874 **Example 4.9.** Consider for instance the AF $\mathcal{F} = (\{a, b\}, \{(a, b), (b, a)\})$ with
 875 $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}) = \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ and $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}) = \{\{a\}, \{b\}\}$. The semantics **ad**, **co**, **pr** and
 876 **st** are serialisable with the selection function α_{ad} . Then, we have $\{a\} \in$
 877 $\alpha_{\text{ad}}(\emptyset, \emptyset, \{\{a\}, \{b\}\})$. Since $\{a\} \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})$, it follows that **ad**, **co**, **pr**, **st** are not
 878 α_{ad} -cautious.

879 We also consider a strengthened version of the $\alpha\beta$ -cautiousness property,
 880 which will be useful to distinguish between semantics that allow self-defense
 881 and those that do not.

882 **Property 9.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We
 883 say that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *strictly cautious*, if and only if for
 884 all argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} it holds that $\alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq$
 885 $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F})$.

886 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious if there exist
 887 α and β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is strictly cautious.
 888 As expected, strict $\alpha\beta$ -cautiousness is only satisfied by strong admissibility
 889 and the grounded semantics.

890 **Theorem 4.6.** Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-
891 rem 3.1. Then, σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious for $\sigma \in \{\mathbf{sa}, \mathbf{gr}\}$. *Proof:* P. 81

892 For all other serialisable semantics, the statement does not hold.

893 **Example 4.10.** Consider the AF $\mathcal{F} = (\{a, b\}, \{(a, b), (b, a), (b, b)\})$. We have
894 that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}) = \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ and $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) = \{\{a\}\}$. Thus, $\{a\} \in \alpha(\emptyset, \{\{a\}\}, \emptyset)$
895 for $\alpha \in \{\alpha_{\text{ad}}, \alpha_{\text{uc}}\}$. Since $\{a\} \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$, it follows that any serialisation
896 system with these selection functions is not strictly cautious.

897 We now turn to a property that is specifically concerned with the pro-
898 cedural aspect of the serialisation system. As mentioned before, an initial
899 set represents an atomic semantical unit and can also be considered as the
900 resolution of an atomic conflict in the argumentation framework. If the selec-
901 tion function of some semantics now allows the selection of some initial set,
902 that implicitly means the extension under construction will get involved in
903 the associated atomic conflict. Assume however that we select another unre-
904 lated initial set in the construction process. In order to have a well-founded
905 serialisation system, it is only sensible that if a selection functions allows
906 involvement in an atomic conflict in one state, then it must allow that in
907 every following state as well. In other words, if an initial set is selectable in
908 some state, then in every follow-up state it must either be accepted, rejected
909 (via accepting some challenging initial set) or still be acceptable. This is
910 formulated as the $\alpha\beta$ -confluence property as follows.

911 **Property 10.** Let α and β be a selection and termination function. We
912 say that the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is *confluent*, if and only if for all AFs
913 $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and any $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $S \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}))$ it holds
914 for any state (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) with $(\mathcal{F}, E) \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1)$:

- 915 (1) $S \subseteq E_1$, or
- 916 (2) $S^- \cap E_1 \neq \emptyset$, or
- 917 (3) $(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}^{E_1 \cup S}, E_1 \cup S)$.

918 For some semantics σ , we say that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent if there exist α and
919 β that serialise σ and the $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system is confluent. The following
920 example illustrates the intuition behind the confluence property.

Figure 11: The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_5 from Example 4.11.

(a) The reduct $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{a\}}$.

(b) The reduct $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{c\}}$.

(c) The reduct $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{b,c\}}$.

Figure 12: Reducts of \mathcal{F}_5 from Example 4.11.

921 **Example 4.11.** Consider the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_5 in Figure 11. We
 922 have the initial sets: $\{a\}$, $\{c\}$ and $\{e, f\}$. Assume all three sets are selectable
 923 by some selection function α and consider the set $\{e, f\}$. Lets say, instead
 924 of $\{e, f\}$ we select $\{a\}$ first, i. e., we transition $(\mathcal{F}_5, \emptyset) \xrightarrow{\{a\}} (\mathcal{F}_5^{\{a\}}, \{a\})$. The
 925 reduct $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{a\}}$ is depicted in Figure 12a. Clearly, in this framework $\{e, f\}$ is
 926 still an initial set and thus should be selectable by any confluent selection
 927 function α . Alternatively, such a selection function could allow selecting
 928 $\{d, g\}$, which is also an initial set and attacks the set $\{e, f\}$, thus resolving
 929 the same underlying atomic conflict (cf. condition (2) of Property 10).

930 On the hand, we can select $\{c\}$ in the first step. In the corresponding
 931 reduct $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{c\}}$, shown in Figure 12b, $\{e, f\}$ is still an initial set and thus should
 932 be directly selectable by α . However, there is also the unattacked initial set
 933 $\{b\}$. Assuming that $\{b\}$ is also selectable by α , we arrive at the reduct $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{b,c\}}$
 934 (see Figure 12c). In this reduct $\{e, f\}$ is no longer an initial set since $\{e\}$
 935 is now unattacked initial. In order for α to be confluent, it must now satisfy
 936 condition (3), i. e., we must have

$$(\mathcal{F}_5^{\{b,c\}}, \{b, c\}) \xrightarrow{\{e\}} (\mathcal{F}_5^{\{b,c,e\}}, \{b, c, e\}) \xrightarrow{\{f\}} (\mathcal{F}_5^{\{b,c,e,f\}}, \{b, c, e, f\}).$$

937 Note that the type of initial set may change when moving to some reduct.
 938 While $\{e, f\}$ is an unchallenged initial set in \mathcal{F}_5 , it is challenged initial in
 939 $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{a\}}$ and in $\mathcal{F}_5^{\{b,c\}}$ it is even decomposed into a sequence of unattacked initial

Figure 13: The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_6 from Examples 4.12, 4.14 and 4.15.

940 sets.

941 The fact that initial sets may change their type in some reducts is one
 942 of the reasons why confluence is important. The underlying conflict that the
 943 initial set is associated with remains the same, which is why it is desirable
 944 that the selection function is still able to select that initial set.

945 The following intermediate results describe the behaviour of initial sets
 946 in reducts. For unattacked initial sets of some argumentation framework \mathcal{F} ,
 947 it follows directly that they remain unattacked initial sets in any reduct of
 948 \mathcal{F} as long as they have not been selected themselves.

949 **Lemma 4.1.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and $S \in$
 950 $is^\#(\mathcal{F})$. Then, for every serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ we have
 951 either that there exists an $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $S = S_i$ or $S \in$
 952 $is^\#(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$. *Proof:* P. 81*

953 For the other types of initial sets we do not necessarily obtain the same
 954 behaviour. But as the following result shows, an unchallenged or challenged
 955 initial set will always at least remain an admissible set of any reduct, assum-
 956 ing all of its arguments are still present in the reduct.

957 **Lemma 4.2.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and $S \in is(\mathcal{F})$.
 958 Then, for every state (\mathcal{F}', S') with $\mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ and $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha ad} (\mathcal{F}', S')$ it
 959 holds that: If $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}'$, then $S \in ad(\mathcal{F}')$. *Proof:* P. 82*

960 Based on the above two lemmas, we can then show that most of the
 961 semantics we consider here are characterised by a selection function such
 962 that they are $\alpha\beta$ -confluent.

963 **Theorem 4.7.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-
 964 rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent for $\sigma \in \{ad, co, pr, sa, gr, st\}$.*

965 *Proof:* P. 82

966 Only the unchallenged semantics is not $\alpha\beta$ -confluent, as shown by the
 967 following example.

Figure 14: The uc-serialisation of \mathcal{F}_6 from Example 4.12.

968 **Example 4.12.** Consider the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_6 in Figure 13.
 969 We have that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_6) = \{\{a\}, \{d\}\}$ with $\{a\}$ being unattacked initial and $\{d\}$
 970 being unchallenged initial. In particular, consider the $\{d\}$ for which we have
 971 $\{d\} \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_6), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_6), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}_6))$. We also have that

$$(\mathcal{F}_6, \emptyset) \xrightarrow{\{a\} \in \alpha_{\text{uc}}(\{\{a\}, \{d\}, \emptyset\})} (\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}}, \{a\}).$$

972 However, in the reduct $\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}} = (\{c, d\}, \{(c, d), (d, c)\})$, we now have the two
 973 challenged initial sets $\{c\}$ and $\{d\}$ and thus $\alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}})) =$
 974 \emptyset . Hence, for this state $(\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}}, \{a\})$ we have that neither of the three condi-
 975 tion of Property 10 are satisfied. $\{d\}$ is no longer selectable, but it is neither
 976 attacked by the extension $\{a\}$ nor included in it. Therefore, the unchallenged
 977 semantics is not α_{uc} -confluent.

978 To conclude, Table 2 summarises the above results and indicates which
 979 semantics satisfies the different serialisation properties, i. e., meaning there
 980 exists a $\alpha\beta$ -serialisation system for σ that satisfies the respective serialisation
 981 properties. In the following section we will investigate closely the properties
 982 of serialisation systems and relate them to the principles for argumentation
 983 semantics from the literature.

984 4.2. Characterising Principles in Terms of Serialisation Properties

985 We now establish connections between properties for serialisable seman-
 986 tics and the principles for extension-based semantics from the literature.
 987 First, we can, however, establish some general relations between serialisabil-
 988 ity and other principles. In particular, every properly serialisable semantics
 989 satisfies *Conflict-Freeness*, *Defense*, *Admissibility* and *Modularisation*.

990 **Theorem 4.8.** *Let σ be any properly serialisable semantics. Then σ satis-*
 991 *fies Language Independence, Conflict-Freeness, Defense, Admissibility and*
 992 *Modularisation.* *Proof: P. 82*

Property	ad	co	pr	sa	gr	st	uc
Abstraction	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monotonicity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Markovian	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Composability	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Closure	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
Maximality	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Reinstatement	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Cautiousness	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓
Strict Cautiousness	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗
Confluence	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗

Table 2: Overview over the serialisation properties satisfied by the different serialisable semantics according to their selection and termination functions from Theorem 3.1.

993 The other direction does not hold in general, as is for instance witnessed
994 by the semi-stable semantics (Caminada et al., 2012), which satisfies all of
995 these properties but is not serialisable (Thimm, 2022). For most of these
996 principles the above established relation follows straight-forwardly from the
997 fact the definition of serialisability. Of particular interest is the connection
998 between *Modularisation* and serialisability which holds in part due to the
999 $\alpha\beta$ -Markov property. Similarly to serialisability, *Modularisation* enables a
1000 decomposition of an extension into smaller parts and can be understood in a
1001 constructive manner. More specifically, for some AF \mathcal{F} , we say that the pair
1002 (E_1, E_2) is a σ -modularisation if $E_1 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and $E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{E_1})$, corresponding
1003 to the σ -extension $E_1 \cup E_2$ of \mathcal{F} . To be more comparable with serialisability,
1004 we also extend this idea to sequences by iteratively applying *Modularisation*,
1005 i. e., (E_1, \dots, E_n) is a σ -modularisation if $E_1 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, $E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{E_1})$, \dots , $E_n \in$
1006 $\sigma(\mathcal{F}^{E_1 \cup \dots \cup E_{n-1}})$. Importantly, for some σ -extension this approach provides a
1007 decomposition into smaller σ -extensions, whereas serialisability always yields
1008 a decomposition into a series of initial sets, independently of the semantics.
1009 It should also be noted that, if a semantics σ satisfies *I-Maximality*, then
1010 any σ -modularisation that we may obtain will be of the form (E_1, \emptyset) , which
1011 is not very insightful. And even for the complete semantics can this be the
1012 case in many argumentation frameworks. The following example illustrated
1013 this idea in contrast to the more expressive serialisation sequences.

1014 **Example 4.13.** Consider the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_7 in Figure 15. We

Figure 15: The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_7 from Example 4.13.

1015 have that $\text{pr}(\mathcal{F}_7) = \text{co}(\mathcal{F}_7) = \{\{a, b, d\}\}$. Trivially, the only modularisation
 1016 for $\{a, b, d\}$ is $(\{a, b, d\}, \emptyset)$ with $\{a, b, d\} \in \text{co}(\mathcal{F}_7)$ and $\emptyset \in \text{co}(\mathcal{F}_7^{\{a, b, d\}})$. On
 1017 the other hand, we have multiple serialisation sequences for $\{a, b, d\}$, e. g.,
 1018 $(\{a\}, \{b\}, \{d\})$ or $(\{b\}, \{d\}, \{a\})$, which gives us significantly more informa-
 1019 tion about the corresponding extension, for instance the fact that d may only
 1020 be accepted after accepting a or b . This kind of information can not generally
 1021 be expressed by *Modularisation*.

1022 For the other argumentation principles from Definition 2.6, there are no
 1023 further general relationships to properly serialisable semantics. However,
 1024 we can utilise the other serialisation properties introduced in Section 4.1 to
 1025 formulate sufficient and necessary conditions for serialisable semantics for the
 1026 satisfaction of most of the remaining argumentation principles.

1027 The first principle we consider for that is *Reinstatement*. As it turns out,
 1028 for any serialisable semantics σ , the $\alpha\beta$ -reinstatement property is a sufficient
 1029 and necessary condition for the *Reinstatement* principle.

1030 **Theorem 4.9.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 1031 *β . Then, σ satisfies Reinstatement, if and only if σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating.*

1032 *Proof: P. 83*

1033 Next, we consider the principle of *Strong Admissibility*. As shown by
 1034 Theorems 4.10 and 4.11 it is closely connected to strict $\alpha\beta$ -cautiousness. In
 1035 particular, strict $\alpha\beta$ -cautiousness is a sufficient condition for *Strong Admis-*
 1036 *sibility* of some semantics σ and also necessary, assuming that σ is not the
 1037 trivial semantics that returns no extensions at all for every argumentation
 1038 framework.

1039 **Theorem 4.10.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 1040 *β . If σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious, then σ satisfies Strong Admissibility.*

1041 *Proof: P. 84*

1042 **Theorem 4.11.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
1043 *β . If σ satisfies Strong Admissibility, then either*

1044 1. *σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious, or*

1045 2. *$\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ for all argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} . *Proof: P. 84**

1046 A perhaps more intriguing case is the connection between $\alpha\beta$ -closure and
1047 *Directionality*. Both describe somehow the characteristic of a semantics to
1048 be independent of “downstream” decisions. On the one hand, $\alpha\beta$ -closure
1049 ensures essentially that whenever the serialisation process can be continued
1050 by selecting some initial set in a state, then the construction will lead to an
1051 extension eventually. In other words, no further evaluation of the selectable
1052 set has to be made to be sure that the argumentation will lead to a result
1053 in the end. On the other hand, *Directionality* requires the semantics to be
1054 able to determine the extension status of a set without considering “down-
1055 stream” information, i. e., attacked arguments, in case they themselves are
1056 not attacking the set. Indeed, it turns out that the $\alpha\beta$ -closure of a semantics
1057 σ implies *Directionality* of σ .

1058 **Theorem 4.12.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
1059 *β . If σ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed, then σ satisfies *Directionality*. *Proof: P. 86**

1060 We conjecture that the other direction does not hold in general but a
1061 formal proof for that is missing. It is likely necessary to establish some
1062 additional restrictions or exceptions that enable such a connection.

1063 We now turn to the *I-Maximality* principle. As one might expect, the $\alpha\beta$ -
1064 maximality of a semantics σ is related to *I-Maximality*. However, on itself
1065 this property is not sufficient, as witnessed by the unchallenged semantics
1066 which is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal but does not satisfy *I-Maximality*.

1067 **Example 4.14.** We continue Example 4.12 with the AF \mathcal{F}_6 depicted in
1068 Figure 13. We have two unchallenged extensions $\{a\}$ and $\{a, d\}$ which are in
1069 a subset relation. This originates from the fact that $\{d\}$ is an unchallenged
1070 initial set in \mathcal{F}_6 but becomes a challenged initial set in the reduct $\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}}$ after
1071 selecting $\{a\}$.

1072 As the previous example shows, $\alpha\beta$ -maximality is not enough to guaran-
1073 tee that no extensions are in any subset relation to each other. To ensure
1074 this, $\alpha\beta$ -confluence is needed as we will show in the following. First, we

1075 consider an intermediate result which is related closely to the *Modularisation*
 1076 principle of Baumann et al. (2022). In fact, it is actually concerned with the
 1077 reverse direction of *Modularisation* and states that given an extension E of
 1078 some admissibility-based semantics σ , if some part $E' \subsetneq E$ of it is also a
 1079 σ -extension, then the remainder $E \setminus E'$ is at least admissible in the reduct
 1080 $\mathcal{F}^{E'}$. We will later use this to define a novel principle, cf. Definition 4.1.

1081 **Lemma 4.3.** *Let σ be a serialisable semantics. For all argumentation frame-*
 1082 *works $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}'$ and sets $E, E' \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ such that $E' \subsetneq E$, it holds that $E \setminus E' \in$*
 1083 *$ad(\mathcal{F}^{E'})$.* *Proof: P. 88*

1084 Based on the above result we can then show that $\alpha\beta$ -maximality and
 1085 $\alpha\beta$ -confluence are sufficient criteria for *I-Maximality*.

1086 **Theorem 4.13.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 1087 *β . If σ is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal and $\alpha\beta$ -confluent, then σ satisfies I-Maximality.*
 1088 *Proof: P. 88*

1089 Again, we conjecture that the other direction does not hold in general, al-
 1090 though there is no proof as of yet. The reason for that is, that the termination
 1091 function β has a lot of freedom in defining when the extension construction
 1092 is finished and we cannot rule out that it allows for a non-confluent selection
 1093 function while keeping *I-Maximality* satisfied.

1094 Regarding the *Allowing Abstention* principle, formulating sufficient or
 1095 necessary conditions is rather difficult. The principle relies on the existence
 1096 of some extension E_3 that does neither contain nor attack some argument a
 1097 that is contained in one extension E_1 and attacked by another extension E_2 .
 1098 This kind of information is however not obtainable during the serialisation
 1099 process of one extension. For that reason, the only sufficient condition for
 1100 the satisfaction of this principle we can formulate, relies on making sure that
 1101 the existence of such an extension E_3 is never needed, i. e., no argument that
 1102 is included in an extension can ever be attacked by another. This can be
 1103 ensured if the semantics is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious and is also the reason why
 1104 the grounded and strong admissible semantics satisfy *Allowing Abstention*.

1105 **Theorem 4.14.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 1106 *β . If σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious, then σ satisfies Allowing Abstention.*
 1107 *Proof: P. 89*

1108 Clearly, the other direction does not hold, as for instance witnessed by
1109 the complete semantics which satisfies *Allowing Abstention* but is not strictly
1110 cautious.

1111 Next, we consider the principle of *Naivety*. While none of the properties
1112 for serialisable semantics introduced in Section 4.1 is viable to formulate a
1113 condition for *Naivety*, we can however pose a fairly simple condition to fully
1114 characterise its satisfaction. If and only if the termination of the serialisation
1115 process of a σ -extension E implies that the corresponding reduct contains no
1116 non-empty conflict-free set, then *Naivety* is satisfied by σ .

1117 **Proposition 4.1.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
1118 *β . $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ implies $cf(\mathcal{F}) = \{\emptyset\}$ for all AFs $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, if*
1119 *and only if σ satisfies Naivety. *Proof: P. 90**

1120 Notably, only the stable semantics satisfies the above described condition
1121 and is thus also the only semantics that satisfies *Naivety*, cf. Table 1.

1122 The only remaining principle from Definition 2.6 to consider is *SCC-*
1123 *Recursiveness*. Similar to our notion of serialisability, the principle of *SCC-*
1124 *Recursiveness* describes a constructive approach to compute extensions where
1125 they are essentially assembled iteratively over the SCCs of the argumenta-
1126 tion framework. In contrast to that, the serialisation of an extension is not
1127 bound to the order of SCCs and also based on initial sets, independently of
1128 the semantics, and not on a specific base function. There exists, to the best
1129 of our knowledge, no general connection between Serialisability and *SCC-*
1130 *Recursiveness*. In particular, note that there is the *stage2* semantics which is
1131 SCC-recursive (Baroni et al., 2005) but not serialisable and the unchallenged
1132 semantics which is serialisable but not SCC-recursive (Bengel and Thimm,
1133 2022). Moreover, a characterisation based on serialisation properties is still
1134 an open problem. More specifically, the properties for serialisable seman-
1135 tics are not enough to provide any characterisation of *SCC-Recursiveness*.
1136 The key point here is that the SCC-recursive scheme is built on iteratively
1137 considering restrictions of the argumentation framework to individual SCCs.
1138 On the other hand, serialisability works with reducts, starting from the orig-
1139 inal argumentation framework and essentially removing resolved parts (for
1140 instance SCCs) with each step. These two approaches need to be brought
1141 together somehow and one essentially needs to define an appropriate base
1142 function based on the selection and termination function of the serialisable
1143 semantics that still works equivalently on the restrictions to SCCs.

1144 Finally, we coin a new principle for argumentation semantics inspired by
 1145 the $\alpha\beta$ -confluence property. In essence, the idea is that if for some extension
 1146 $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ there exists a subset $E' \subsetneq E$ such that E' is a σ -extension of \mathcal{F} ,
 1147 then the remainder of E must also be a σ -extension of the reduct $\mathcal{F}^{E'}$.

1148 **Definition 4.1.** Let σ be a semantics. σ satisfies *Confluence* if and only if
 1149 for every argumentation framework $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$, $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and $E' \subsetneq E$, if
 1150 $E' \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ then $E \setminus E' \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{E'})$.

1151 **Example 4.15.** Consider again the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_6 depicted
 1152 in Figure 13. Consider for instance the set $\{a, d\}$ which is an unchallenged
 1153 extension of \mathcal{F}_6 . However, we have that $\{a\} \in \text{uc}(\mathcal{F}_6)$ but in the reduct $\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}}$
 1154 the only uc-extension is \emptyset and thus *Confluence* is violated. On the other
 1155 hand, $\{a, d\}$ and $\{a\}$ are also complete extensions and we have that $\{d\}$ is a
 1156 complete extension of $\mathcal{F}_6^{\{a\}}$.

1157 This principle is actually an inverse version of the *Modularisation* princi-
 1158 ple of Baumann et al. (2022), as already observed by Thimm (2023), where
 1159 it was shown that undisputed sets, i. e., conflict-free sets such that the reduct
 1160 contains no non-empty admissible sets, satisfy the above property.

1161 It can then be shown that *Confluence* is implied by $\alpha\beta$ -confluence for any
 1162 properly serialisable semantics.

1163 **Theorem 4.15.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 1164 *β . If σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent, then σ satisfies Confluence. Proof: P. 90*

1165 Based on the above result, we can then easily show that all semantics con-
 1166 sidered in this work, except the unchallenged semantics, satisfy the principle
 1167 of *Confluence*.

1168 **Theorem 4.16.** *Let $\sigma \in \{ad, co, pr, sa, gr, st\}$ be a semantics. Then σ satis-*
 1169 *fies Confluence. Proof: P. 91*

1170 To summarise, we defined properties for serialisable semantics that al-
 1171 low us to characterise the serialisation process of different semantics. Sub-
 1172 sequently, we have shown that these properties can serve as sufficient and
 1173 sometimes also necessary conditions for the argumentation principles devel-
 1174 oped for extension-based semantics. More specifically, we were not only able
 1175 to formulate sufficient (and some necessary) conditions for almost all prin-
 1176 ciples presented in Definition 2.6, but also introduced the novel principle of

1177 *Confluence* inspired by the $\alpha\beta$ -confluence property for serialisable semantics.
 1178 For some principles, namely *I-Maximality*, *Directionality* and *Confluence*, it
 1179 has yet to be determined whether there exist necessary serialisation proper-
 1180 ties for their satisfaction. Only for *SCC-Recursiveness* it remains an open
 1181 question whether the principle can be characterised in terms of serialisation
 1182 properties at all.

1183 5. Initial Models and Serialisability in Abstract Dialectical Frame- 1184 works

1185 So far, we have considered the argumentation process of serialisable se-
 1186 mantics by inspecting the underlying selection and termination functions in
 1187 depth. We will now take one step back and just consider serialisation as a
 1188 procedural approach to semantical representations in formal argumentation.
 1189 That means, in the following we will only consider the semantical representa-
 1190 tion in form of the serialisation sequences that is induced by serialisability.

1191 As already mentioned, abstract dialectical frameworks are a powerful gen-
 1192 eralisation of argumentation frameworks that allow us to represent more com-
 1193 plex types of relations between arguments. As the name suggests, ADFs are
 1194 inspired by dialectics (Brewka et al., 2013). However, similarly to the case
 1195 of AFs, the procedural aspect of dialectical argumentation is only modelled
 1196 well on the syntactic level of ADFs, while the semantic representation in form
 1197 of the three-valued interpretations does not incorporate this element at all.
 1198 This is highlighted by the following example.

Figure 16: The ADF \mathcal{D}_3 from Example 5.1, the arguments a and b are in a conflict, while b supports c and attacks d and the argument e may only be accepted if c is rejected and d is accepted.

1199 **Example 5.1.** Consider, for instance, the ADF \mathcal{D}_3 in Figure 16, where the
 1200 acceptance conditions of arguments are placed right next to them (for the
 1201 formal definitions recall Section 2.3). In words, we have that a and b can

1202 only be accepted if the other is rejected, meaning they form a sort of atomic
 1203 conflict that must be resolved. Only after resolving this conflict, for example
 1204 by accepting a and rejecting b , can we turn to the remaining arguments
 1205 and evaluate them properly. Now, rejecting b directly implies that c must
 1206 also be rejected and in turn that we shall accept d . Consequently, this then
 1207 implies that we may accept e afterwards. On the other hand, if we accept b
 1208 and reject a in the initial conflict, that implies that we accept c and reject d .
 1209 Subsequently, that leads to the rejection of e . If we only consider the resulting
 1210 admissible model that assigns the respective truth values, we disregard this
 1211 information about the reasoning process of the argumentation performed to
 1212 arrive at the conclusion.

1213 To amend the above-mentioned issue, we define in this work the notion
 1214 of serialisability of semantics for the setting of ADFs. Due to the higher ex-
 1215 pressiveness of the semantic representation via three-valued interpretations
 1216 in ADFs (compared to the extension-based approach in AFs), this yields se-
 1217 rialisation sequences that are even more fine-grained and make explicit the
 1218 process of both accepted and rejected arguments within acceptable models.
 1219 That means, with our approach we incorporate both the procedural aspect
 1220 and the exchange of arguments of dialectic argumentation directly into the
 1221 semantics of ADFs. As mentioned before, ADFs subsume many argumenta-
 1222 tion formalisms, including BAFs and SetAFs (Polberg, 2017), which means
 1223 that our work can easily be adapted and utilised in those frameworks as well.

1224 To summarise, the contribution of this section consists of the following.
 1225 In Section 5.1, we introduce the notion of *initial models* for ADFs as the
 1226 atomic semantical units of ADFs and show that they generalise the notion of
 1227 initial sets of AFs. Following that, in Section 5.2, we generalise serialisability
 1228 via the *serialisation sequences* to ADFs and show that they are actually
 1229 more expressive than their AF counterpart. Based on that, we characterise
 1230 serialisation sequences for the classical admissibility-based semantics in ADFs
 1231 in Section 5.3.

1232 5.1. Characterising Initial Models in ADFs

1233 In the following, we introduce *initial models* in the context of ADFs as the
 1234 atomic semantical units as a generalisation of the initial sets. Before we get
 1235 to that, let us we consider again the translation from a model v of an ADF
 1236 $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ to an extension E_v of the corresponding AF \mathcal{F} defined as $E_v = v^{-1}(\mathbf{t})$
 1237 (cf. Equation (4)). Notably, there are cases where multiple models v of

1238 $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ correspond to the same extension E_v of \mathcal{F} , as shown by the following
 1239 example.

1240 **Example 5.2.** Consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_4 in Figure 17. \mathcal{D}_4 has the following
 1241 three admissible models:

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}, \\ v_2 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}, \\ v_3 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}. \end{aligned}$$

1242 Both v_2 and v_3 correspond to the preferred extension $\{a\}$ of the corresponding
 1243 AF $\mathcal{F} = (\{a, b\}, \{(a, b)\})$. However, v_2 is not a complete model of \mathcal{D}_4 while
 1244 v_3 is complete and \leq_i -maximal in \mathcal{D}_4 and thus a preferred model.

Figure 17: The ADF \mathcal{D}_4 from Examples 5.2 and 5.3.

1245 To obtain a unique correspondence between extensions and models we
 1246 define the reverse direction as follows. For some conflict-free set of arguments
 1247 $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ of an AF \mathcal{F} we define the corresponding interpretation v_S of the ADF
 1248 $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ via

$$v_S(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } a \in S \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } a\mathcal{R}S \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

1249 Note that, according to Equation (5) the truth value \mathbf{f} is assigned only if
 1250 a attacks S . With that, we deviate, for good reason, from previous literature
 1251 where \mathbf{f} is assigned to an argument a if $S\mathcal{R}a$, cf. (Brewka et al., 2018). Note
 1252 first that our translation is well-defined and indeed constructs an admissible
 1253 model v_S iff S is an admissible set of \mathcal{F} .

1254 **Proposition 5.1.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding*
 1255 *ADF. $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is an admissible set of \mathcal{F} , if and only if v_S is an admissible*
 1256 *model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Proof: P. 92*

1257 Now, the reason for introducing this new translation from an admissible
 1258 set to a three-valued interpretation is rooted in the fundamental idea of
 1259 initial sets, i. e., the fact that they represent a *minimal* resolution to an
 1260 atomic conflict (Thimm, 2022). Equation (5) ensures exactly that, i. e., the
 1261 corresponding model v_S will be \leq_i -minimal, as we will show in the proof of
 1262 Theorem 5.1 below.

1263 **Example 5.3.** We continue Example 5.2 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_4 in Figure 17.
 1264 According to Equation (5), only the extension $\{a\}$ corresponds to the unique
 1265 admissible model

$$v_2 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}$$

1266 which is a \leq_i -minimal admissible model of \mathcal{D}_4 (excluding the trivial model
 1267 $v_{\mathbf{u}}$).

1268 With that, we now define the *initial models* of an ADF as those models
 1269 that are admissible and minimal wrt. the information ordering \leq_i , excluding
 1270 the model $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ that assigns \mathbf{u} to all arguments.

1271 **Definition 5.1.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF. An interpretation $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow$
 1272 $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is called an *initial model* of \mathcal{D} , iff v is admissible with $v \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$ and
 1273 there is no admissible model $v' \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$ with $v' <_i v$.

1274 We denote with $\text{is}(\mathcal{D})$ the initial models of \mathcal{D} . These initial models then
 1275 represent the atomic semantic units that we will use to construct admissible
 1276 models iteratively.

1277 It follows then from Proposition 5.1 and the fact that Equation (5) in-
 1278 deed induces a \leq_i -minimal model that the initial sets of any argumentation
 1279 framework \mathcal{F} correspond exactly to the initial models of the corresponding
 1280 ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

1281 **Theorem 5.1.** Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF.
 1282 Then $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is an initial set of \mathcal{F} if and only if v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

1283 *Proof: P. 93*

1284 **Example 5.4.** Consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_5 in Figure 18, which corresponds di-
 1285 rectly to an AF (we can simply ignore the acceptance conditions and consider

Figure 18: The ADF \mathcal{D}_5 from Examples 5.4, 5.6 and 5.8.

1286 the links of \mathcal{D}_5 to be attacks to obtain the corresponding AF). The initial
 1287 models of \mathcal{D}_5 are

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_1 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{u}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}, \\
 v_2 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}, \\
 v_3 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}, \\
 v_4 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{u}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

1288 They correspond directly to the initial sets $\{a\}$, $\{c\}$, $\{d\}$ and $\{e\}$ of the asso-
 1289 ciated AF, respectively. Interestingly, while the initial sets of the associated
 1290 AF are all singleton sets, the corresponding initial models assign more than
 1291 one classical truth value to the arguments in \mathcal{D}_5 . This is quite similar to
 1292 the labeling-based representation known for AFs (Caminada and Gabbay,
 1293 2009), where arguments are labelled as accepted, rejected and undecided.
 1294 However, ensured by Equation (5), an initial models only assigns the truth
 1295 value \mathbf{f} to arguments that must necessarily be rejected, in contrast to label-
 1296 ings, where all arguments attacked by accepted arguments must be assigned
 1297 the rejected status. For instance, in the initial model v_3 we have that c is
 1298 assigned \mathbf{f} , but b is assigned \mathbf{u} , even though both are attacked by c . This
 1299 suggests already that three-valued interpretations allow for a more expressive
 1300 semantical evaluation than other representations, even for AFs.

1301 Let us now turn to an ADF that cannot be represented as an AF. As
 1302 the following example shows, the initial models of such an ADF can be quite
 1303 different from the initial sets in AFs. In particular, we can have initial
 1304 models in which only \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{u} are assigned, i. e., no argument is accepted,
 1305 either because of an unsatisfiable acceptance condition or because of cyclic
 1306 support relations. In fact, the latter case always leads to two initial models

1307 (assuming no further influences): one where the arguments in the support-
 1308 cycle are assigned **t** and one where they are assigned **f**.

Figure 19: The ADF \mathcal{D}_6 from Examples 5.5 and 5.7.

1309 **Example 5.5.** Consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_6 in Figure 19. Intuitively, b is attacked
 1310 collectively by a and c , while e is supported by b and attacked by d and c
 1311 and f are in a circular support relation. a is both attacked and supported
 1312 by d . The initial models of \mathcal{D}_6 are:

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}, f \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \\ v_2 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}, f \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \\ v_3 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{u}, d \mapsto \mathbf{u}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}, f \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}, \\ v_4 &= \{a \mapsto \mathbf{u}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{u}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}, f \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}. \end{aligned}$$

1313 The initial models v_1 and v_2 are the two minimal resolutions to the support-
 1314 cycle of c and f , representing that we can either accept or reject both to-
 1315 gether. v_3 shows that an initial model may only reject a single argument if
 1316 its acceptance condition is unsatisfiable. Notably, while b is generally accept-
 1317 able, i. e., there exist admissible models v with $v(b) = \mathbf{t}$, it requires that the
 1318 status of either a or c is resolved first, thus b does not occur in any initial
 1319 model of \mathcal{D}_6 .

1320 To better investigate the relation between different models of an ADF,
 1321 we introduce a notion of conflict between models. For two models v_1, v_2 of
 1322 an ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$, we say that they are *conflicting*⁵ iff there exists an

⁵Note that we use this notion to refer to a conflict of assignments between two mod-
 els. That does not necessarily mean that there must be attacks between the involved
 arguments, like it would be the case in an AF, where only the attack relation exists.

1323 argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $v_1(a) \neq v_2(a)$ with $v_1(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ and $v_2(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$.
 1324 With this notion of conflict we can now distinguish between three types of
 1325 initial models for ADFs, similar to how it is done for AFs, cf. Definition 3.2.

1326 **Definition 5.2.** For $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and some initial model v of \mathcal{D} , we say that

- 1327 1. v is *unattacked* iff for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$ if $v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$, then $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}} \cup \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$,
- 1328 2. v is *unchallenged* iff v is not unattacked and there is no initial model
 1329 v' that is conflicting with v ,
- 1330 3. v is *challenged* iff there is some model v' that is conflicting with v and
 1331 v' is an initial model.

1332 We denote with $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D})$, $\text{is}^{\nrightarrow}(\mathcal{D})$, and $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{D})$ the set of unattacked, un-
 1333 challenged, and challenged initial models, respectively. Note that, in contrast
 1334 to AFs, an argument in an unattacked initial model may still have parents in
 1335 \mathcal{D} , as long as the acceptance condition is tautological/unsatisfiable. See also
 1336 Examples 5.6 and 5.7 that illustrate both cases. Intuitively, the truth value
 1337 assignment of an unattacked initial models is entirely uncontroversial and
 1338 must hold in any model of the ADF. On the other hand, unchallenged and
 1339 challenged initial models contain some contestable truth value assignment
 1340 and the latter even conflicts with some other initial model.

1341 **Example 5.6.** We continue Example 5.4 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_5 in Figure 18. We
 1342 have that $v_1 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ is an unattacked initial model of \mathcal{D}_5 . This follows
 1343 easily from the fact that $\phi_a = \top$. The models $v_2 = \{c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$ and
 1344 $v_3 = \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ are challenged initial models of \mathcal{D}_5 , both conflicting
 1345 with each other on the arguments c and d . Finally, $v_4 = \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ is an
 1346 unchallenged initial model of \mathcal{D}_5 since both ϕ_b and ϕ_e are neither a tautology
 1347 nor unsatisfiable and there is no other initial model that conflicts with the
 1348 assignments of v_4 .

1349 **Example 5.7.** We continue Example 5.5 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_6 in Figure 19.
 1350 The models $v_1 = \{c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, f \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ and $v_2 = \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, f \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$ are challenged
 1351 initial models of \mathcal{D}_6 , conflicting both on c and f . $v_3 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$ is unattacked
 1352 initial, since $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$, and $v_4 = \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$ is the only unchallenged
 1353 initial model of \mathcal{D}_6 .

1354 Indeed, we have that Definition 5.2 is a proper generalisation of Defini-
 1355 tion 3.2.

1356 **Proposition 5.2.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF, $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding*
 1357 *ADF and $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Then, $S \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if $v_S \in \sigma(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$ for $\sigma \in$*
 1358 *$\{is^{\neq}, is^{\neq}, is^{\leftrightarrow}\}$. *Proof: P. 94**

1359 Analogously to the initial sets in AFs, we have that an unattacked initial
 1360 model is always a singleton. There is however an important difference, while
 1361 for AFs this singleton set obviously contains only one accepted argument, in
 1362 the unattacked initial models for ADFs we can have that the single argument
 1363 is evaluated to either **t** or **f**.

1364 **Corollary 5.1.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and v is an unattacked initial*
 1365 *model of \mathcal{D} . Then, we have that $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| = 1$.*

1366 Conversely, for the other types of initial models we have that they must
 1367 contain more than one assignment to **t/f**. Interestingly, the same does *not*
 1368 hold for initial sets in AFs, which can be singletons independently of their
 1369 type.

1370 **Corollary 5.2.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and v is an (un)challenged initial*
 1371 *model of \mathcal{D} . Then, we have that $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| > 1$.*

1372 5.2. Serialisability in ADFs

1373 We now characterise admissibility for ADFs in terms of serialisation se-
 1374 quences, i. e. sequences of initial models. Before we consider the notion of
 1375 a serialisation sequence we first generalise the notion of the *reduct* in the
 1376 sense of Baumann et al. (2020b) to ADFs. For some model v , we define the
 1377 v -reduct of \mathcal{D} as the ADF \mathcal{D}^v where all arguments that are evaluated to **t** or
 1378 **f** by v are removed and their occurrence in the acceptance condition of some
 1379 other argument is replaced by \top or \perp respectively. The intuition being that
 1380 the reduct of an ADF \mathcal{D} wrt. some model v represents the part of the ADF
 1381 that is unresolved by v .

1382 **Definition 5.3.** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is a
 1383 three-valued interpretation. Then we define the v -reduct of \mathcal{D} as the ADF
 1384 $\mathcal{D}^v = (\mathcal{A}', \{\phi'_a\}_{a \in \mathcal{A}'})$ where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}' &= \mathcal{A} \setminus \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}, \\ \mathcal{C}' &= \{\phi'_a\}_{a \in \mathcal{A}'} \end{aligned}$$

1385 with $x \in \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}\}$ and $\phi'_a = \phi_a^{[b/x : v(b)=x]}$ for each $a \in \mathcal{A}'$.

1386 **Example 5.8.** Consider again the ADF \mathcal{D}_5 in Figure 18 and the model

$$v = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{u}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{u}\}.$$

1387 Then, the reduct wrt. v is the ADF $\mathcal{D}_5^v = (\{b, e\}, \mathcal{C}')$ with

$$\phi'_b = \perp \wedge \neg e \quad \text{and} \quad \phi'_e = \neg b$$

1388 depicted in Figure 20. We have that only the unresolved part of the model v
 1389 remains, i. e., the arguments b and e who not been assigned one of the classical
 1390 truth values by v . Notably, while \mathcal{D}_5 correspond to an AF, the reduct \mathcal{D}_5^v
 1391 does not, because of $\phi'_b \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}'}$, which cannot be modelled in an AF.
 1392 This happens because we only remove arguments that are actively rejected
 1393 by the model (assigned \mathbf{f}) and not necessarily all attacked arguments, like
 1394 it is the case for the reduct of AFs. This is also one of the reasons for the
 1395 higher expressiveness of serialisation sequences in ADFs, as well will show
 1396 later.

Figure 20: The reduct \mathcal{D}_5^v from Example 5.8.

1397 It should be noted that this new definition of a reduct wrt. a three-valued
 1398 model v is different from the reduct used in the definition of the stable
 1399 models, cf. Definition 2.11. That definition is used for two-valued models,
 1400 as the ADF where only arguments evaluated to \mathbf{t} are retained and in the
 1401 acceptance conditions all arguments that are evaluated to \mathbf{f} are replaced by
 1402 their truth value. The intention behind that approach is to verify whether a
 1403 two-valued model v is the grounded model of this reduct. In contrast to that,
 1404 in our approach, where the intention is to obtain the unresolved part of the
 1405 framework to iteratively compute a model for the original ADF. Meaning,
 1406 using the reduct from Definition 5.3 with a two-valued model $v \in \text{val}_2(\mathcal{D})$
 1407 will always yield the empty ADF $\mathcal{D}^v = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.

1408 Indeed, our definition of the reduct wrt. a three-valued model is a proper
 1409 generalisation of the reduct for AFs from Definition 2.3. For that, consider
 1410 first the function $\mathbf{toAF} : \mathbb{ADF} \mapsto \mathbb{AF}$ that takes an ADF and transforms it
 1411 back to an AF, defined as follows.

$$\mathbf{toAF}((\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{L}, \{\phi_a\}_{a \in \mathcal{A}})) = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}') \text{ with}$$

1412

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}' &= \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid \phi_a \notin \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}\} \\ \mathcal{R}' &= \mathcal{L} \cap \mathcal{A}' \times \mathcal{A}' \end{aligned}$$

1413 The above defined function essentially just removes those arguments that
 1414 have an unsatisfiable acceptance condition, since those are attacked by the
 1415 set S in the AF \mathcal{F} and would have been removed directly in the reduct \mathcal{F}^S .
 1416 Note that \mathbf{toAF} is only well-defined for ADFs corresponding to AFs.

1417 For some AF \mathcal{F} and an admissible set S , we can then show that applying
 1418 the reduct directly on the AF, i. e., computing \mathcal{F}^S , leads to the same result as
 1419 taking the corresponding ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and model v_S , applying the reduct $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S}$
 1420 from Definition 5.3 and transforming it back to an AF via the function \mathbf{toAF} .

1421 **Proposition 5.3.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF, $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF
 1422 and $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $S \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. Then, it holds that $\mathcal{F}^S = \mathbf{toAF}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S})$.*

1423

Proof: P. 96

1424 Dual to the consensus operator \sqcap , we define the *union operator* \sqcup , which
 1425 combines two *non-conflicting* interpretations v_1 and v_2 into an interpretation
 1426 v_3 by unifying their value assignments. So in case there is no $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with
 1427 $\{v_1(a), v_2(a)\} = \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}\}$, we define $v_3 = v_1 \sqcup v_2$ as

$$v_3(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } v_1(a) = \mathbf{t} \text{ or } v_2(a) = \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } v_1(a) = \mathbf{f} \text{ or } v_2(a) = \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

1428 for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$. If v_1 and v_2 are in conflict (so there is some $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with
 1429 $\{v_1(a), v_2(a)\} = \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}\}$) we leave $v_1 \sqcup v_2$ undefined.

1430 We now define the concept of the *serialisation sequence* for ADFs as a
 1431 series of initial models of the respective reducts.

1432 **Definition 5.4.** A *serialisation sequence* for some ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ is a
 1433 sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ with $v_1 \in \mathbf{is}(\mathcal{D})$ and for each $2 \leq i \leq n$ we have
 1434 that $v_i \in \mathbf{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$.

1435 As an intermediary result we formulate a generalisation of Dung’s fun-
 1436 damental lemma for AFs (Dung, 1995), stating that given non-conflicting
 1437 admissible models v_1, v_2 of an ADF \mathcal{D} , the union $v_1 \sqcup v_2$ is itself an admis-
 1438 sible model of \mathcal{D} .

1439 **Lemma 5.1.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and v_1, v_2 are admissible models
 1440 of \mathcal{D} . If v_1 and v_2 are not in conflict with each other, then $v_1 \sqcup v_2$ is an
 1441 admissible model of \mathcal{D} . *Proof: P. 97**

1442 If v_2 is an admissible model of the reduct \mathcal{D}^{v_1} then v_1 and v_2 are non-
 1443 conflicting and we can infer in that case that $v_1 \sqcup v_2$ is an admissible model
 1444 of \mathcal{D} . The following lemma formalises this statement and is a generalisation
 1445 of the modularisation property for AFs (Baumann et al., 2020a).

1446 **Lemma 5.2.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and v_1, v_2 are three-valued interpre-
 1447 tations. If $v_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ and $v_2 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1})$ then $v_1 \sqcup v_2 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$. *Proof: P. 97**

1448 Note again that serialisability is generally more expressive than (itera-
 1449 tive) modularisation, since the former considers initial sets (resp. models),
 1450 independently of the semantics (Bengel and Thimm, 2022).

1451 Based on the above results, we can then show that the union of all initial
 1452 models v_i in some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ corresponds directly
 1453 to an admissible model. In particular, we can characterise the admissible
 1454 models of ADFs in this way.

1455 **Theorem 5.2.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF. A serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} =$
 1456 (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} induces an admissible model $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ of \mathcal{D} and for
 1457 every admissible model there is at least one such sequence. *Proof: P. 98**

1458 With $\hat{\mathcal{Y}} = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ we denote the admissible model induced by the
 1459 serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$. Note that, every serialisation sequence
 1460 corresponds to exactly one admissible model, but an admissible model may
 1461 have multiple corresponding serialisation sequences, each representing one
 1462 particular order in which the admissible model can be constructed.

Figure 21: The ADF \mathcal{D}_7 from Example 5.9.

Figure 22: Reducts of \mathcal{D}_7 for each step of the serialisation sequence \mathcal{Y}_1 from Example 5.9.

1463 **Example 5.9.** Consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_7 in Figure 21. We have, for instance,
 1464 the initial model $v_1 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$. Now, in the reduct $\mathcal{D}_7^{v_1}$ (Figure 22a), we
 1465 have $\phi'_b \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}'}$ and thus the unattacked initial model $v_2 = \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$.
 1466 Note that, in the corresponding AF \mathcal{F} the argument b would be removed in
 1467 the reduct $\mathcal{F}^{\{a\}}$ since $b \in a_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ and thus the information that b can be rejected
 1468 after accepting a would not be explicitly encoded in the serialisation sequence
 1469 for the AF.

1470 In the reduct $\mathcal{D}_7^{v_1 \sqcup v_2}$ (Figure 22b) we have two initial models

$$\begin{aligned} v_3 &= \{d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \\ v_4 &= \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}. \end{aligned}$$

1471 Then, we have that in the reduct $\mathcal{D}_7^{v_1 \sqcup v_2 \sqcup v_3}$ (Figure 22c) only the argument
 1472 c is left with $\phi'_c = \top$ and thus the initial model $v_5 = \{c \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$.

1473 It follows then that

$$\mathcal{Y}_1 = (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{t}\})$$

1474 is an admissible serialisation sequence corresponding to the admissible model

$$v = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}, d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}.$$

1475 Intuitively, the sequence then tells us the following. We can accept a
 1476 unconditionally and after that rejecting b follows logically, but not necessarily.
 1477 On the other hand, when accepting e we must necessarily reject d in the same
 1478 step. Finally, after rejecting d the argument c can now be accepted.

1479 Making the alternative choice of v_4 in the reduct $\mathcal{D}_7^{v_1 \sqcup v_2}$, we also obtain
 1480 the serialisation sequence

$$\mathcal{Y}_2 = (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\})$$

1481 corresponding to the admissible model

$$v' = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}.$$

1482 Clearly there are many more serialisation sequences of \mathcal{D}_7 , for instance:
 1483 (v_1, v_2) , (v_3, v_1, v_2) , (v_4, v_1) or (v_4) .

1484 It is worth reiterating the significance of the order of assignments given
 1485 by a serialisation sequence, which stands in contrast to simple admissible
 1486 models, where the order of truth value assignments is not taken into ac-
 1487 count. This is why serialisability yields are more expressive and procedural
 1488 form of semantics. Interestingly, as the above example shows, the serialisa-
 1489 tion sequences for ADFs provide an even more fine-grained sequence than
 1490 we can obtain for AFs. There are two reasons for this. First, recall that the
 1491 semantic representation via three-valued interpretations in ADFs enables us
 1492 to have unattacked initial models that assign \mathbf{f} to one argument and \mathbf{u} to all
 1493 others. This means, we have a way to express that some argument is sim-
 1494 ply rejected, without having to accept another argument in the same step
 1495 (because its acceptance condition is unsatisfiable). Second, the reduct for
 1496 ADFs is more cautious, i. e., we do not automatically remove all attacked
 1497 arguments. Instead, it may contain arguments with unsatisfiable acceptance
 1498 conditions. Together, this allows us to express that an argument must even-
 1499 tually be rejected given the current part of the serialisation sequence, but
 1500 it is not necessary to reject it immediately. Consequently, a serialisation se-
 1501 quence of an ADF not only provides a sequence of accepted arguments within
 1502 some model (like in the case of AFs), but rather a sequence that explicitly
 1503 includes both accepted and rejected arguments. This ties in nicely with the
 1504 procedural exchange of arguments of dialectical argumentation discussed in
 1505 the introduction and shows that we bring this aspect to the semantical eval-
 1506 uation of ADFs with our approach.

1507 The following result formalises that, even for ADFs corresponding to AFs,
 1508 the serialisation sequences of the ADF are more expressive than those of the
 1509 corresponding AF.

1510 **Theorem 5.3.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF.*
 1511 *A serialisation sequence \mathcal{Y} of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ induces a serialisation sequence \mathcal{S} of \mathcal{F} with*
 1512 *$\hat{\mathcal{Y}} = v_{\hat{\mathcal{S}}}$ and for every serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} there is at least one such*
 1513 *sequence for $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. *Proof: P. 99**

1514 In other words, for a serialisation sequence of an AF there are multiple
 1515 corresponding serialisation sequences in the ADF while a ADF-serialisation
 1516 sequence corresponds to exactly one serialisation sequence of the AF. As al-
 1517 ready noted above the representation via three-valued interpretations makes
 1518 it possible to explicitly include rejected arguments in the serialisation se-

Figure 23: The ADF \mathcal{D}_8 from Examples 5.10 and 5.11.

1519 quence, which is not possible for the set-based sequences in AFs⁶.

1520 5.3. Characterising Serialisable Semantics in ADFs

1521 Besides characterising admissible models through serialisation sequences,
 1522 we can also characterise other admissibility-based semantics for ADFs, gen-
 1523 eralising the corresponding results for AFs. For that, we utilise different
 1524 restrictions as well as the distinction between initial models introduced in
 1525 Definition 5.2. First, we consider the preferred semantics which can be char-
 1526 acterised by the maximal serialisation sequences, i.e., the serialisation se-
 1527 quences (v_1, \dots, v_n) where the final reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}$ possesses no further ini-
 1528 tial models. This mirrors the definition of preferred serialisation sequences
 1529 from Theorem 3.2.

1530 **Theorem 5.4.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an*
 1531 *interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a seriali-*
 1532 *sation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that*
 1533 *$\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$.* *Proof: P. 100*

1534 **Example 5.10.** Consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_8 in Figure 23. We have, for instance,
 1535 the two preferred serialisation sequences

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Y}_1 &= (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}), \\ \mathcal{Y}_2 &= (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}). \end{aligned}$$

⁶Note that, even when using a labeling-based representation for the sequences in AFs the same would still apply. Labelings must always contain some accepted arguments in order to reject other arguments and all arguments attacked by the accepted arguments are automatically assigned the rejected status (Caminada and Gabbay, 2009).

Figure 24: Reducts of \mathcal{D}_8 from Examples 5.10 and 5.11.

1536 We verify their correctness as follows. The interpretation $v_1 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto$
 1537 $\mathbf{t}\}$ is one of two initial models of \mathcal{D}_8 . The other being $v_2 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, c \mapsto$
 1538 $\mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$, representing the two possible solutions for the atomic conflict
 1539 between a , c and d which needs to be resolved first before the rest of the
 1540 ADF can be evaluated. Taking v_1 to resolve this conflict, we arrive at the
 1541 reduct $\mathcal{D}_8^{v_1}$ (Figure 24a). Here, it is easy to see that the acceptance condition
 1542 ϕ'_d is tautological and thus $v_3 = \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_8^{v_1}$. Finally,
 1543 in the subsequent reduct $\mathcal{D}_8^{v_1 \sqcup v_3}$, depicted in Figure 24b, we have again to
 1544 initial models that challenge each other: $v_4 = \{b \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$ and $v_5 =$
 1545 $\{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$. After selecting either v_4 or v_5 we arrive at the preferred
 1546 serialisation sequence \mathcal{Y}_1 and \mathcal{Y}_2 , respectively and since the remaining ADF
 1547 is empty, they are trivially maximal sequences.

1548 Now, recall that there also is the initial model v_2 of \mathcal{D}_8 to resolve the
 1549 atomic conflict of a , c and d . The resulting reduct $\mathcal{D}_8^{v_2}$ is actually equivalent
 1550 to the reduct $\mathcal{D}_8^{v_1 \sqcup v_3}$ (see Figure 24b), and thus we obtain two more preferred
 1551 serialisation sequences

$$\mathcal{Y}_3 = (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}),$$

$$\mathcal{Y}_4 = (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}).$$

1552 Those are the only preferred serialisation sequences of \mathcal{D}_8 and each induces
 1553 a different preferred model of \mathcal{D}_8 .

1554 We continue with the complete semantics, which can be characterised by
 1555 the serialisation sequences that maximise only the unattacked initial models,
 1556 in correspondence to the complete serialisation sequences of AFs (cf. The-
 1557 orem 3.2). Meaning, a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) is only complete iff
 1558 there does not exist an unattacked initial model in the final reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}$.

1559 This nicely generalises the intuition behind the complete semantics that a
 1560 complete extension should contain every argument defended by it. So, for
 1561 ADFs, a complete model should contain all of the information (in the sense
 1562 of truth value assignments) that is directly implied by it.

1563 **Theorem 5.5.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an
 1564 interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{co}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation
 1565 sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$.*

1566

Proof: P. 101

1567 **Example 5.11.** We continue Example 5.10 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_8 in Figure 23.
 1568 Besides the preferred serialisation sequences, which are obviously also com-
 1569 plete, the empty sequence (and thus the trivial model $v_{\mathbf{u}}$) is complete, be-
 1570 cause both initial models of \mathcal{D}_8 are challenging each other, i. e., $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}_8) = \emptyset$.
 1571 Moreover, the sequences

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{Y}_5 &= (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}, c \mapsto \mathbf{f}, d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}), \\ \mathcal{Y}_6 &= (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}),\end{aligned}$$

1572 are complete, since their reduct (see Figure 24b) again contains only chal-
 1573 lenged initial models. Note that the sequence $(\{a \mapsto \mathbf{f}, c \mapsto \mathbf{t}\})$ is not com-
 1574 plete, since in this reduct we have that $v_3 = \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ is an unattacked initial
 1575 model, cf. Figure 24a.

1576 For the grounded semantics, a serialisation sequence is then comprised
 1577 only of unattacked initial models and there must be no further unattacked
 1578 initial model left. Notably, while the grounded model of an ADF is always
 1579 unique, there may be multiple serialisation sequences corresponding to it.

1580 **Theorem 5.6.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an
 1581 interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation
 1582 sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and for all v_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$,
 1583 it holds that $v_i \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$. *Proof: P. 102**

1584 This again mirrors the grounded serialisation sequences for AFs, as de-
 1585 fined in Theorem 3.2. The following example illustrates the grounded se-
 1586 quences.

1587 **Example 5.12.** \mathcal{D}_9 We consider the ADF \mathcal{D}_9 in Figure 25. The ADF has
 1588 two unattacked initial models: $v_1 = \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ and $v_2 = \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$. In any case,

Figure 25: The ADF \mathcal{D}_9 from Examples 5.12, 5.13, 5.14 and 5.15.

1589 we need to resolve both before we can consider the status of c , since in the
 1590 reduct $\mathcal{D}_9^{v_1}$ v_2 is the only unattacked initial model and in $\mathcal{D}_9^{v_2}$ we only have
 1591 v_1 . However, in the reduct $\mathcal{D}_9^{v_1 \sqcup v_2}$ we have that the acceptance condition
 1592 of c simplifies to $\phi'_c = \perp$ and thus $v_3 = \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$ is an unattacked initial
 1593 model. We end up in the reduct $\mathcal{D}_9^{v_1 \sqcup v_2 \sqcup v_3} = (\{d, e\}, \{\phi'_d = e, \phi'_e = d\})$ where
 1594 no further unattacked initial model exists. To summarise, we then have the
 1595 following two grounded serialisation sequences

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Y}_1 &= (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}), \\ \mathcal{Y}_2 &= (\{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}), \end{aligned}$$

1596 representing the two different ways to obtain the grounded model of \mathcal{D}_9 .

1597 For the two-valued models of ADFs, we obtain the following characteri-
 1598 sation. Simply put, to be a two-valued model the reduct must be empty.

1599 **Theorem 5.7.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an
 1600 interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{val}_2(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation
 1601 sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} =$
 1602 (\emptyset, \emptyset) . *Proof: P. 104**

1603 **Example 5.13.** We continue Example 5.12 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_9 in Figure 25.
 1604 The two grounded serialisation sequences are not two-valued sequences since
 1605 the status of both d and e remains unknown. However, in the reduct $\mathcal{D}_9^{v_1 \sqcup v_2 \sqcup v_3}$,
 1606 we still have two challenged initial models: $v_4 = \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}$ and
 1607 $v_5 = \{d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}$, representing the two alternatives for resolving the
 1608 situation around d and e . This leads to the following four val_2 -serialisation

1609 sequences in total

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{Y}_3 &= (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}), \\
\mathcal{Y}_4 &= (\{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}), \\
\mathcal{Y}_5 &= (\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{t}, e \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}), \\
\mathcal{Y}_6 &= (\{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{c \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{d \mapsto \mathbf{f}, e \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}).
\end{aligned}$$

1610 Notably, there are no other sequences for val_2 because d and e can only be
1611 resolved once c has been assigned \mathbf{f} .

1612 This characterisation is closely related to that of the stable semantics for
1613 AFs, cf. Theorem 3.2. This is reinforced by the following result for AF-like
1614 ADFs, which follows directly from Theorem 5.7 and the work of Brewka et al.
1615 (2013).

1616 **Corollary 5.3.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF.
1617 For any interpretation $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ the following are equivalent:*

1618 (1) *There is a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) with
1619 $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$,*

1620 (2) $E_v \in \text{st}(\mathcal{F})$,

1621 (3) $v \in \text{st}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$,

1622 (4) $v \in \text{val}_2(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$.

1623 It should be noted that, in the general case, Theorem 5.7 only charac-
1624 terises the two-valued models and not the stable semantics described in Def-
1625 inition 2.12. The difference lies in the handling of self-supporting arguments
1626 (either directly or indirectly), which are only allowed to be assigned \mathbf{f} by a
1627 stable model. Thus, we only have that a stable model can be represented as
1628 a serialisation sequence according to Theorem 5.7.

1629 **Proposition 5.4.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is
1630 an interpretation. We have that if $v \in \text{st}(\mathcal{D})$ then there is a serialisation
1631 sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} =$
1632 (\emptyset, \emptyset) . *Proof: P. 104**

1633 The other direction does not hold in general for the stable models as the
1634 following example illustrates.

1635 **Example 5.14.** We continue Example 5.13 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_9 in Figure 25.
1636 Consider the serialisation sequences \mathcal{Y}_3 and \mathcal{Y}_5 which satisfy Theorem 5.7.
1637 According to Definition 2.12 of the stable semantics, we consider the reduced
1638 ADF $\mathcal{D}_{9,\downarrow\hat{\mathcal{Y}}_3}$, where b and c will be replaced by \perp in the acceptance conditions
1639 of the other arguments. It is easy to see that this leaves the grounded model
1640 v_{gr} unaffected (cf. Example 5.12) and thus we have $v_{\text{gr}}^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \neq \hat{\mathcal{Y}}_3^{-1}(\mathbf{t})$, which
1641 means $\hat{\mathcal{Y}}_3$ is not a stable model of \mathcal{D}_9 . Clearly the same holds for \mathcal{Y}_5 since
1642 they induce the same two-valued model, hence only the sequences \mathcal{Y}_4 and \mathcal{Y}_6
1643 correspond to stable models of \mathcal{D}_9 .

1644 It is an open question whether the stable semantics of Brewka et al. (2013)
1645 can be fully characterised in terms of serialisation sequences. For that, one
1646 needs to essentially distinguish between initial sets that are dependent on a
1647 self-support cycle and those that are not.

1648 Finally, we consider strong admissibility for ADFs due to Keshavarzi Za-
1649 farghandi et al. (2022). Analogously to the grounded serialisation sequences,
1650 strongly admissible serialisation sequences are comprised only of unattacked
1651 initial models, representing the fact that each argument cannot be involved
1652 in its own justification at the moment of its acceptance or rejection in the ar-
1653 gumentation process. This is then a generalisation of the strongly admissible
1654 serialisation sequences of AFs from Theorem 3.2.

1655 **Theorem 5.8.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an*
1656 *interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{sa}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation*
1657 *sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and for all $v_i, i = 1, \dots, n,$*
1658 *it holds that $v_i \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$. *Proof: P. 105**

1659 **Example 5.15.** We continue Example 5.12 with the ADF \mathcal{D}_9 in Figure 25.
1660 The two grounded serialisation sequences \mathcal{Y}_1 and \mathcal{Y}_2 are also strongly admissi-
1661 ble serialisation sequences as is the empty sequence by default. In addition to
1662 that we also have that all partial sequences of \mathcal{Y}_1 and \mathcal{Y}_2 are strongly admis-
1663 sible, i. e., $(\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\})$, $(\{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\})$, $(\{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\}, \{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\})$ and $(\{b \mapsto \mathbf{f}\}, \{a \mapsto \mathbf{t}\})$.

1664 To conclude this section, we have characterised the classical admissibility-
1665 based semantics in terms of serialisation sequences for ADFs. Only for the
1666 stable semantics of Brewka et al. (2013) it remains an open question whether
1667 they can be characterised for general ADFs in this way. It should also be
1668 noted that serialisability allows us to define novel semantics for ADFs. In
1669 particular, one can easily define the unchallenged semantics for ADFs via

1670 the distinction of initial models from Definition 5.2, analogously to its AF
1671 counterpart (see Definition 3.7).

1672 There also exist further admissibility-based semantics for ADFs. For
1673 instance, the semi-stable semantics (Keshavarzi Zafarghandi et al., 2021),
1674 which is also well-known in AFs (Caminada et al., 2012). However, it has
1675 already been shown that the semi-stable semantics is not serialisable for AFs
1676 by Thimm (2022) and, since AFs are a special case of ADFs, this result
1677 straight-forwardly generalises to ADFs.

1678 6. Computational Complexity

1679 In the following section, we will investigate in detail the computational
1680 complexity of typical reasoning problems associated with the concepts intro-
1681 duced in this work, both for AFs and ADFs.

1682 The computational complexity of task wrt. initial sets in AFs has already
1683 been studied in detail by Thimm (2022). To complement that, we investigate
1684 in Section 6.1 the computational complexity of the corresponding tasks for
1685 initial models in ADFs that we introduced in this work. For that we consider
1686 both general ADFs, as well as the well-known subclass of bipolar ADFs. As
1687 it turns out, the complexity of initial models in general ADFs is higher, while
1688 the computational complexity of initial models in bipolar ADFs is equivalent
1689 to that of initial sets in AFs.

1690 Furthermore, in Section 6.2, we analyse the computational complexity of
1691 tasks wrt. serialisation sequences in both AFs and ADFs, which has so far
1692 not been considered in the literature. We again consider general ADFs as
1693 well as bipolar ADFs. As it turns out again, the computational complexity
1694 of tasks wrt. serialisation sequences in bipolar ADFs is equivalent to that of
1695 the respective tasks for AFs. Moreover, the complexity of serialisation se-
1696 quences for AFs and bipolar ADFs is equivalent to that of the corresponding
1697 extension-based and model-based representation of the respective semantics.

1698 We assume familiarity with the basics of computational complexity and
1699 the standard complexity classes \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{NP} and \mathbf{coNP} . See (Papadimitriou, 1994)
1700 for a detailed overview on computational complexity. We also consider the
1701 non-standard classes \mathbf{DP} , Σ_2^P , Π_2^P , and $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\mathbf{NP}}$. \mathbf{DP} is the class of decision prob-
1702 lems that are in the intersection of \mathbf{NP} and \mathbf{coNP} . The class $\Sigma_2^P = \mathbf{NP}^{\mathbf{NP}}$
1703 denotes decision problems that are solvable in polynomial time by a non-
1704 deterministic algorithm that has access to an \mathbf{NP} -oracle and Π_2^P is the com-
1705plementary class, i. e., $\Pi_2^P = \mathbf{coNP}^{\mathbf{NP}}$. Furthermore, we consider the class $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\mathbf{NP}}$

1706 whose problems can be solved by a deterministic polynomial-time algorithm
 1707 that can make polynomially many *non-adaptive* (or *parallel*) queries to an
 1708 NP-oracle (Eiter and Gottlob, 1997). Note that $\mathsf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ is sometimes denoted as
 1709 Θ_2^P and is equivalent to $\mathsf{P}^{\text{NP}[\log]}$ (Papadimitriou, 1994).

1710 6.1. Complexity of Tasks Related to Initial Models in ADFs

1711 We first examine initial models as introduced in Section 5.1. For that, we
 1712 consider typical decision problems known in the argumentation literature,
 1713 namely verification, existence as well as credulous and skeptical reasoning
 1714 wrt. initial models in ADFs. More formally, we consider the following com-
 1715 putational tasks, cf. (Strass and Wallner, 2015):

VER $_{\sigma}$	Given $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$, decide whether $v \in \sigma(\mathcal{D})$,
EXISTS $_{\sigma}$	Given $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$, decide whether $\sigma(\mathcal{D}) \neq \emptyset$,
EXISTS $_{\sigma}^{-\emptyset}$	Given $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$, decide whether there exists $v \in \sigma(\mathcal{D})$ with $v \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$,
CRED $_{\sigma}$	Given $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and $a \in \mathcal{A}$, decide whether there exists $v \in \sigma(\mathcal{D})$ with $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$,
SKEPT $_{\sigma}$	Given $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and $a \in \mathcal{A}$, decide whether for all $v \in \sigma(\mathcal{D})$ we have $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$.

1716 Note that, in the case of initial models the problems EXISTS $_{\text{is}}$ and EXISTS $_{\text{is}}^{-\emptyset}$
 1717 are equivalent since per definition initial models must be non-trivial. We in-
 1718 vestigate the complexity both for general ADFs as well as bipolar ADFs.

1719 6.1.1. Results for General ADFs

1720 First, we recall the complexity of deciding whether some interpretation
 1721 v is admissible, i. e., checking that $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$, which has been shown by
 1722 Strass and Wallner (2015) to be in coNP via approximation fixpoint the-
 1723 ory (Denecker et al., 2000). We briefly recall the proof in the appendix since
 1724 we use different notation to that in Strass and Wallner (2015).

1725 **Lemma 6.1.** *Given an ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and a model v of \mathcal{D} , deciding*
 1726 *whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ is in coNP .* *Proof: P. 106*

1727 To facilitate checking the \leq_i -minimality of an admissible model, we gen-
 1728 eralise Lemma 1 of Thimm (2022) for deciding whether for a given set S there

1729 exists an admissible subset from AFs to ADFs as follows. Notably, while this
 1730 can be done in polynomial time (just like verifying admissibility) in the case
 1731 of AFs, for general ADFs checking the minimality of an admissible model
 1732 proves to be computationally harder.

1733 **Lemma 6.2.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an inter-
 1734 pretation. The problem of deciding whether there exists a model $v' \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{D})$
 1735 with $v' \leq_i v$ and $v'(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ is in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. *Proof: P. 107**

1736 Based on Lemmas 6.1 and 6.2 it follows that VER_{is} is in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ and it can be
 1737 shown to be coNP -hard. We conjecture that VER_{is} is $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -hard, but a formal
 1738 proof is missing at the moment.

1739 **Proposition 6.1.** *VER_{is} is in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ and coNP -hard. *Proof: P. 107**

1740 The problem $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$ is equivalent to $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{ad}}^{-\emptyset}$ and thus the following
 1741 result follows directly.

1742 **Proposition 6.2.** *$\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$ and $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}^{-\emptyset}$ are Σ_2^P -complete. *Proof: P. 109**

1743 Before we turn to the complexity of credulous and skeptical reasoning wrt.
 1744 initial models in ADFs, we make a small observation on the complexity class
 1745 $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. As the following lemma shows, this class brings no more expressivity
 1746 than NP when used as an oracle for a polynomial-time complexity class.

1747 **Lemma 6.3.** *$\text{NP}^{P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} = \Sigma_2^P$ and $\text{coNP}^{P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}} = \Pi_2^P$. *Proof: P. 109**

1748 It follows then that CRED_{is} is on the second level of the polynomial hier-
 1749 archy, just like the corresponding problem for \mathbf{ad} in ADFs.

1750 **Proposition 6.3.** *CRED_{is} is Σ_2^P -complete. *Proof: P. 110**

1751 With the same approach we can then show that SKEPT_{is} is Π_2^P -complete.
 1752 Note that the corresponding problem for \mathbf{ad} in ADFs is trivial, because the
 1753 model $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ that assigns \mathbf{u} to every argument is always admissible but by defi-
 1754 nition never an initial model.

1755 **Proposition 6.4.** *SKEPT_{is} is Π_2^P -complete. *Proof: P. 113**

1756 *6.1.2. Results for Bipolar ADFs*

1757 We consider now the same tasks for the subclass of bipolar ADFs (Brewka
1758 and Woltran, 2010), which are defined as follows. We first define for some
1759 interpretation v and some argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$, the interpretation $v^{[a \rightarrow \mathbf{t}]}$ where
1760 the assignment of a is overwritten to \mathbf{t} as

$$v^{[a \rightarrow \mathbf{t}]}(b) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } b = a \\ v(b) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

1761 for all $b \in \mathcal{A}$. Formally, given some ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{C})$, a link $(a, b) \in \mathcal{L}$ is
1762 called *supporting* in \mathcal{D} iff it holds for all interpretations v that if $v(\phi_b) = \mathbf{t}$,
1763 then $v^{[a \rightarrow \mathbf{t}]}(\phi_b) = \mathbf{t}$. Conversely, a link $(a, b) \in \mathcal{L}$ is called *attacking* in \mathcal{D} iff
1764 it holds for all interpretations v that if $v^{[a \rightarrow \mathbf{t}]}(\phi_b) = \mathbf{t}$, then $v(\phi_b) = \mathbf{t}$. An
1765 ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{C})$ is then called *bipolar* if all links in \mathcal{L} are supporting or
1766 attacking or both.

1767 As shown by Strass and Wallner (2015), this simplifies the verification of
1768 admissibility of some interpretation v which can be done in polynomial time
1769 in bipolar ADFs.

1770 **Lemma 6.4.** *Given a bipolar ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and a model v of \mathcal{D} , deciding
1771 whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ is in P . *Proof: P. 114**

1772 Due to that, checking the minimality of some admissible model of a bipo-
1773 lar ADF can then also be done in polynomial time as shown by the following
1774 Lemma.

1775 **Lemma 6.5.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be a bipolar ADF, $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an
1776 interpretation and $a \in \mathcal{A}$. The problem of deciding whether there exists a
1777 model $v' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ with $v' \leq_i v$ and $v'(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ is in P . *Proof: P. 114**

1778 This yields the following results for the computational complexity of rea-
1779 soning with initial models in bipolar ADFs.

1780 **Theorem 6.1.**

- 1781 1. VER_{is} is in P .
- 1782 2. EXISTS_{is} and $\text{EXISTS}_{is}^{-\emptyset}$ are NP -complete.
- 1783 3. CRED_{is} is NP -complete.

σ	AFs		General ADFs		Bipolar ADFs	
	ad	is	ad	is	ad	is
VER_σ	in L	in P	coNP-c	in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, coNP-h	in P	in P
EXISTS_σ	trivial	NP-c	trivial	Σ_2^P -c	trivial	NP-c
$\text{EXISTS}_\sigma^{-\emptyset}$	NP-c	NP-c	Σ_2^P -c	Σ_2^P -c	NP-c	NP-c
CRED_σ	NP-c	NP-c	Σ_2^P -c	Σ_2^P -c	NP-c	NP-c
SKEPT_σ	trivial	coNP-c	trivial	Π_2^P -c	trivial	coNP-c

Table 3: Complexity of tasks related to initial models in ADFs, in comparison to their respective counterpart for AFs and to the respective tasks related to ad in AFs and ADFs, cf. Thimm (2022); Dvorák and Dunne (2018); Strass and Wallner (2015). The highlighted columns are the contributions of this work.

1784

4. $\text{SKEPT}_{i\mathfrak{s}}$ is coNP-complete.

Proof: P. 114

1785

Table 3 summarises our results in comparison to the complexity of tasks related to admissible and initial sets for AFs (Dvorák and Dunne, 2018; Thimm, 2022) as well as admissible models for (bipolar) ADFs (Strass and Wallner, 2015). As our results show, the complexity of reasoning with initial models generally mirrors that of reasoning with admissible models. Notable exceptions are the problems $\text{EXISTS}_{i\mathfrak{s}}$ and $\text{SKEPT}_{i\mathfrak{s}}$ which are intractable for initial models, since the empty interpretation $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ is always admissible but never an initial model. This behaviour is in line with that of initial sets in AFs. Another exception is the problem $\text{VER}_{i\mathfrak{s}}$ in the case of general ADFs which is in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ and coNP-hard for initial models but coNP-c for admissible models. This simply stems from the fact that checking the \leq_i -minimality of an admissible model is intractable for ADFs in general. However, when considering bipolar ADFs this difference disappears. Even more so, the complexity of tasks wrt. initial models in bipolar ADFs is exactly the same as that of the corresponding tasks for initial sets in AFs. That means, the increased expressivity of bipolar ADFs can be utilised without suffering any additional computational cost when working with initial models.

1802

6.2. Complexity of Tasks Related to Serialisation Sequences

1803

We turn now to the computational complexity of reasoning with serialisation sequences. For that, given some serialisable semantics σ , we consider the

1804

1805 problem of verifying whether a given sequence is a σ -serialisation sequence
 1806 of some AF or ADF.

$\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{S}}$ Given $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$, decide whether
 \mathcal{S} is a σ -serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F}

$\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{Y}}$ Given $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$, decide whether
 \mathcal{Y} is a σ -serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D}

1807 Note that we do not consider the other problems like existence and credu-
 1808 lous/skeptical reasoning with serialisation sequences, because they are equiv-
 1809 alent to their extension- and model-based counterparts. For instance, if there
 1810 exists some σ -extension (or model) for the semantics σ , then by definition
 1811 there also exists a corresponding σ -serialisation sequence and vice versa. The
 1812 same applies to the credulous and skeptical reasoning problems.

1813 6.2.1. Results for AFs

1814 We first consider the computational complexity in abstract argumentation
 1815 frameworks, which has so far not been analysed. As summarised in Theo-
 1816 rem 6.2, verifying whether some sequence is a σ -serialisation sequence of the
 1817 AF \mathcal{F} is generally on the same complexity level as checking whether some
 1818 set is a σ -extension of \mathcal{F} , cf. Dvorák and Dunne (2018) and Table 4. Mean-
 1819 ing, even though serialisation sequences are more expressive than extensions,
 1820 they incur no significant additional computational cost.

1821 Theorem 6.2.

1822 1. $\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{S}}$ is in P for $\sigma \in \{ad, co, st, sa, gr\}$.

1823 2. $\text{VER}_{pr}^{\mathcal{S}}$ is *coNP*-complete.

1824 3. $\text{VER}_{uc}^{\mathcal{S}}$ is P_{\parallel}^{NP} -complete.

Proof: P. 116

1825 6.2.2. Results for General ADFs

1826 We now turn to serialisation sequences for ADFs as characterised in Sec-
 1827 tion 5.2. First, we state an intermediate result on checking whether some
 1828 interpretation v is an unattacked initial model of some ADF \mathcal{D} , which is
 1829 relevant for the serialisation sequences wrt. grounded semantics and strong
 1830 admissibility.

1831 **Lemma 6.6.** VER_{is^*} is in *coNP*.

Proof: P. 117

1832 Due to the fact that verifying whether an interpretation is an initial model
1833 is intractable, the problem of verifying σ -serialisation sequences is computa-
1834 tionally harder (under standard complexity-theoretic assumptions) than just
1835 verifying whether some interpretation v is a σ -model of an arbitrary ADF,
1836 for any semantics σ .

1837 **Theorem 6.3.**

1838 1. $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{J}}$ is in P_{\parallel}^{NP} for $\sigma \in \{ad, co, val_2, sa, gr\}$.

1839 2. $\text{VER}_{pr}^{\mathcal{J}}$ is Π_2^P -complete.

Proof: P. 117

1840 The exact complexity of $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{J}}$ for all semantics, except *pr*, is still an open
1841 problem. As the following result shows, it is at least *coNP*-hard for *ad* and
1842 *sa* and *DP*-hard for *co* and *gr*. For the two-valued models, we could not find
1843 any result on the hardness.

1844 **Theorem 6.4.**

1845 1. $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{J}}$ is *coNP*-hard for $\sigma \in \{ad, sa\}$.

1846 2. $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{J}}$ is *DP*-hard for $\sigma \in \{co, gr\}$.

Proof: P. 118

1847 6.2.3. Results for Bipolar ADFs

1848 Finally, we investigate the computational complexity in the subclass of
1849 bipolar ADFs. Since verifying that some interpretation is an initial model
1850 is tractable in this case, the computational complexity of verifying a σ -
1851 serialisation sequence is then again just as difficult as verifying a σ -model,
1852 analogously to the AF case.

1853 **Theorem 6.5.**

1854 1. $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{J}}$ is in *P* for $\sigma \in \{ad, co, val_2, sa, gr\}$.

1855 2. $\text{VER}_{pr}^{\mathcal{J}}$ is *coNP*-complete.

Proof: P. 119

1856 Table 4 summarises our complexity results for reasoning with serialisation
1857 sequences in AFs as well as general and bipolar ADFs. For comparison, we
1858 include the complexity of the corresponding tasks wrt. the extension- and
1859 model-based representation due to Dvorák and Dunne (2018) and Strass and

1860 Wallner (2015), respectively. Note that the last row for st/val_2 represents
1861 the results for the stable semantics in AFs and the two-valued models in
1862 general ADFs (for bipolar ADFs they coincide). For ADFs in general, our
1863 results show that reasoning with σ -serialisation sequences turns out to be
1864 more complex than reasoning with σ -models for most semantics. This is
1865 mostly due to the fact that it requires a polynomial number of intractable
1866 checks to verify that each initial model in a given sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) is
1867 an initial model of the respective reduct. Only for preferred semantics is
1868 reasoning with serialisation sequences on the same level of complexity as
1869 reasoning with preferred models.

σ	AFs		General ADFs		Bipolar ADFs	
	VER_σ	VER_σ^S	VER_σ	$\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{Y}}$	VER_σ	$\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{Y}}$
ad	in L	in P	coNP-c	in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, coNP-h	in P	in P
co	in P	in P	DP-c	in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, DP-h	in P	in P
pr	coNP-c	coNP-c	Π_2^p -c	Π_2^p -c	coNP-c	coNP-c
sa	in P	in P	coNP-c	in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, coNP-h	in P	in P
gr	in P	in P	DP-c	in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, DP-h	in P	in P
st/val ₂	in P	in P	coNP-c	in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$	in P	in P

Table 4: Complexity of verification of serialisation sequences wrt. different semantics σ in AFs, ADFs and bipolar ADFs in comparison to the corresponding tasks for the extension/model-based semantics, cf. Dvorák and Dunne (2018); Strass and Wallner (2015). The highlighted columns are the contribution of this work.

1870 More interestingly, reasoning with serialisation sequences is generally as
1871 complex as reasoning with the less expressive extension- and model-based
1872 representation in the case of both AFs and bipolar ADFs. The only ex-
1873 ception is admissibility, i. e., verifying whether some set S is admissible can
1874 be done in polynomial time with logarithmic space for AFs (Dvorák and
1875 Dunne, 2018), but it is unlikely that the same holds for verifying whether a
1876 sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) is an ad-serialisation sequence. However, a formal proof
1877 for this is missing at the moment. That means, utilising the sequence-based
1878 representation of semantics that is provided by serialisability, yields a more
1879 expressive semantical approach than existing approaches, while keeping the
1880 same level of complexity. This holds true for classical AFs but also for the

1881 more expressive bipolar ADFs.

1882 7. Related Work

1883 Over the course of this work, we have considered in depth the notion of
1884 serialisability and especially the serialisation sequences induced by it, which
1885 are a process-based form of representation for argumentation semantics. The
1886 literature on argumentation has seen various approaches that also take into
1887 account the argumentation process in some form. A prominent approach
1888 are *discussion games* (Caminada, 2018), where sequences of arguments are
1889 constructed as a dialectical proof for the acceptance of some argument. In
1890 particular, a discussion game consists of two players that take turns: the
1891 proponent tries to show the acceptance of the argument while the opponent
1892 tries to challenge the arguments brought forward by the proponent. Import-
1893 tantly, a discussion game is always targeted at a specific argument and the
1894 constructed sequence always starts with this argument and goes “backwards”
1895 from there to prove or disprove its acceptance. Over the course of the game
1896 arguments may also be repeated, if they defend against multiple attacks. In
1897 contrast to that, a serialisation sequence is a sequence of minimal accept-
1898 able sets of arguments and always starts with sets that defend themselves
1899 independently of other arguments. Additionally, a serialisation sequence is
1900 more concise since arguments only appear at most once in the sequence.
1901 The serialisation sequences are also an alternative representation for seman-
1902 tics and not necessarily concerned with the acceptance of a particular argu-
1903 ment. However, in argumentation frameworks, a serialisation sequence does
1904 not explicitly contain the counterarguments. This changes when considering
1905 serialisation sequences in abstract dialectical frameworks, where rejected ar-
1906 guments are explicitly included in the sequence. Notably, discussion games
1907 have also been generalised to other argumentation formalisms, in particular
1908 argumentation frameworks with collective attacks (Buraglio et al., 2024) as
1909 well as the abstract dialectical frameworks (Keshavarzi Zafarghandi et al.,
1910 2019, 2020). Specifically in the later case, in contrast to the AF variant, a
1911 discussion game can be constructed to prove both the acceptance as well as
1912 the rejection of an argument.

1913 Other approaches that take into account some sort of construction order
1914 for extensions are the principles of *Modularisation* (Baumann et al., 2022) and
1915 *SCC-Recursiveness* (Baroni et al., 2005) as already discussed in Section 4.
1916 To reiterate the most important difference, in both of these approaches, for

1917 some semantics σ , they produce a sequence of σ -extensions. We have ei-
1918 ther σ -extensions of a series of reducts in the case of *Modularisation*, or
1919 σ -extensions of strongly connected components for *SCC-Recursiveness*. On
1920 the other hand, a serialisation sequence consists of initial sets, i. e. atomic
1921 semantical units, independently of the semantics. This is an important fac-
1922 tor which allows us to analyse and compare the underlying process for the
1923 different semantics formally with a property-based approach.

1924 On the subject of formal analysis, there exist many relevant related
1925 works in the argumentation literature. Most importantly, the principle-
1926 based approach to analyse extension- and labeling-based semantics as popu-
1927 larised by van der Torre and Vesic (2018) and contributed to by many other
1928 works (Baroni and Giacomin, 2007; Baumann et al., 2020b; Dauphin et al.,
1929 2020). In this work, we also contributed to this field by introducing the
1930 principle of *Confluence* for extension-based semantics and by relating the se-
1931 rialisation properties to many argumentation principles, cf. Section 4. Other
1932 prominent works on this topic is the principle-based study of ranking-based
1933 semantics for abstract argumentation by Bonzon et al. (2016) or, more re-
1934 cently, the principle-based analysis of semantics in bipolar argumentation
1935 frameworks (Yu et al., 2023) and argumentation frameworks with collective
1936 attacks (Dvorák et al., 2024). As already mentioned earlier, the latter two
1937 formalisms are subsumed by abstract dialectical frameworks, which makes it
1938 an interesting idea for future work to investigate whether the relations be-
1939 tween serialisation properties and argumentation principles also hold in these
1940 extended formalisms and in ADFs in general. In regard of abstract dialecti-
1941 cal frameworks, there is also the work of Gaggl and Strass (2014); Gaggl
1942 et al. (2021) who generalised the SCC-recursiveness scheme of Baroni et al.
1943 (2005) to ADFs. This then yields a construction method for σ -models of an
1944 ADF, by decomposing it into its strongly connected components and com-
1945 puting the σ -models of these components. We can then consider this as some
1946 form of constructing sequence for a σ -model. However, just like it is the case
1947 for AFs, this will then be a sequence of σ -models of the strongly connected
1948 components, which is decidedly different from a serialisation sequence, which
1949 only contains initial models, independently of the semantics. Another inter-
1950 esting work is *splitting* abstract dialectical frameworks (Linsbichler, 2014).
1951 This work introduces a method for partitioning ADFs to compute partial
1952 σ -models in these partitions that are then combined to a σ -model of the
1953 original ADF. The concept is quite similar to SCC-recursiveness, however
1954 the partitions are not necessarily the strongly connected components. While

1955 both of these approaches are conceptually different from the serialisation se-
1956 quences, they might still prove useful in the development of computational
1957 methods for initial models and serialisation sequences in ADFs. As we have
1958 seen in Section 6, the complexity of these concepts in general ADFs is quite
1959 high, compared to standard semantics. Additionally, it is known that initial
1960 sets of AFs are contained within strongly connected components (Thimm,
1961 2022) and the same likely holds for ADFs as well. This makes both of the
1962 above mentioned approaches seem promising for partitioning the ADF into
1963 smaller parts to limit the search space when computing initial models.

1964 Finally, another important related work is *approximation fixpoint theory*
1965 (AFT) (Denecker et al., 2000, 2004), which is a framework to study seman-
1966 tics of knowledge representation formalisms. In particular, AFT allows us
1967 to define operators over algebraic structures to analyse knowledge bases and
1968 the fixpoints of those operators correspond to acceptable models of the se-
1969 mantics. Strass (2013a) has utilised this framework to characterise many
1970 semantics of AFs and ADFs, including most of the admissibility-based se-
1971 mantics that we also considered in our work. Essentially, the approximation
1972 operator of some semantics σ then moves through the lattice of three-valued
1973 interpretations wrt. the information ordering \leq_i . The fixpoints of this oper-
1974 ator then correspond to σ -labelings of the AF, respectively σ -models of the
1975 ADF. Importantly, this \leq_i -lattice consists of all three-valued interpretations
1976 over the set of arguments \mathcal{A} . Similarly, the serialisation system induced by
1977 some semantics also induce a lattice structure, cf. Example 3.3. However, the
1978 important difference is that our approach only operates on admissible sets of
1979 the AF (respectively admissible models for ADFs). In addition to that, every
1980 transition in a serialisation system corresponds to an initial set/model and
1981 the information strictly grows (wrt. \leq_i) with each selection step. Moreover,
1982 the serialisation system also does not depend on fixpoints to identify seman-
1983 tic models and instead uses a termination criterion. On the other hand, an
1984 approximation operator of Strass (2013a) can move in any direction through
1985 the lattice of three-valued interpretations. We refer to Brewka et al. (2018)
1986 for a detailed overview on approximation operators for semantics of both AFs
1987 and ADFs.

1988 8. Conclusion

1989 In this work, we have considered the notion of serialisability of argumenta-
1990 tion semantics in detail. Serialisability describes a non-deterministic iterative

1991 construction scheme for extensions of argumentation semantics via the initial
1992 sets. Essentially, this yields a process-based approach to semantics in formal
1993 argumentation and we can represent them the form of sequences of atomic
1994 semantical units. First, we have introduced properties for serialisable seman-
1995 tics to investigate in detail the behaviour of these process-based semantics
1996 for abstract argumentation. Subsequently, we explored the relation between
1997 serialisation properties and well-known argumentation principles from the
1998 literature. In particular, we were able to show many sufficient and some
1999 necessary conditions for most argumentation principles. Secondly, we gener-
2000 alised the concepts of serialisability, in particular initial models as the atomic
2001 semantical units and serialisation sequences as a process-based form of rep-
2002 resentation of semantics to abstract dialectical frameworks, a powerful gen-
2003 eralisation of Dung’s argumentation frameworks. The serialisation sequences
2004 for the different admissibility-based semantics then essentially enable us to
2005 fully bring the procedural nature of dialectical semantics to ADFs. Lastly,
2006 we analysed the computational complexity of relevant problems related to
2007 initial models in ADFs and serialisation sequences in AFs and ADFs. Most
2008 notably, the complexity of working with serialisation sequences in AFs turns
2009 out to be as complex as the extension-based approach, meaning they allow
2010 for a richer and more fine-grained representation without incurring additional
2011 computational cost. The same holds for the working with initial models and
2012 serialisation sequences in bipolar ADFs.

2013 There are various interesting targets for future work, some of them al-
2014 ready mentioned over the course of this work. Regarding the property-based
2015 approach to serialisable semantics, there remain some appealing open ques-
2016 tions. In particular, there are some missing necessary conditions, namely
2017 for the principles of *I-Maximality* or *Directionality*, and it remains unclear
2018 whether the *SCC-Recursiveness* principle can be characterised by serialisa-
2019 tion properties at all. On the topic of abstract dialectical frameworks, future
2020 work may explore whether the stable semantics of Brewka et al. (2013) can
2021 be characterised in terms of serialisation sequences. Another prominent for-
2022 malism in computational argumentation is *assumption-based argumentation*
2023 (ABA) (Dung et al., 2009), which is a form of structured argumentation, i. e.,
2024 the arguments are not abstract and instead consist of a set of assumptions
2025 from which some conclusion follows via the underlying rules of the framework.
2026 Recently, it has been shown by Berthold et al. (2024) that ABA can be cap-
2027 tured via bipolar SetAFs. An interesting direction for future work would be
2028 to explore whether the definitions of initial models and serialisation sequences

2029 of ADFs can be transferred to ABA, since bipolar SetAFs are likely to be
2030 subsumed by ADFs as well. Finally, regarding the complexity analysis, the
2031 exact complexity of verifying initial models as well as serialisation sequences
2032 wrt. most semantics in general ADFs remains an open question for future
2033 research.

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2039 **Appendix A. Proofs for Section 4 (A Formal Analysis of Serialis-**
2040 **able Semantics)**

2041 **Theorem 4.1.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
2042 *rem 3.1. Then*

- 2043 1. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -abstract,
- 2044 2. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -Markovian,
- 2045 3. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -monotonous,
- 2046 4. σ is $\alpha\beta$ -composable.

2047 *Proof.* We proof each statement separately as follows.

2048 **$\alpha\beta$ -abstract** Follows directly from the definitions. First of all, the functions
2049 $\text{is}(\mathcal{F})$, $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$, $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$ and $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})$ are language independent. That
2050 follows easily from the fact that they, like any other semantics, only
2051 take into account the topology of the argumentation framework and
2052 not the names of arguments, cf. (van der Torre and Vesic, 2018).

2053 Furthermore, the selection functions α_{ad} , α_{gr} , α_{uc} simply return subsets
2054 of initial sets (depending on their type) without considering argument
2055 names. Analogously, the termination functions β_{co} , β_{uc} , β_{pr} only decide
2056 based on set-emptiness. The termination function β_{ad} is trivial and β_{st}
2057 decides based on emptiness of the AF and thus does also not consider
2058 argument names. Hence, all semantics induced by these functions are
2059 $\alpha\beta$ -abstract.

2060 **$\alpha\beta$ -Markovian** For all considered semantics, this follows directly from the
2061 definition of their termination function β .

- 2062 • β_{ad} trivially terminates in every state.
- 2063 • β_{co} , β_{pr} and β_{uc} terminate based only on the initial sets of \mathcal{F} .
- 2064 • β_{st} terminates iff $\mathcal{F} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.

2065 All functions are completely independent of the previously constructed
2066 set.

2067 **$\alpha\beta$ -monotonous** For all semantics, this follows directly from the definition
 2068 if the selection functions, $\alpha_{\text{ad}}, \alpha_{\text{gr}}, \alpha_{\text{uc}}$ respectively. All selection func-
 2069 tions do not distinguish between initial sets of the same type, thus if
 2070 an initial set $S \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$ (respectively $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$ or $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})$) is selectable
 2071 in some AF \mathcal{F} , then it is selectable in every AF \mathcal{F}' with $S \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}')$
 2072 (respectively $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}')$ or $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}')$).

2073 **$\alpha\beta$ -composable** Consider two disjunct AFs $\mathcal{F}_1 = (\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_2 = (\mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{R}_2)$,
 2074 i. e., we have $\mathcal{F}_1 \sqcap \mathcal{F}_2 = \emptyset$. We assume that $\beta(\mathcal{F}_1, S_1) = 1$ and
 2075 $\beta(\mathcal{F}_2, S_2) = 1$ for some sets $S_1 \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1$ and $S_2 \subseteq \mathcal{A}_2$. Now we consider
 2076 the semantics separately grouped by their termination function.

2077 **ad, sa** are serialisable via β_{ad} . This holds trivially, since β_{ad} always
 2078 returns 1 for every serialisation state.

2079 **st** is serialisable via β_{st} . It follows that $\mathcal{F}_1 = \mathcal{F}_2 = \mathcal{F}_1 \sqcup \mathcal{F}_2 = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$
 2080 and thus the claim holds trivially.

2081 **pr** is serialisable via β_{pr} . It follows that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \text{is}(\mathcal{F}_2) = \emptyset$. Assume
 2082 we now have $\beta(\mathcal{F}_1 \sqcup \mathcal{F}_2, S_1 \cup S_2) = 0$. Then, there must exist
 2083 some initial set $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}_1 \sqcup \mathcal{F}_2)$. However, that means we must
 2084 have either $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1$ or $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}_2$. In any case, since \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2
 2085 are disjunct, it follows immediately that $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}_1)$ (respectively
 2086 $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}_2)$) which contradicts the assumption.

2087 **co, gr** are serialisable via β_{co} . Follows analogously to the previous item
 2088 for the preferred semantics. Clearly, since the two AFs are dis-
 2089 junct, an initial set of $\mathcal{F}_1 \sqcup \mathcal{F}_2$ of any type, will be of the same
 2090 type in \mathcal{F}_1 or \mathcal{F}_2 respectively.

2091 **uc** is serialisable via β_{uc} . Follows analogously to the previous item. \square

2092 **Theorem 4.2.** Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-
 2093 rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{uc}\}$.

2094 *Proof.* We show the claim for each semantics separately.

2095 **ad** is serialisable via α_{ad} and β_{ad} . The associated transition system trivially
 2096 terminates for every path, since β_{ad} is per definition always true and
 2097 thus **ad** is $\alpha_{\text{ad}}\beta_{\text{ad}}$ -closed.

2098 **co** is serialisable via α_{ad} and β_{co} . Let $\mathcal{F}_0 = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation
 2099 framework. Consider the state (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) with $(\mathcal{F}_0, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{\text{ad}}} (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1)$.

2100 Assume that (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) is not terminal, i.e., $\beta_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) = 0$. It follows
 2101 directly that $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_1) \neq \emptyset$. Then, there is at least one initial set S'
 2102 which is selectable wrt. α_{ad} . Thus, there exists the state (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2) such
 2103 that $(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) \xrightarrow{S'} (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2)$. Trivially, we have that $\beta_{\text{co}}((\emptyset, \emptyset), E_1) =$
 2104 1 . It follows, that for every state we will eventually reach a followup
 2105 state (\mathcal{F}_n, E_n) where the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_n is either empty
 2106 or there exists no initial set that can be selected. In both cases the
 2107 termination function β_{co} is true and, thus, the complete semantics is
 2108 $\alpha_{\text{ad}}\beta_{\text{co}}$ -closed.

2109 **pr** The preferred semantics is serialisable via α_{ad} and β_{pr} . Let $\mathcal{F}_0 = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$
 2110 be an argumentation framework. Consider the state (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) with
 2111 $(\mathcal{F}_0, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{\text{ad}}} (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1)$. Assume that (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) is not terminal, i.e.,
 2112 $\beta_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) = 0$. However, then it follows that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}_1) \neq \emptyset$. Then,
 2113 there is at least one initial set S' which is selectable wrt. α_{ad} . Thus,
 2114 there exists some state (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2) such that $(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) \xrightarrow{S'} (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2)$. Triv-
 2115 ially, we also have that $\beta_{\text{pr}}((\emptyset, \emptyset), E_1) = 1$. It follows, that for every
 2116 state we will eventually reach a followup state (\mathcal{F}_n, E_n) where the ar-
 2117 gumentation framework \mathcal{F}_n is either empty or there exists no initial set
 2118 that can be selected. In both cases the termination function β_{pr} is true
 2119 and, thus, the preferred semantics is $\alpha_{\text{ad}}\beta_{\text{pr}}$ -closed.

2120 **sa** is serialisable via α_{gr} and β_{ad} . The associated transition system trivially
 2121 terminates for every path, since β_{ad} is per definition always true and
 2122 thus **sa** is $\alpha_{\text{gr}}\beta_{\text{ad}}$ -closed.

2123 **gr** is serialisable via α_{gr} and β_{co} . Let $\mathcal{F}_0 = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation
 2124 framework. Consider the state (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) with $(\mathcal{F}_0, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{\text{ad}}} (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1)$.
 2125 Assume that (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) is not terminal, i.e., $\beta_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) = 0$. However,
 2126 then it follows that $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_1) \neq \emptyset$. Then, there is at least one initial
 2127 set S' which is selectable wrt. α_{gr} . Thus, there exists some state
 2128 (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2) such that $(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) \xrightarrow{S'} (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2)$. Trivially, we also have that
 2129 $\beta_{\text{co}}((\emptyset, \emptyset), E_1) = 1$. It follows, that for every state we will eventually
 2130 reach a followup state (\mathcal{F}_n, E_n) where the argumentation framework
 2131 \mathcal{F}_n is either empty or there exists no initial set that can be selected. In
 2132 both cases the termination function β_{co} is true and, thus, the preferred
 2133 semantics is $\alpha_{\text{gr}}\beta_{\text{co}}$ -closed.

2134 **uc** is serialisable via α_{uc} and β_{uc} . Let $\mathcal{F}_0 = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation
2135 framework. Consider the state (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) obtained by starting in the
2136 transition system from the empty set, i.e. $(\mathcal{F}_0, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{uc}} (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1)$. Sim-
2137 ilar to the preferred semantics, the eventual termination of each state
2138 follows easily from the definitions of the selection and termination func-
2139 tions. Assume $\beta_{uc}(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) = 0$, then it follows from the definition that
2140 $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) \cup \text{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}) \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, we have that $\alpha_{uc}(\text{is}^{\neq}, \text{is}^{\neq\neq}, \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}) \neq \emptyset$
2141 which means there exists some state (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2) such that $(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) \xrightarrow{S'} (\mathcal{F}_2, E_2)$. So, whenever β_{uc} evaluates to false, there exists per definition
2142 a follow-up state.
2143

2144 Now, all we need to show is that there is a finite number of transition
2145 steps for every argumentation framework. Per definition, every initial
2146 set $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ is non-empty, i.e., $\forall S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}) : S \neq \emptyset$. Therefore,
2147 for every transition step with some $S' \in \alpha_{uc}(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_i), \text{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}_i), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}_i))$,
2148 it follows easily that $AF_i^{S'} \sqsubset \mathcal{F}_i$, i.e., the argumentation framework
2149 gets strictly smaller with every transition step. Thus, after a finite
2150 number of transitions we will eventually reach a state for which no
2151 initial set exists, i.e., the empty argumentation framework. For the
2152 empty argumentation framework, β_{uc} trivially terminates, thus, the
2153 unchallenged semantics is $\alpha\beta$ -closed. \square

2154 **Theorem 4.3.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
2155 *rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal for $\sigma \in \{\text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}\}$.*

2156 *Proof.* The claim follows directly from the definitions of the respective selec-
2157 tion and termination functions.

2158 **pr** is serialisable via α_{ad} and β_{pr} . From $\beta_{pr}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ it follows that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$
2159 and thus $\alpha_{ad}(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) = \emptyset$.

2160 **gr** is serialisable via α_{gr} and β_{co} . From $\beta_{co}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ it follows that $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) =$
2161 \emptyset and thus $\alpha_{gr}(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) = \emptyset$.

2162 **st** is serialisable via α_{ad} and β_{st} . From $\beta_{st}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ it follows that $\mathcal{F} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$
2163 and thus trivially $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ and $\alpha_{ad}(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) = \emptyset$.

2164 **uc** is serialisable via α_{uc} and β_{uc} . From $\beta_{uc}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ it follows that $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}) \cup$
2165 $\text{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ and thus $\alpha_{uc}(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) = \emptyset$. \square

2166 **Theorem 4.4.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
 2167 *rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{gr}, \text{st}, \text{uc}\}$.*

2168 *Proof.* We consider the semantics separately according to their termination
 2169 functions.

2170 **co, gr:** It follows directly from the definition of β_{co} since $\beta_{\text{co}}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ if and
 2171 only if $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$.

2172 **pr:** We have that $\beta_{\text{pr}}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ if and only if $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$. That implies directly
 2173 that $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F})$.

2174 **uc:** Analogously to before, we have that $\beta_{\text{uc}}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ if and only if $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}) \cup$
 2175 $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$.

2176 **st:** We have that $\beta_{\text{st}}(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ if and only if $\mathcal{F} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$. From that it follows
 2177 easily that $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ and thus $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$.

2178 **ad, sa:** Consider the AF $\mathcal{F} = (\{a\}, \emptyset)$. Per definition we have $\beta_{\text{ad}}(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) = 1$,
 2179 but $\{a\} \in \text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F})$. Thus **ad** and **sa** are not reinstating. \square

2180 **Theorem 4.5.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
 2181 *rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -cautious for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{uc}\}$.*

2182 *Proof.* The statement follows directly from the definitions of α_{gr} and α_{uc} . \square

2183 **Theorem 4.6.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-*
 2184 *rem 3.1. Then, σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.*

2185 *Proof.* The statement follows directly from the definition of α_{gr} , which is the
 2186 selection function for both **sa** and **gr**. \square

2187 **Lemma 4.1.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and $S \in$
 2188 $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F})$. Then, for every serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ we have
 2189 either that there exists an $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $S = S_i$ or $S \in$
 2190 $\text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n})$.*

2191 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $S \in \text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F})$. Clearly, for every $S' \subseteq$
 2192 $\mathcal{A} \setminus S$ and $\mathcal{F}^{S'} = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$, we have that $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}'$ since $S_{\mathcal{F}}^- = \emptyset$. Since $S_{\mathcal{F}}^- = \emptyset$
 2193 it also follows directly that $S_{\mathcal{F}^{S'}}^-$ and thus $S \in \text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}^{S'})$. It is easy to see that
 2194 it then holds for every serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ that either
 2195 $S \in \mathcal{S}$ or $S \in \text{is}^\#(\mathcal{F}^{\mathcal{S}})$. \square

2196 **Lemma 4.2.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$.
 2197 Then, for every state (\mathcal{F}', S') with $\mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ and $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{\text{ad}}} (\mathcal{F}', S')$ it
 2198 holds that: If $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}'$, then $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}')$.*

2199 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $\mathcal{F}' = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$ such that $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ and $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{\text{ad}}}$
 2200 (\mathcal{F}', E') . We have that $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}'$. We show that $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}')$ holds. Clearly,
 2201 since S is conflict-free in \mathcal{F} it follows that S must also be conflict-free in \mathcal{F}' .
 2202 Since $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}'$, we know that no argument of S is removed in the reduct \mathcal{F}'
 2203 and thus every attacker that S defends itself against in \mathcal{F} is also defended
 2204 against in \mathcal{F}' . It follows directly that $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}')$. \square

2205 **Theorem 4.7.** *Let $\sigma \in \Sigma_s$ be serialisable via α and β according to Theo-
 2206 rem 3.1. Then, σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{pr}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}, \text{st}\}$.*

2207 *Proof.* We consider the different semantics separately.

2208 **gr, sa:** The result follows directly from Lemma 4.1. In particular, for both
 2209 semantics we have $\alpha(X, Y, Z) = X$, i. e., they only allow the selec-
 2210 tion of unattacked initial sets. Since, according to Lemma 4.1, every
 2211 unattacked initial set is also an unattacked initial set in any reduct that
 2212 contains it (wrt. any serialisation sequence), it follows directly that for
 2213 every state (\mathcal{F}', E') with $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha} (\mathcal{F}', E')$, we either have $S \subseteq E'$ or
 2214 $S \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}')$ and thus $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha} (\mathcal{F}', E') \xrightarrow{S} (\mathcal{F}^{E' \cup S}, E' \cup S)$.

2215 **ad, co, pr, st** are serialisable via α_{ad} . Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and (\mathcal{F}', E')
 2216 a state such that $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{\text{ad}}} (\mathcal{F}', E')$ and $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}')$. Consider now
 2217 some state (\mathcal{F}'', E'') such that $(\mathcal{F}', E') \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha_{\text{ad}}} (\mathcal{F}'', E'')$. Assume that
 2218 neither (1) nor (2) are satisfied by (\mathcal{F}'', E'') , i. e., we have $S \not\subseteq E''$ and
 2219 $S_{\mathcal{F}'}^- \cap E'' = \emptyset$. It follows directly that $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}''$ with $\mathcal{F}'' = (\mathcal{A}'', \mathcal{R}'')$. Then
 2220 it follows immediately from Lemma 4.2 that $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}'')$ and thus from
 2221 Theorem 3.2 that there exists a serialisation sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) such
 2222 that $S = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$. In other words, there exists a state (\mathcal{F}''', E''')
 2223 such that $(\mathcal{F}'', E'') \xrightarrow{S_1} \dots \xrightarrow{S_n} (\mathcal{F}''', E''')$. Clearly, the state (\mathcal{F}''', E''')
 2224 satisfies (1), i. e., we have that $S \subseteq E'''$. \square

2225 **Theorem 4.8.** *Let σ be any properly serialisable semantics. Then σ satis-
 2226 fies Language Independence, Conflict-Freeness, Defense, Admissibility and
 2227 Modularisation.*

2228 *Proof.* We consider each principle as follows.

2229 **Language Independence** Follows directly from the fact that any properly
 2230 serialisable semantics is $\alpha\beta$ -abstract.

2231 **Conflict-Freeness, Defense, Admissibility** Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an ar-
 2232 gumentation framework, σ is a semantics properly serialisable via α and
 2233 β and $S \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ is a σ -extension of \mathcal{F} . Assume that S is not admissible.
 2234 We know that there exists some admissible set $S_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ such that
 2235 $S_1 \subseteq S$, i. e., S_1 has been selected first by α during the construction
 2236 of S . In every subsequent step $i = 2, \dots, n$ of the transition system
 2237 until termination we only select initial sets S_i of the respective reduct
 2238 $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ of \mathcal{F} . Per definition, there can be no conflict between any
 2239 S_i, S_j with $1 \leq i, j \leq n$. Since every S_i is per definition admissible
 2240 in the respective reduct, it follows that $S = \bigcup_{i=1, \dots, n} S_i$ is admissible
 2241 as well and, thus, every serialisable semantics satisfies *Admissibility*.
 2242 Since *Conflict-Freeness* and *Defense* are subsumed by *Admissibility*, it
 2243 follows that every serialisable semantics satisfies *Conflict-Freeness* and
 2244 *Defense* as well.

2245 **Modularisation** Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and σ
 2246 is a semantics properly serialisable via α and β . In particular, that
 2247 means σ is $\alpha\beta$ -Markovian. Assume we have some $E_1 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and we
 2248 also have some $E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}^{E_1})$. Then we have that

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1)$$

2249 and also

$$(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^{E_1 \cup E_2}, E_2)$$

2250 σ is by assumption $\alpha\beta$ -Markovian, thus from the fact that $\beta(\mathcal{F}^{E_1 \cup E_2}, E_2) =$
 2251 1 it follows immediately that $\beta(\mathcal{F}^{E_1 \cup E_2}, E_1 \cup E_2) = 1$. Therefore, we
 2252 have that

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^{E_1 \cup E_2}, E_1 \cup E_2)$$

2253 which means $E_1 \cup E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$. Thus, σ satisfies *Modularisation*. \square

2254 **Theorem 4.9.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 2255 *β . Then, σ satisfies Reinstatement, if and only if σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating.*

2256 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2257 “ \Rightarrow ” σ is serialisable via α and β and σ satisfies *Reinstatement*. We have
2258 to show that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating, i. e., if $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$, then $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$
2259 for all AFs \mathcal{F} . Assume there is some AF $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and some $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$
2260 such that $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}) \neq \emptyset$. Per definition, there exists
2261 some AF \mathcal{F}_0 such that \mathcal{F} is the E -reduct of \mathcal{F}_0 , i. e., $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_0^E$. Now,
2262 if $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$, then it follows directly that E is a σ -extension of \mathcal{F}_0 .
2263 Since we have $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}) \neq \emptyset$, there exists some $\{a\} \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F})$. Clearly,
2264 since $a \in \mathcal{A}$ it follows that a is not attacked by E in \mathcal{F}_0 . Furthermore,
2265 a does not attack E , otherwise E would have to defend itself against a
2266 and thus attack a . Hence, since $\{a\}$ is unattacked in \mathcal{F} , it follows that
2267 a is defended by E in \mathcal{F}_0 but we clearly have $a \notin E$. That contradicts
2268 the assumption that σ satisfies *Reinstatement* and thus we must have
2269 that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating.

2270 “ \Leftarrow ” We have that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating for all AFs \mathcal{F} . Assume the statement
2271 does not hold, then there is some $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ such that
2272 there is some $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with E defends a and $a \notin E$. Since $S \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$, we
2273 have that $\beta(\mathcal{F}^E, E) = 1$ and thus, since σ is $\alpha\beta$ -reinstating, $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^E) =$
2274 \emptyset . \mathcal{F}^E contains the arguments $\mathcal{A} \setminus (E \cup E_{\mathcal{F}}^+)$. Clearly, every argument
2275 in \mathcal{F}^E has at least one attacker and thus cannot be defended by E in
2276 \mathcal{F} . All arguments in $E_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ are also not defended by E and finally all
2277 arguments in E are per definition defended by E and included in E .
2278 That is a contradiction to the assumption and it follows that σ must
2279 satisfy *Reinstatement*. \square

2280 **Theorem 4.10.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
2281 *β . If σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious, then σ satisfies Strong Admissibility.*

2282 *Proof.* We have that σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious for all AFs $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$. Con-
2283 sider any σ -serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$. Since σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -
2284 cautious it follows that all S_i are unattacked initial sets in their respective
2285 reduct. Every unattacked initial set S_i is always a singleton $S_i = \{s_i\}$ with
2286 $s_i \in \mathcal{A}$. Then, we define $S'_1 = \emptyset$ for $\{s_1\}$ and for every $s_i \in S$ with $i = 2, \dots, n$
2287 we construct the set $S'_i = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}$. Clearly $S'_i \subseteq S \setminus \{s_i\}$ for all i and
2288 S'_i also defends s_i in \mathcal{F} . Thus, σ must satisfy *Strong Admissibility*. \square

2289 **Theorem 4.11.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
2290 *β . If σ satisfies Strong Admissibility, then either*

2291 1. σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious, or

2292 2. $\sigma(\mathcal{F}) = \emptyset$ for all argumentation frameworks \mathcal{F} .

2293 *Proof.* Let σ be a semantics that is serialisable via α and β and σ satisfies
 2294 *Strong Admissibility*.

2295 Assume that σ is not strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious. Then there exists some AF
 2296 $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ such that there is some $S \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}))$ with
 2297 $S \notin \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F})$, i. e., we have

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \xrightarrow{S} (\mathcal{F}^S, S).$$

2298 Assume now that there is some state (\mathcal{F}', E) with

$$(\mathcal{F}^S, S) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}', E).$$

2299 Per assumption E must now be strongly admissible in \mathcal{F} . Assume first that S
 2300 is unchallenged initial in \mathcal{F} . Consider some $a \in S$ with $a_{\mathcal{F}}^- \neq \emptyset$. In particular,
 2301 that means there is some $S' \subseteq E \setminus \{a\}$ that strongly defends a in \mathcal{F} . Consider
 2302 now the AF $\mathcal{F}'' = (\mathcal{A}'', \mathcal{R}'')$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}'' &= \mathcal{A} \cup \{x\} \\ \mathcal{R}'' &= \mathcal{R} \cup \{(x, a), (a, x), (x, x)\} \end{aligned}$$

2303 Now, recall that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -monotonous, and clearly $S \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}'')$. Thus we
 2304 have $S \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}''), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}''), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}''))$ and therefore

$$(\mathcal{F}'', \emptyset) \xrightarrow{S} (\mathcal{F}''^S, S).$$

2305 It is easy to see that $\mathcal{F}^S = \mathcal{F}''^S$ because the only additional argument in \mathcal{F}''
 2306 is removed in the reduct because $x \in S_{\mathcal{F}''}^+$. It follows that

$$(\mathcal{F}'', \emptyset) \xrightarrow{S} (\mathcal{F}^S, S) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}', E).$$

2307 Clearly β cannot distinguish between \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{F}'' , since their reduct wrt. E is
 2308 the same. That is a contradiction to the assumption that σ satisfies *Strong*
 2309 *Admissibility* because E is not strongly admissible in \mathcal{F}'' .

2310 Now, it is easy to see that the same follows analogously if S is a challenged
 2311 initial set in \mathcal{F} . In that case we do not add the self-attack in \mathcal{F}'' and we reach
 2312 the contradiction in the same way.

2313 That leaves the only option for β to be 0 for all states which corresponds
 2314 to the empty semantics for any selection function α . \square

2315 **Theorem 4.12.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 2316 *β . If σ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed, then σ satisfies Directionality.*

2317 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an argumentation framework and σ is a semantics
 2318 that is serialisable via α and β and is $\alpha\beta$ -monotonous and $\alpha\beta$ -closed. We
 2319 have to show, for all $U \in \mathfrak{UG}(\mathcal{F})$ it holds that $\sigma(\mathcal{F}, U) = \sigma(\mathcal{F}|_U)$ with
 2320 $\sigma(\mathcal{F}, U) = \{E \cap U \mid E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})\}$. For that, we show the following:

2321 $\sigma(\mathcal{F}|_U) \subseteq \sigma(\mathcal{F}, U)$: Let $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F}|_U)$ be a σ -extension of $\mathcal{F}|_U$. Then there
 2322 exists a sequence of initial sets (S_1, \dots, S_n) such that $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n = E$
 2323 with $S_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}|_U)$ and $\forall i = 2, \dots, n : S_i \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}|_U^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$.

2324 We have that U is an unattacked set of \mathcal{F} . From $S_1 \subseteq U$, it follows
 2325 that $S_1^- \subseteq U$ (otherwise U would not be an unattacked set of \mathcal{F}) and
 2326 since S_1 defends itself against all its attackers in $\mathcal{F}|_U$ it follows that
 2327 S_1 also defends itself in \mathcal{F} and thus $S_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. Clearly, S_1 is also
 2328 necessarily an initial set in \mathcal{F} (otherwise it would not be an initial set
 2329 in $\mathcal{F}|_U$). Furthermore, it must also be of the same type in \mathcal{F} , since every
 2330 attacker of S_1 must be present in $\mathcal{F}|_U$, because U is an unattacked set in
 2331 \mathcal{F} and thus no additional attackers can be present that could affect the
 2332 initial set type. From the fact that σ must be $\alpha\beta$ -abstract, it follows
 2333 directly that $S_1 \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}))$.

2334 Similarly, we also have that S_2 is admissible in $\mathcal{F}|_U^{S_1}$. Again, S_2 cannot
 2335 be attacked by arguments outside of U , meaning S_2 is clearly either
 2336 defended by S_1 or itself against all relevant attacks in \mathcal{F} , thus it is also
 2337 admissible in \mathcal{F}^{S_1} . Therefore, it follows inductively that all S_i are also
 2338 initial sets of the same type in the respective reducts $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ for all
 2339 $i = 2, \dots, n$.

2340 Since σ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed, we know that every transition path has to ter-
 2341minate eventually. Therefore, there must be some σ -extension E' with
 2342 $E \subseteq E'$ for which $\beta(\mathcal{F}', E') = 1$ and thus $E' \cap U = E$.

2343 $\sigma(\mathcal{F}, U) \subseteq \sigma(\mathcal{F}|_U)$: Let $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ be a σ -extension of \mathcal{F} . Assume w.l.o.g.
 2344 that E is \subseteq -maximal in $\sigma(\mathcal{F})$. Then there exists a sequence of initial
 2345 sets (S_1, \dots, S_n) such that $S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n = E$ with $S_1 \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ and
 2346 $\forall i = 2, \dots, n : S_i \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}})$. Recall that in every strongly
 2347 connected component (SCC) S of \mathcal{F} , for every pair of arguments $a, b \in$
 2348 S there exists an attack path between them. Consider an unattacked
 2349 set $U \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and some SCC S of \mathcal{F} . Clearly, we have that if $U \cap S \neq \emptyset$

2350 then $S \subseteq U$. In other words, a SCC S is either completely contained in
 2351 an unattacked set U , or no argument of S is in U at all. Furthermore,
 2352 every initial set $S_i \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ is always contained within some SCC S
 2353 of \mathcal{F} , cf. Proposition 1 of (Thimm, 2022). It follows, that for every
 2354 initial set S_i of the sequence we have that either $S_i \subseteq U$ or $S_i \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus U$,
 2355 i. e., every S_i lies either fully in $\mathcal{F}|_U$ or not at all. Let j_1, \dots, j_m be
 2356 the indices of those initial sets in the sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) that are
 2357 contained in U with $1 \leq j_1 < \dots < j_m \leq n$. In other words, the initial
 2358 sets S_{j_1}, \dots, S_{j_m} are exactly those that are contained in U while all
 2359 other initial sets S_i with $i \notin \{j_1, \dots, j_m\}$ of the sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n)
 2360 are not in U .

2361 We now have to show that $(S_{j_1}, \dots, S_{j_m})$ is a valid serialisation sequence
 2362 in $\mathcal{F}|_U$ and $E' = S_{j_1} \cup \dots \cup S_{j_m}$ a σ -extension of $\mathcal{F}|_U$. For every initial
 2363 set S_{j_x} of the sequence $(S_{j_1}, \dots, S_{j_m})$ we have that $S_{j_x}^- \subseteq U$. Since every
 2364 S_{j_x} is admissible in \mathcal{F} , it is also admissible in $\mathcal{F}|_U$ (and therefore also
 2365 initial). Without loss of generality, consider two initial sets $S_{j_x}, S_{j_{x+1}}$
 2366 out of the sequence $(S_{j_1}, \dots, S_{j_m})$. Then, there exists an initial set S_y
 2367 in (S_1, \dots, S_n) such that $j_x = y$. Now, one of two cases applies:

2368 $j_{x+1} = y + 1$: Then S_{j_x} and $S_{j_{x+1}}$ are adjacent in the original sequence
 2369 and we have that $S_{j_{x+1}} \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{j_x}})$. Moving to $\mathcal{F}|_U$, we can
 2370 ignore all $S_i \notin S_{j_1}, \dots, S_{j_m}$ in the reduct step, because they are not
 2371 in U and thus $\mathcal{F}|_U = \mathcal{F}|_U^{S_i}$. That means, we also have that $S_{j_{x+1}} \in$
 2372 $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}|_U^{S_{j_1} \cup \dots \cup S_{j_x}})$, i. e., $S_{j_{x+1}}$ is also an initial set of the corresponding
 2373 reduct of $\mathcal{F}|_U$.

2374 $j_{x+1} > y + 1$: That means there is at least one initial set $S_i \subseteq \mathcal{A} \setminus U$
 2375 between them in the original sequence for E . So, before select-
 2376 ing $S_{j_{x+1}}$, we move to the reduct $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{j_x} \cup S_i}$ by removing the
 2377 arguments $S_i \cup S_i^+$. However, since S_i is not contained in U , all
 2378 arguments that are removed are clearly not in U as well.

2379 It follows for all x that $S_{j_{x+1}} \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}|_U^{S_{j_1} \cup \dots \cup S_{j_x}})$ in any case. Therefore,
 2380 $(S_{j_1}, \dots, S_{j_m})$ is a valid serialisation sequence for $\mathcal{F}|_U$.

2381 What remains is to show that $E' = S_{j_1} \cup \dots \cup S_{j_m}$ is a σ -extension
 2382 of $\mathcal{F}|_U$. Assume the opposite is true, i. e., $\beta(\mathcal{F}|_U^{S_{j_1} \cup \dots \cup S_{j_m}}, E') = 0$.
 2383 Since σ is $\alpha\beta$ -closed, the sequence $(S_{j_1}, \dots, S_{j_m})$ can be continued in
 2384 $\mathcal{F}|_U^{S_{j_1} \cup \dots \cup S_{j_m}}$. So there must exist an initial set S' of $\mathcal{F}|_U^{S_{j_1} \cup \dots \cup S_{j_m}}$ that

2385 is selected by α . As before, S' is then also an initial set of the same
 2386 type in $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}$, and the sequence (S_1, \dots, S_n) can be extended in \mathcal{F}
 2387 as well, contradicting the assumption that E is \subseteq -maximal.

2388 Therefore, $E' = E \cap U$ must be a σ -extension of $\mathcal{F}|_U$.

2389 It follows that the $\alpha\beta$ -closure of a serialisable semantics σ implies that σ
 2390 satisfies *Directionality*. \square

2391 **Lemma 4.3.** *Let σ be a serialisable semantics. For all argumentation frame-*
 2392 *works $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}'$ and sets $E, E' \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ such that $E' \subsetneq E$, it holds that $E \setminus E' \in$*
 2393 *$\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{E'})$.*

2394 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and σ is serialisable via α and β . Consider
 2395 two σ -extension E, E' such that $E' \subsetneq E$. Consider now the set $S' = E \setminus E'$,
 2396 for which we now show $S' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{E'})$ as follows.

2397 (1) **S' is conflict-free in $\mathcal{F}^{E'}$:** Follows immediately from the fact that E is
 2398 conflict-free in \mathcal{F} and $S' \subseteq E$.

2399 (2) **S' defends all its arguments in $\mathcal{F}^{E'}$:** Assume this is false. Then there
 2400 exists some $a \in S'$ such that a is not defended by S' in $\mathcal{F}^{E'} = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{R}')$,
 2401 i. e., there exists some $b \in \mathcal{A}'$ with $b\mathcal{R}'a$ and $b \notin S'_{\mathcal{F}^{E'}}^+$. However, since
 2402 b is also not attacked by E' in \mathcal{F} , otherwise b would not exist in the
 2403 reduct \mathcal{F}^E , it follows that E would not be admissible in \mathcal{F} .

2404 Hence, we have that $S' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{E'})$. \square

2405 **Theorem 4.13.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 2406 *β . If σ is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal and $\alpha\beta$ -confluent, then σ satisfies I-Maximality.*

2407 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and σ is serialisable via α and β and σ is
 2408 $\alpha\beta$ -maximal and $\alpha\beta$ -confluent.

2409 Assume σ does not satisfy *I-Maximality*. Then there exist two extensions
 2410 $E_1, E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ such that $E_1 \subsetneq E_2$. From the fact that σ is serialisable, it
 2411 follows that

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1)$$

2412 Consider the set $S' = E_2 \setminus E_1$. It follows from Lemma 4.3 that $S' \in$
 2413 $\text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{E_1})$. Since admissible sets are serialisable with α_{ad} it follows that there
 2414 exists some initial set $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{E_1})$ with $S \subseteq S'$.

2415 However, recall that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal and $\beta(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1) = 1$, thus we have
 2416 $S \notin \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}))$. Note also that for any two serialisation
 2417 sequences $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ and $\mathcal{S}' = (S'_1, \dots, S'_n)$ if $\hat{\mathcal{S}} = \hat{\mathcal{S}}'$ then $\mathcal{F}^{\hat{\mathcal{S}}} =$
 2418 $\mathcal{F}^{\hat{\mathcal{S}'}}$. Therefore, any σ -serialisation sequence for E_2 cannot start with any
 2419 serialisation sequence for E_1 , i. e. we do not have

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^{E_2}, E_2).$$

2420 Consider some arbitrary σ -serialisation sequence of E_1

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \xrightarrow{S_1} \dots \xrightarrow{S_n} (\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}, E_1).$$

2421 Then, there must be some state, where we can select some $S \subseteq E_2$ with
 2422 $S \cap (E_2 \setminus E_1) \neq \emptyset$ instead of the respective S_i . Let $(\mathcal{F}_i, S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i)$ be that state
 2423 with $i \in [1, n]$ and $\mathcal{F}_i = \mathcal{F}^{S_i}$. We have that $S \in \alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}_i), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}_i), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}_i))$.

2424 Recall that σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent. Thus, for every follow-up state (\mathcal{F}', E')
 2425 with $(\mathcal{F}_i, S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i) \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}', E')$ it must hold that either

- 2426 (1) $S \subset E'$, or
- 2427 (2) $S_{\mathcal{F}}^- \cap E' \neq \emptyset$, or
- 2428 (3) $(\mathcal{F}', E') \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}'^S, E' \cup S)$.

2429 Consider the state (\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1) for which we know

$$(\mathcal{F}_i, S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i) \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1).$$

2430 Clearly, condition (1) is false because we have $S \cap (E_2 \setminus E_1) \neq \emptyset$. Similarly,
 2431 (2) is false, because $E_1 \cup S \subseteq E_2$ and $E_2 \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ is conflict-free. Finally,
 2432 (3) is also false because σ is $\alpha\beta$ -maximal and we have $\beta(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}, E_1) = 1$ and
 2433 thus $\alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}^{E_1}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}^{E_1})) = \emptyset$. Hence, there exists no follow-
 2434 up state for (\mathcal{F}', E') . We arrive at a contradiction and thus σ must satisfy
 2435 *I-Maximality*. \square

2436 **Theorem 4.14.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 2437 *β . If σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious, then σ satisfies Allowing Abstention.*

2438 *Proof.* Let σ be a semantics serialisable via α and β . We have that σ is
 2439 strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious, i. e., $\alpha(\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})) \subseteq \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F})$ for all AFs
 2440 $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$. Assume there is an argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that there exist

2441 $S, S' \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ with $a \in S$ and $a \in S'_{\mathcal{F}}^+$. From the proof of Theorem 4.10 it
 2442 follows that both S and S' are strongly admissible. That implies directly
 2443 that they are a subset of the grounded extension S_{gr} of \mathcal{F} , i. e., $S \cup S' \subseteq S_{\text{gr}}$.
 2444 However, since $a \in S$ and $a \in S'_{\mathcal{F}}^+$ it follows that $a \in S_{\text{gr}}^+$ and thus the
 2445 grounded extension would not be conflict-free, which is a contradiction. It
 2446 follows that no such S and S' can exist if σ is strictly $\alpha\beta$ -cautious and thus
 2447 σ trivially satisfies *Allowing Abstention*. \square

2448 **Proposition 4.1.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 2449 *β . $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ implies $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F}) = \{\emptyset\}$ for all AFs $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, if*
 2450 *and only if σ satisfies *Naivety*.*

2451 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2452 “ \Rightarrow ” Let σ be a semantics that is serialisable via α and β . It holds that
 2453 $\beta(\mathcal{F}, E) = 1$ implies $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F}) = \{\emptyset\}$ for all AFs $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ and $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$.
 2454 Assume that σ does not satisfy *Naivety*. Then, there must be some
 2455 $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that there is an $E' \in \text{cf}(\mathcal{F})$ with $E \subsetneq E'$. Since $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$
 2456 we have that $\beta(\mathcal{F}^E, E) = 1$ and thus by assumption also $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F}^E) = \{\emptyset\}$.
 2457 Consider $E'' = E' \setminus E$, i. e., the arguments contained in E' but not
 2458 E . The, E'' must either be contained in the reduct \mathcal{F}^E , or not. In
 2459 the former case, that implies directly that $E'' \notin \text{cf}(\mathcal{F}^E)$ and thus also
 2460 $E'' \notin \text{cf}(\mathcal{F})$. It follows that no superset of E'' , in particular E' , is
 2461 conflict-free in \mathcal{F} , which contradicts our assumption. In the latter
 2462 case, it follows there is some $a \in E$ and $b \in E''$ with $(a, b) \in \mathcal{R}$. Hence,
 2463 $E' = E \cup E''$ would not be conflict-free in \mathcal{F} .

2464 “ \Leftarrow ” Let σ be a semantics serialisable via α and β that satisfies *Naivety*.
 2465 Assume that the above defined property is satisfied by σ , i. e., there is
 2466 some state (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) such that $(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^\alpha (\mathcal{F}_1, E_1)$ and $\beta(\mathcal{F}_1, E_1) = 1$ but
 2467 $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F}_1) \neq \{\emptyset\}$. Since, $\text{cf}(\mathcal{F}_1) = \emptyset$ is not possible by definition, it follows
 2468 that there is some $S \in \text{cf}(\mathcal{F}_1)$. Now, it is easy to see that $E_2 = E_1 \cup S$
 2469 is conflict-free in \mathcal{F} . In particular, no element of S can be attacked by
 2470 some element of E_1 , because S is contained in the reduct \mathcal{F}^{E_1} , and S
 2471 cannot attack E_1 , because E_1 is admissible (cf. Theorem 4.8). Hence,
 2472 $E_2 \in \text{cf}(\mathcal{F})$ with $E_1 \subsetneq E_2$ and thus *Naivety* would be violated which is
 2473 a contradiction. \square

2474 **Theorem 4.15.** *Let σ be a semantics that is properly serialisable via α and*
 2475 *β . If σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent, then σ satisfies *Confluence*.*

2476 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF. Let σ be serialisable via α and β and
 2477 σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent. Assume that σ does not satisfy Confluence, then there
 2478 is some $E \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ such that there exists $E' \subsetneq E$ with $E' \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ and
 2479 $E'' = E \setminus E' \notin (\mathcal{F}^{E'})$. We have that

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^E, E)$$

2480 and also

$$(\mathcal{F}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha, \beta} (\mathcal{F}^{E'}, E').$$

2481 From Lemma 4.3 it follows that $E'' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F}^{E'})$. Let (S_1, \dots, S_n) be a σ -
 2482 serialisation sequence such that $E' = S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n$. Then there must be a
 2483 step $i = 1, \dots, n$ in this sequence such that there is some initial set $S' \in$
 2484 $\text{is}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i})$ such that $S' \in \alpha(\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i}), \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i}), \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i}))$
 2485 and $S' \cap E'' \neq \emptyset$. This follows from the fact that E is a σ -extension and thus
 2486 there must some point during the construction of E' where some element of
 2487 E'' can be added to the extension. This point must come before or at the state
 2488 $(\mathcal{F}^{E'}, E')$. For the state $(\mathcal{F}^{E'}, E')$, we have that $S' \not\subseteq E'$ and clearly
 2489 $S'_{\mathcal{F}} \cap E' = \emptyset$. Since σ is $\alpha\beta$ -confluent, it follows that there is a sequence
 2490 (S_1, \dots, S_n) such that

$$(\mathcal{F}^{E'}, E') \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha} (\mathcal{F}^{E' \cup S'}, E' \cup S').$$

2491 We now either reached $E' \cup S' = E$ or we have $E''' = E \setminus (E' \cup S')$ and
 2492 $E''' \subsetneq E''$. In the latter case, it is easy to see that we can apply the same
 2493 reasoning again and again until we reach the former case because the set of
 2494 remaining arguments gets smaller with each step. In the former case, we
 2495 have shown that

$$(\mathcal{F}^{E'}, \emptyset) \rightsquigarrow^{\alpha} (\mathcal{F}^{E' \cup E''}, E'')$$

2496 and since σ is $\alpha\beta$ -Markovian and we know that $\beta(\mathcal{F}^E, E) = 1$ and $\mathcal{F}^E =$
 2497 $\mathcal{F}^{E' \cup E''}$ it follows that $\beta(\mathcal{F}^{E' \cup E''}, E'') = 1$. Hence, E'' is a σ -extension of $\mathcal{F}^{E'}$
 2498 and σ must satisfy Confluence. \square

2499 **Theorem 4.16.** *Let $\sigma \in \{ad, co, pr, sa, gr, st\}$ be a semantics. Then σ satis-*
 2500 *fies Confluence.*

2501 *Proof.* Recall that all of these semantics are properly serialisable, cf. Theo-
 2502 rem 3.1, and that they satisfy $\alpha\beta$ -confluence according to Theorem 4.7. Then,
 2503 it follows immediately from Theorem 4.15 that σ satisfies Confluence. \square

2504 **Appendix B. Proofs for Section 5 (Initial Models and Serialisabil-**
 2505 **ity in Abstract Dialectical Frameworks)**

2506 **Proposition 5.1.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding*
 2507 *ADF. $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is an admissible set of \mathcal{F} , if and only if v_S is an admissible*
 2508 *model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.*

2509 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2510 “ \Rightarrow ” We have that v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. We have to show that
 2511 S is admissible in \mathcal{F} , i. e.,

- 2512 (1) S is conflict-free, and
 2513 (2) S defends all its members.

2514 to (1): Follows directly from the definition of the corresponding model
 2515 in Equation (5). If S is not conflict-free, then v_S is not well-defined.

2516 to (2): Assume S does not defend itself, i. e., there is some $b \in S^-$
 2517 with $b \notin S^+$. Then, the acceptance condition of b is given as $\phi_b =$
 2518 $\bigwedge_{a_i \in b^-} \neg a_i$. Since S does not defend against b , we clearly have that
 2519 $b^- \cap S = \emptyset$. Recall that v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, i. e., we must
 2520 have $v_S \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)$. Per Equation (5), we have that $v_S(b) = \mathbf{f}$. Thus,
 2521 we must have $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(b) = \mathbf{f}$. $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(b)$ is defined as

$$\prod \{v'(\phi_b) \mid v' \in [v_S]_2\} = \mathbf{f}.$$

2522 It follows that we must have $v_S(a_i) = \mathbf{t}$ for all $a_i \in b^-$. However, per
 2523 Equation (5) we only assign \mathbf{t} to some argument a_i if we have that
 2524 $a_i \in S$. That contradicts the fact that $b^- \cap S = \emptyset$.

2525 Hence, we have that if v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ it follows that
 2526 S is an admissible extension of \mathcal{F} .

2527 “ \Leftarrow ” We have that $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. Then, we have to show that v_S is an admis-
 2528 sible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, i. e., $v_S \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)$. For any argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$, we
 2529 consider each truth value in $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ individually. Clearly, if $v_S(a) = \mathbf{u}$
 2530 we have that $v_S(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(a)$.

2531 Consider now the case $v_S(a) = \mathbf{f}$. That directly implies, via Equ-
 2532 ation (5), that $a \mathcal{R} S$. Since S is admissible, it follows that there exists
 2533 some $b \in S$ with $b \mathcal{R} a$. From Definition 2.15 it follows that $\phi_a = \phi' \wedge \neg b$

2534 with ϕ' being some arbitrary conjunctive formula. Per Equation (5),
 2535 we have that $v_S(b) = \mathbf{t}$. It follows that $v'(b) = \mathbf{t}$ for all $v' \in [v_S]_2$ and
 2536 thus $\prod\{v'(\phi_a) \mid v' \in [v_S]_2\} = \mathbf{f}$. Hence, we have $v_S(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(a)$.

2537 Finally, consider the case $v_S(a) = \mathbf{t}$. The acceptance condition of a is
 2538 given as $\phi_a = \bigwedge_{b \in a^-} \neg b$. Per Equation (5), we assign in the model v_S
 2539 the truth value \mathbf{f} to an argument b iff $b \mathcal{R} S$. Thus, $v_S(b) = \mathbf{f}$ for all
 2540 $b \in a^-$. It follows that $\prod\{v'(\phi_a) \mid v' \in [v_S]_2\} = \mathbf{t}$. Hence, we have
 2541 $v_S(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)(a)$.

2542 All in all, it follows that $v_S \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v_S)$ and v_S is an admissible model
 2543 of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. \square

2544 **Theorem 5.1.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF.*
 2545 *Then $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is an initial set of \mathcal{F} if and only if v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.*

2546 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2547 “ \Leftarrow ” We have that $S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$. Then, we have to show that v_S is an initial
 2548 model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, i. e.,

- 2549 (1) $v_S \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$, and
- 2550 (2) v_S is an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, and
- 2551 (3) v_S is \leq_i -minimal among the non-empty admissible models of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

2552 *to (1):* Clearly, we have that $S \neq \emptyset$ and thus there exists some $a \in \mathcal{A}$
 2553 with $a \in S$. It follows from Equation (5) that $v_S(a) = \mathbf{t}$ and thus
 2554 $v_S \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$.

2555 *to (2):* Follows directly from the proof of Proposition 5.1.

2556 *to (3):* Assume the contrary. That means, there exists some admissible
 2557 model v' with $v' \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$ and $v' \leq_i v_S$. Let S' be the extension of
 2558 \mathcal{F} that corresponds to v' via Equation (5). Then, w.l.o.g., there
 2559 exists an argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with $v'(a) = \mathbf{u}$ and $v_S(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$.

2560 Consider first the case $v_S(a) = \mathbf{t}$. Clearly, that implies $a \in S$
 2561 and $a \notin S'$ and together with $v' \leq_i v_S$ it follows that $S' \subsetneq S$.
 2562 Thus, S cannot be an initial set of \mathcal{F} which contradicts the initial
 2563 assumption.

2564 Consider now the case $v_S(a) = \mathbf{f}$. Per Equation (5), it follows that
 2565 $a \mathcal{R} S$ in \mathcal{F} . For $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, it follows that there is some argument $b \in S$

2566 with $v_S(b) = \mathbf{t}$ and the acceptance condition $\phi_b = \phi_1 \wedge \neg a$ where ϕ_1
 2567 may be some arbitrary formula. Since $a \neq b$, we have that $v'(b) =$
 2568 \mathbf{t} . Clearly, because of $v'(a) = \mathbf{u}$ it follows that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v')(b) \neq \mathbf{t}$ and
 2569 thus $v \not\leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}(v')$. Hence, v' is not an admissible model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

2570 “ \Rightarrow ” We have that v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Dual to the other direction,
 2571 we have to show that S is an initial set of \mathcal{F} , i. e.,

- 2572 (1) $S \neq \emptyset$, and
 2573 (2) $S \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{F})$, and
 2574 (3) S is \subseteq -minimal among the non-empty admissible sets of \mathcal{F} .

2575 to (1): Since v_S is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$, there exists some argument
 2576 $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with $v_S(a) = \mathbf{t}$. Via Equation (5) it follows directly that
 2577 $a \in S$ and thus $S \neq \emptyset$.

2578 to (2): Follows directly from the proof of Proposition 5.1.

2579 to (3): Assume the contrary, i. e., there is some initial set $S' \neq \emptyset$ of \mathcal{F}
 2580 with $S' \subsetneq S$. We show that for every argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ we have
 2581 that $v_{S'}(a) \leq_i v_S(a)$.

2582 Consider first the case $v_S(a) = \mathbf{t}$. Assume $v_{S'}(a) = \mathbf{f}$. Per Equat-
 2583 ion (5) that implies directly that there exists some argument
 2584 $b \in S'$ (and thus also $b \in S$) with $a\mathcal{R}b$. That means S is not
 2585 conflict-free, which is not possible. It follows that $v_{S'}$ assigns ei-
 2586 ther \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{u} to a .

2587 Consider now the case $v_S(a) = \mathbf{f}$. Assume $v_{S'}(a) = \mathbf{t}$. That would
 2588 mean $S' \not\subseteq S$. It follows that $v_{S'}$ assigns either \mathbf{f} or \mathbf{u} to a .

2589 Finally, consider the case $v_S(a) = \mathbf{u}$. Like before, if $v_{S'}(a) = \mathbf{t}$
 2590 we have that $S' \not\subseteq S$. Assume $v_{S'}(a) = \mathbf{f}$. That implies $a\mathcal{R}S'$.
 2591 However, because of $S' \subset S$ it follows $a\mathcal{R}S$ and thus $v_S(a) = \mathbf{f}$.

2592 Therefore, it follows that $v_{S'}(a) \leq_i v_S(a)$ for all arguments $a \in \mathcal{A}$.
 2593 From the “ \Rightarrow ”-direction it follows that $v_{S'}$ is admissible in $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$
 2594 and because of $v_{S'} \not\leq_i v_S$ we arrive at a contradiction. \square

2595 **Proposition 5.2.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF, $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding*
 2596 *ADF and $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Then, $S \in \sigma(\mathcal{F})$ if and only if $v_S \in \sigma(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$ for $\sigma \in$*
 2597 *$\{is^\neq, is^\neq, is^{\leftrightarrow}\}$.*

2598 *Proof.* We proof the statement for is^\neq , is^{\neq} and $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}$ individually as follows.

2599 • $S \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{F})$ iff $v_S \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$: We show both directions as follows.

2600 “ \Rightarrow ” S is an unattacked initial set of \mathcal{F} . Per Theorem 5.1 it follows
 2601 directly that $\text{model}_S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$. Clearly, since $|S| = 1$ we have that
 2602 $|v_S^{-1}(\mathbf{t})| = 1$ Let a denote the unique argument assigned \mathbf{t} by v_S .
 2603 It remains to show that $v_S^{-1}(\mathbf{f}) = \emptyset$. Assume the contrary, i. e.,
 2604 there is some argument b with $v_S(b) = \mathbf{f}$. Then, per Equation (5)
 2605 it follows that b attacks a , which contradicts the assumption that
 2606 $S = \{a\}$ is unattacked initial in \mathcal{F} .

2607 “ \Leftarrow ” v_S is an unattacked initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Per Theorem 5.1 S is
 2608 then an initial set of \mathcal{F} . Clearly, we must have that there is a
 2609 unique argument a with $v_S(a) = \mathbf{t}$ since unsatisfiable acceptance
 2610 conditions are not possible in $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Consider then the correspond-
 2611 ing set $S = \{a\}$. Assume S is not unattacked initial in \mathcal{F} . Then
 2612 there must exist an argument $b \in a^-$. However, in that case the
 2613 acceptance condition ϕ_a of a would contain $\neg b$ and thus not be
 2614 true since we have $v(b) = \mathbf{u}$ contradicting our assumption.

2615 • $S \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{F})$ iff $v_S \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$: We show both directions as follows.

2616 “ \Rightarrow ” S is an unchallenged initial set of \mathcal{F} . Per Theorem 5.1 it follows
 2617 directly that $v_S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$. We need to show that (1) v_S is not
 2618 unattacked and (2) that there is no initial model v' that is in
 2619 conflict with v . To (1), from the fact that $S_{\mathcal{F}}^- \neq \emptyset$ it follows that
 2620 $\phi_a \neq \top$ for every $a \in S$. In particular, we have that $\phi_a = \bigwedge_{b \in a^-} \neg b$.

2621 Hence, $\phi_a \notin \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}} \cup \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ for every $a \in S$ and v_S is not
 2622 unattacked.

2623 To (2), assume the contrary, i. e., there exists an initial model v'
 2624 that is in conflict with v . It follows immediately from Theorem 5.1
 2625 that there is some S' with $v_{S'} = v'$. W.l.o.g., it follows that
 2626 there must be arguments $a, b \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$, $v(b) = \mathbf{f}$ and
 2627 $v'(a) = \mathbf{f}$, $v'(b) = \mathbf{t}$. That means we have $a \in S$ and $b \in S'$.
 2628 Clearly, from Equation (5) it follows that $a \mathcal{R} b$ and $b \mathcal{R} a$. That
 2629 contradicts the assumption that S is an unchallenged initial set.

2630 “ \Leftarrow ” v_S is an unchallenged initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Per Theorem 5.1 S is
 2631 then an initial set of \mathcal{F} . First, we show that $S^- \neq \emptyset$. Since v_S is

2632 not an unattacked initial model, we have that there is some a with
 2633 $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$ and $\phi_a \notin \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}} \cup \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$. Per Definition 2.15 that
 2634 implies directly that $a^- \neq \emptyset$ and thus $S^- \neq \emptyset$. Now, assume there
 2635 is some initial set $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ such that $S' \mathcal{R} S$. Per Theorem 5.1 $v_{S'}$
 2636 is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Assume, w.l.o.g., that $a \in S'$ and $b \in S$
 2637 such that $a \mathcal{R} b$ and thus $a \mathcal{R} S$. It follows from Equation (5) that
 2638 $v(a) = \mathbf{f}$ and $v_{S'}(a) = \mathbf{t}$, thus v_S and $v_{S'}$ are conflicting which
 2639 contradicts our assumption.

2640 • $S \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{F})$ iff $v_S \in \text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$: We show both directions as follows.

2641 “ \Rightarrow ” S is an challenged initial set of \mathcal{F} . Per Theorem 5.1 it follows
 2642 directly that $v_S \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}})$. Per Definition 3.2 we know that there
 2643 exists a $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$ such that $S' \mathcal{R} S$. Since $v_{S'}$ is then also an initial
 2644 model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ it follows directly from the proof of the previous
 2645 statement that v_S and $v_{S'}$ are conflicting and thus both challenged
 2646 initial models of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.

2647 “ \Leftarrow ” v_S is an challenged initial model of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Per Theorem 5.1 S is
 2648 then an initial set of \mathcal{F} . Like before, it follows immediately that
 2649 there is some model $v_{S'}$, corresponding to an initial set $S' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{F})$,
 2650 that is in conflict with v_S . From the proof of the previous state-
 2651 ment regarding $\text{is}^{\leftrightarrow}$ it then follows directly that S is a challenged
 2652 initial set of \mathcal{F} . \square

2653 **Proposition 5.3.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF, $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF*
 2654 *and $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ such that $S \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{F})$. Then, it holds that $\mathcal{F}^S = \text{toAF}(\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S})$.*

2655 *Proof.* Recall that in the reduct \mathcal{F}^S , we remove all arguments in $S \cup S_{\mathcal{F}}^+$.
 2656 The corresponding model v_S for some set of arguments $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ assigns \mathbf{t} to
 2657 all $a \in S$ and \mathbf{f} to all $b \in S_{\mathcal{F}}^-$. Notably, we have that $S_{\mathcal{F}}^- \subseteq S_{\mathcal{F}}^+$, since S is
 2658 admissible. In the reduct $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S}$, we remove all arguments that are assigned
 2659 either \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} . Thus, there may be arguments, i. e., the set $S_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \setminus S_{\mathcal{F}}^-$, which are
 2660 removed in \mathcal{F}^S but not in $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S}$. Let $a \in S_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \setminus S_{\mathcal{F}}^-$ be such an argument. Then,
 2661 since $a \in S_{\mathcal{F}}^+$, it follows that there is some $b \in S$ that occurs in the acceptance
 2662 condition ϕ_a of a . This acceptance condition has the form $\phi_a = \bigwedge_{b \in a_{\mathcal{F}}^-} \neg b$,
 2663 cf. Definition 2.15. Since $b \in S$, we have $v_S(b) = \mathbf{t}$ and thus it is easy to
 2664 see that replacing b in the acceptance condition ϕ_a with its truth value \mathbf{t} will
 2665 lead to it being unsatisfiable. For arguments that are neither included in S
 2666 nor attacked by it, we may only replace arguments that are assigned \mathbf{f} by

2667 v_S , which will never make the acceptance condition unsatisfiable. It is also
 2668 clear that no argument may have an unsatisfiable acceptance condition for
 2669 any other reason than the above described case, since $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ corresponds to an
 2670 AF and therefore no such acceptance conditions may exist naturally.

2671 Finally, when applying **toAF** to $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S}$, we remove all arguments with un-
 2672 satisfiable acceptance conditions, i. e., exactly the set $S_{\mathcal{F}}^+ \setminus S_{\mathcal{F}}^-$, and since S and
 2673 $S_{\mathcal{F}}^-$ have already been removed in $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S}$, it follows that \mathcal{F}^S and **toAF**($\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S}$)
 2674 contain the same arguments. It is then easy to see, that the attacks in
 2675 **toAF**($\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}^{v_S}$) are the same attacks as those in \mathcal{F}^S , since **toAF** simply retains
 2676 all relations between remaining arguments and discard those concerning re-
 2677 moved arguments, just like the reduct for AFs. \square

2678 **Lemma 5.1.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and v_1, v_2 are admissible models
 2679 of \mathcal{D} . If v_1 and v_2 are not in conflict with each other, then $v_1 \sqcup v_2$ is an
 2680 admissible model of \mathcal{D} .*

2681 *Proof.* Given $v_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ and $v_2 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1})$, we consider the model $v =$
 2682 $v_1 \sqcup v_2$. Recall that v_1 and v_2 are non-conflicting. We only have to show
 2683 that $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$. Assume the contrary. Then there must be some argument
 2684 $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = \mathbf{u}$ and $v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$. We distinguish between two
 2685 cases:

2686 $v_1(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ We distinguish further between:

2687 $v_1(a) = \mathbf{t}$ We know that $v_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ and thus $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_1)(a) = \mathbf{t}$. That
 2688 means all two-valued completions of v_1 assign \mathbf{t} to a . For any
 2689 model v' with $v_1 \leq_i v'$ we know that $[v'] \leq [v_1]$. Clearly, it follows
 2690 that any model v' must then also assign \mathbf{t} to a . Recall that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$
 2691 is defined as the consensus over the set of completions of v . Since
 2692 we have $v_1 \leq_i v$, it follows that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = \mathbf{t}$.

2693 $v_1(a) = \mathbf{f}$ This follows analogously to the previous case.

2694 It follows that for all arguments that are assigned \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} in v_1 , that
 2695 they are also assigned the same value in $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$.

2696 $v_2(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ The claim follows analogously to the previous case.

2697 It follows that $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ and thus $v = v_1 \sqcup v_2$ is admissible in \mathcal{D} . \square

2698 **Lemma 5.2.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and v_1, v_2 are three-valued inter-
 2699 pretations. If $v_1 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ and $v_2 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1})$ then $v_1 \sqcup v_2 \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$.*

2700 *Proof.* First, we observe the fact that v_1 and v_2 are non-conflicting, which
 2701 follows directly from Definition 5.3 of the reduct: All argument for which v_1
 2702 assigns \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} are removed in the reduct \mathcal{D}^{v_1} , and since v_2 is a model of \mathcal{D}^{v_1}
 2703 in every case where $v_2 \neq \mathbf{u}$ we know that $v_1 = \mathbf{u}$. \square

2704 **Theorem 5.2.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF. A serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} =$
 2705 (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} induces an admissible model $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ of \mathcal{D} and for
 2706 every admissible model there is at least one such sequence.*

2707 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2708 “ \Rightarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence of the ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$.
 2709 We show that it follows that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ by induction
 2710 over the length of the serialisation sequence $n = |(v_1, \dots, v_n)|$.

2711 $(n = 0)$ We have that $\mathcal{Y} = ()$ and it follows directly that $v_{\mathbf{u}} \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{D})$.

2712 $(n \rightarrow n + 1)$ Per assumption we have that $\mathcal{Y}' = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ is a seri-
 2713 alisation sequence and $v' = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissible model
 2714 of \mathcal{D} . Now, per Definition 5.4 we know that $v_{n+1} \in \mathbf{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v'})$ and
 2715 thus also $v_{n+1} \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v'})$. It follows directly from Lemma 5.2 that
 2716 $v = v' \sqcup v_{n+1}$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} .

2717 “ \Leftarrow ” Let v be an admissible model of the ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$. We show
 2718 that there exists a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ with $v =$
 2719 $v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ by induction over the number of arguments assigned \mathbf{t} or
 2720 \mathbf{f} in v , i. e., $m = |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}|$.

2721 $(m = 0)$ We have that $v = v_{\mathbf{u}}$ and trivially the corresponding seriali-
 2722 sation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = ()$.

2723 $(m \rightarrow m + 1)$ Consider the model $v \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ with $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq$
 2724 $\mathbf{u}\}| = m + 1$. Now, if $v \in \mathbf{is}(\mathcal{D})$ we have the serialisation sequence
 2725 (v) of \mathcal{D} . Otherwise, it follows from Definition 5.1 that there exists
 2726 some $v_0 \leq_i v$ with $v_0 \in \mathbf{is}(\mathcal{D})$. Consider the model $v' = v \setminus v_0$
 2727 defined as follows:

$$v'(a) = \begin{cases} v(a) & \text{if } v_0(a) = \mathbf{u} \\ \text{undefined} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2728 Meaning, v' assigns the same values as v if v_0 assigns \mathbf{u} and oth-
 2729 erwise v' assigns nothing. In other words, v' is the part of v that

2730 is concerned only with the reduct \mathcal{D}^{v_0} . We now have to show that
2731 $v' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_0})$. We distinguish between three cases:

2732 $v'(a) = \mathbf{u}$ Clearly, we always have $v(a)' \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}^{v_0}}(v')(a)$.
2733 $v'(a) = \mathbf{t}$ Per definition, if v' assigns \mathbf{t} (or \mathbf{f}) to some argument,
2734 then v also assigns \mathbf{t} (respectively \mathbf{f}). Consider the arguments
2735 where v assigns \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} and v' is undefined. Those are exactly
2736 the arguments where v_0 assigns \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} . Now, per Definition 5.3
2737 of the reduct wrt v_0 , the occurrences of the arguments in all
2738 acceptance conditions in \mathcal{D}^{v_0} are replaced with \top and \perp re-
2739 spectively. That is exactly the same as taking the acceptance
2740 conditions of \mathcal{D} and assigning \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} to the respective argu-
2741 ments in every completion of v' for which v' is undefined. It
2742 is easy to see that we then have $v'(a) =_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}^{v_0}} = \mathbf{t}$.

2743 $v'(a) = \mathbf{f}$ Analogous to the previous case.

2744 It follows that $v' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D}^{v_0})$. From the fact that $v_0 \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$ it follows
2745 directly that $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| \leq m$. Thus, we know that there
2746 exists a serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) with $v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n = v'$.
2747 It follows that $\mathcal{Y} = (v_0, v_1, \dots, v_n)$ is a serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D}
2748 with $v_0 \sqcup v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n = v$. \square

2749 **Theorem 5.3.** *Let $\mathcal{F} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R})$ be an AF and $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is the corresponding ADF.
2750 A serialisation sequence \mathcal{Y} of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ induces a serialisation sequence \mathcal{S} of \mathcal{F} with
2751 $\hat{\mathcal{Y}} = v_{\hat{\mathcal{S}}}$ and for every serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} there is at least one such
2752 sequence for $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.*

2753 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows:

2754 “ \Rightarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Consider the
2755 serialisation sequence $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_m)$ constructed as follows. We
2756 start with $\mathcal{S} = ()$. Iterate over each $v_i \in \mathcal{Y}$ and consider E_{v_i} , computed
2757 according to Equation (4). If $E_{v_i} \neq \emptyset$, we add E_{v_i} to \mathcal{S} , otherwise we
2758 continue with v_{i+1} . Note that $E_{v_1} \neq \emptyset$ since $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ corresponds to an
2759 AF. Assume that there is some E_{v_i} with $i > 1$ such that $v_i^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) = \emptyset$.
2760 Then it follows immediately that $v_i^{-1}(\mathbf{f}) \neq \emptyset$. Thus v_i contains only
2761 arguments rejected by some previously selected initial model. Clearly,
2762 in the corresponding AF that means these arguments are attacked by
2763 some previously selected initial set in the so far constructed sequence \mathcal{S} .
2764 Consequently, they are removed in the AF-reduct directly. It follows

2765 that the constructed sequence \mathcal{S} is a serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} . Note
 2766 that this construction is unique, i. e., there is exactly one corresponding
 2767 serialisation sequence in the AF.

2768 “ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ be a serialisation sequence of \mathcal{F} . We construct a
 2769 serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_m)$ for the corresponding ADF $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$
 2770 as follows. We iterate over each $S_i \in \mathcal{S}$ and consider v_{S_i} , computed
 2771 according to Equation (5). First, we add v_{S_i} to \mathcal{Y} . Afterwards, we
 2772 consider the arguments in $S' = S_i^+ \setminus S_i^-$, i. e., the arguments that
 2773 are attacked by S_i but not already assigned \mathbf{f} by v_{S_i} . Assume some
 2774 arbitrary order over the arguments in S' and let a_1, \dots, a_m be those
 2775 arguments. Then we add (v_1, \dots, v_m) , such that for each v_j we have
 2776 $v_j(a_j) = \mathbf{f}$ and $v_j(b) = \mathbf{u}$ otherwise, to the constructed sequence \mathcal{Y} .
 2777 It is easy to see that each v_j must be an unattacked initial model in
 2778 the respective reduct. Adding these models for arguments rejected by
 2779 S_i then also ensures that $v_{S_{i+1}}$ is an initial model of the next ADF-
 2780 reduct and thus we ultimately obtain a serialisation sequence of $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$.
 2781 Note that, since we can select the order over the rejected arguments
 2782 arbitrarily, this construction is not necessarily unique, i. e., there can
 2783 be multiple corresponding serialisation sequences in the ADF. \square

2784 **Theorem 5.4.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an*
 2785 *interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a seriali-*
 2786 *sation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that*
 2787 *$\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$.*

2788 *Proof.* We prove both directions as follows:

2789 “ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{pr}(\mathcal{D})$ be a preferred model of \mathcal{D} . Then, by definition v is
 2790 also admissible and thus there exists some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} =$
 2791 (v_1, \dots, v_n) with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$. Now assume that $\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) \neq \emptyset$.
 2792 That means, there exists some initial model v' . Per Lemma 5.2 it
 2793 follows directly that $v \sqcup v'$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} which contradicts
 2794 the assumption that v is a preferred model of \mathcal{D} .

2795 “ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) =$
 2796 \emptyset . We know that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} . As-
 2797 sume that v is not preferred, i. e., there exists some admissible model
 2798 v' with $v \leq_i v'$. Per Lemma 5.2 it follows directly that there is some
 2799 admissible model v'' in \mathcal{D}^v with $v' = v \sqcup v''$. It follows that either

2800 $v'' \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}^v)$ or there exists some other $v_{n+1} \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}^v)$ with $v_{n+1} <_i v''$.
 2801 That contradicts the assumption that $\text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$. \square

2802 **Theorem 5.5.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an
 2803 interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{co}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation
 2804 sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$.*

2805 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2806 “ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{co}(\mathcal{D})$. Then there is some serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$
 2807 with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$. Assume that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^v) \neq \emptyset$, i. e., there exists
 2808 some unattacked initial model v' in \mathcal{D}^v . Then, per Definition 5.2 and
 2809 Corollary 5.1 it follows that v' only assigns \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} to exactly one argu-
 2810 ment $a \in \mathcal{A}$ and that the acceptance condition ϕ'_a for that argument in
 2811 the ADF \mathcal{D}^v is a tautology or unsatisfiable, respectively. Furthermore,
 2812 since the argument a is in the reduct \mathcal{D}^v , we know that $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$. Re-
 2813 call that per Definition 5.3 in the acceptance condition of the reduct
 2814 all occurrences of the arguments assigned \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} by v are replaced by
 2815 their truth value. Now, if we consider the acceptance condition ϕ_a of
 2816 a in \mathcal{D} , this is exactly what is done when applying the characteristic
 2817 operator $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ on the model v . That means we obtain $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = \mathbf{t}$ if
 2818 ϕ'_a is a tautology (respectively \mathbf{f} if ϕ'_a is unsatisfiable). That means we
 2819 have $v <_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ and thus a contradiction to the assumption that v is
 2820 complete in \mathcal{D} .

2821 “ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) =$
 2822 \emptyset . From Theorem 5.2 it follows that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissi-
 2823 ble model of \mathcal{D} . It remains to show that v is complete, i. e., that we
 2824 have $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$. Assume the contrary, i. e., there is some argument
 2825 $a \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$ and $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$. Assume, without loss of
 2826 generality, that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)(a) = \mathbf{t}$. That means, in every completion of v
 2827 the argument a is assigned \mathbf{t} , regardless of the assignment of arguments
 2828 assigned \mathbf{u} by v . In other words, when fixing all arguments assigned
 2829 \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} by v to their respective truth value, the acceptance condition
 2830 ϕ_a is tautological. It is easy to see that this is exactly the acceptance
 2831 condition ϕ'_a of the argument a in the reduct \mathcal{D}^v . It follows that v'
 2832 with

$$v'(b) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } b = a \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2833 is an unattacked initial model of \mathcal{D}^v and we arrive at a contradiction.
 2834 □

2835 **Theorem 5.6.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an*
 2836 *interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation*
 2837 *sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and for all $v_i, i = 1, \dots, n,$*
 2838 *it holds that $v_i \in \text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$ and $\text{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset.$*

2839 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2840 “ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{gr}(\mathcal{D})$ be the unique grounded model of \mathcal{D} . Recall from Def-
 2841 inition 2.9 that the grounded model is computed iteratively via the
 2842 function $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ starting with $v_0 = v_{\mathbf{u}}$. The grounded model is then the
 2843 model v_k such that $v_k = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{k-1})$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is the smallest number satisfying
 2844 this condition.

2845 We construct a corresponding serialisation \mathcal{Y} sequence as follows. We
 2846 start with $\mathcal{Y} = ()$. Consider first $v_1 = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{\mathbf{u}})$. We distinguish between
 2847 three cases:

2848 (1.1) $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_1(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| = 1$

2849 Let a be the argument assigned \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} by v_1 . Since $v_0 = v_{\mathbf{u}}$ it
 2850 follows directly that $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ or $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$. Clearly v'_0
 2851 with

$$v'_0(b) = \begin{cases} v_1(b) & \text{if } b = a, \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2852 is then an unattacked initial model of \mathcal{D} . The corresponding seri-
 2853 alisation sequence is updated to $\mathcal{Y} = (v'_0)$.

2854 (1.2) $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_1(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| > 1$

2855 We denote $\mathcal{A}' = \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_1(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}$. Like in (1.1) we know that
 2856 $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ or $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ for all $a \in \mathcal{A}'$. Clearly, if ϕ_a is a
 2857 tautology (or unsatisfiable) then this will also be the case after
 2858 substituting any subset of its atoms with arbitrary truth values \mathbf{t}
 2859 or \mathbf{f} , i. e., any ϕ'_a of any possible reduct of \mathcal{D} will still be a tau-
 2860 tology (respectively unsatisfiable). Let $<$ be some arbitrary order
 2861 over the arguments \mathcal{A}' and (a_1, \dots, a_m) is then an ordered list of

2862 the arguments in \mathcal{A}' . Then $\mathcal{Y}' = (v'_1, \dots, v'_m)$ is a serialisation
 2863 sequence with v'_i for $1 \leq i \leq m$ defined as

$$v'_i(b) = \begin{cases} v_1(b) & \text{if } b = a_i, \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2864 The corresponding serialisation sequence is updated to $\mathcal{Y} = \mathcal{Y}'$.

2865 (1.3) $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_1(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| = 0$

2866 We have that $v_1 = v_1 = v_{\mathbf{u}}$ and thus v_1 is the grounded model of
 2867 \mathcal{D} with the corresponding serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} = ()$.

2868 Consider now $v_i = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{i-1})$ for any $1 < i \leq n$. We distinguish between
 2869 the same three cases.

2870 (2.1) $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_i(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| = 1$ Like in the case (1.1), the model v_j that
 2871 only assigns \mathbf{t} (or \mathbf{f}) to one argument a is added to the sequence.

2872 (2.2) $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_i(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| > 1$ Again, like in case (1.2) we add one
 2873 model for each argument assigned \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} to the sequence.

2874 (2.3) $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v_i(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}| = 0$ The fixpoint of $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$ is reached and we
 2875 have that v_{i-1} is the grounded model of \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{Y} is a grounded
 2876 serialisation sequence corresponding to v_{i-1} .

2877 Thus, we have that there is at least one grounded serialisation sequence
 2878 that corresponds to the grounded model of \mathcal{D} .

2879 “ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $v_i \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$
 2880 for every i with $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $\text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}) = \emptyset$. Denote with v_{gr}
 2881 the unique grounded model of \mathcal{D} and with $\hat{v}_i = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_i$ the partial
 2882 model at step i for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

2883 We first show that $\hat{v}_i \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ by induction over i .

2884 ($i = 1$) We have that $\hat{v}_1 = v_1$ and by definition $\hat{v}_1 \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D})$. Let a
 2885 be the unique argument assigned either \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} by v_1 . Per Defini-
 2886 tion 5.2 it follows that $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ or $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$. Clearly, that
 2887 implies directly that $v_{\text{gr}}(a) = \mathbf{t}$ (or \mathbf{f} respectively) and therefore
 2888 $\hat{v}_1 \leq_1 v_{\text{gr}}$.

2889 $(i > 1)$ By assumption, we have that $\hat{v}_i = v' \sqcup v_{i-1}^{\hat{}}$ with $v' \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$.
2890 Again, let a be the unique argument assigned \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} by v' . Assume
2891 w.l.o.g. that $v'(a) = \mathbf{t}$. It follows that $\phi'_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$ with ϕ'_a being
2892 the acceptance condition of a in the reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}}$. Now, as al-
2893 ready shown in the proof of Lemma 5.1 if an acceptance condition
2894 ϕ'_a is true wrt. a model v' in the reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_{i-1}^{\hat{}}}$ then the acceptance
2895 condition ϕ_a of \mathcal{D} is true for the model $v_{i-1}^{\hat{}} \sqcup v'$. Thus, since by
2896 assumption we have that $v_{i-1}^{\hat{}} \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$, it follows that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{\text{gr}}) = \mathbf{t}$
2897 and therefore $v_{\text{gr}}(a) = \mathbf{t}$. Hence, it follows that $\hat{v}_i \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$.

2898 From Theorem 5.5 it follows directly that $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is a complete
2899 model of \mathcal{D} , i. e., $v \leq_i v_{\text{gr}}$. Thus, we have $v = v_{\text{gr}}$. \square

2900 **Theorem 5.7.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an*
2901 *interpretation. We have that $v \in \text{val}_2(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation*
2902 *sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} =$*
2903 *(\emptyset, \emptyset) .*

2904 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2905 “ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \text{val}_2(\mathcal{D})$ be a two-valued model of \mathcal{D} . It follows directly from
2906 Definition 2.8 of the characteristic operator that $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ and thus
2907 $v \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$. It follows that there exists a serialisation sequence $\mathcal{Y} =$
2908 (v_1, \dots, v_n) with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$. Since v is a two-valued model we
2909 have that $|\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) = \mathbf{u}\}| = 0$ and it follows directly that the
2910 v -reduct of \mathcal{D} is $\mathcal{D}^v = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.

2911 “ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} =$
2912 (\emptyset, \emptyset) . Per definition $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} .
2913 It remains to show that v does not assign \mathbf{u} to any argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$.
2914 Clearly, if there were such arguments, then we can construct the v -
2915 reduct $\mathcal{D}^v = (\mathcal{A}', \mathcal{C}')$ with

$$\mathcal{A}' = \mathcal{A} \setminus \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}$$

2916 and we would have $|\mathcal{A}'| \neq 0$ which contradicts the assumption. \square

2917 **Proposition 5.4.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is*
2918 *an interpretation. We have that if $v \in \text{st}(\mathcal{D})$ then there is a serialisation*
2919 *sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and it holds that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} =$*
2920 *(\emptyset, \emptyset) .*

2921 *Proof.* Follows directly from the fact that a stable model is by definition
 2922 always a two-valued model and the characterisation of two-valued models in
 2923 Theorem 5.7. \square

2924 **Theorem 5.8.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an*
 2925 *interpretation. We have that $v \in \mathbf{sa}(\mathcal{D})$ if and only if there is a serialisation*
 2926 *sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) of \mathcal{D} with $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ and for all $v_i, i = 1, \dots, n,$*
 2927 *it holds that $v_i \in \mathbf{is}^\neq(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}})$.*

2928 *Proof.* We show both directions as follows.

2929 “ \Rightarrow ” Let $v \in \mathbf{sa}(\mathcal{D})$ be an strongly admissible model of \mathcal{D} . We show that
 2930 there is a \mathbf{sa} -serialisation sequence for v via induction on the size of v ,
 2931 i. e., $n = |v^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \cup v^{-1}(\mathbf{f})|$.

2932 ($n = 0$) Trivially, the empty sequence is a strongly admissible seriali-
 2933 sation sequence corresponding to the empty model $v_{\mathbf{u}}$.

2934 ($n \rightarrow n + 1$) Let $a \in v^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \cup v^{-1}(\mathbf{f})$ such that v' with

$$v'(b) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{u} & \text{if } b = a, \\ v(b) & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

2935 is a strongly admissible model of \mathcal{D} . Note that the existence of
 2936 such a model is guaranteed by Definition 2.14. By the induction
 2937 hypothesis, there exists a \mathbf{sa} -serialisation sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) such
 2938 that $v' = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$. Since v is strongly admissible, it follows that
 2939 a is strongly justified in v , i. e., the acceptance condition ϕ_a of a
 2940 must be tautological, if $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$ (unsatisfiable, if $v(a) = \mathbf{f}$), in the
 2941 reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v'}$, since that includes that all parents of a are replaced by
 2942 their truth value in the reduct. Thus, it follows directly that the
 2943 interpretation v_a such that $v_a(a) = \mathbf{t}$ (respectively $v_a(a) = \mathbf{f}$) and
 2944 $v_a(b) = \mathbf{u}$ for all other arguments in $\mathcal{D}^{v'}$ is an unattacked initial
 2945 model of $\mathcal{D}^{v'}$ and thus (v_1, \dots, v_n, v_a) is a strongly admissible
 2946 serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D} .

2947 “ \Leftarrow ” Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a serialisation sequence such that all $v_i \in \mathcal{Y}$
 2948 are unattacked initial models of the respective reducts. We show that
 2949 $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ is a strongly admissible model of \mathcal{D} via induction on
 2950 the size of v , i. e., $n = |v^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \cup v^{-1}(\mathbf{f})|$.

2951 $(n = 0)$ The empty model $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ is by definition a strongly admissible
2952 model of \mathcal{D} .

2953 $(n \rightarrow n + 1)$ We consider the last model v_n in the sequence (v_1, \dots, v_n) .
2954 By the above characterisation v_n is an unattacked initial model of
2955 $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{n-1}}$ and thus it follows from Corollary 5.1 that $|v_n^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \cup$
2956 $v_n^{-1}(\mathbf{f})| = 1$. Let a be the single argument that is assigned \mathbf{t} (or \mathbf{f})
2957 by v_n . By Definition 5.2, the acceptance condition ϕ_a of a is a tau-
2958 tology (unsatisfiable) in the reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{n-1}}$. Thus, a is strongly
2959 justified in v given all other arguments $b \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $v(b) \neq \mathbf{u}$.
2960 Let $v' : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ such that $v'(a) = \mathbf{u}$ and $v'(b) = v(b)$ oth-
2961 erwise. By the induction hypothesis, v' is a strongly admissible
2962 model of \mathcal{D} , i. e., all $b \in v'^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \cup v'^{-1}(\mathbf{f})$ are strongly justified in
2963 v' (in particular that includes all parents of a , otherwise ϕ_a would
2964 not be tautological/unsatisfiable in the reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v'}$). Hence, v is a
2965 strongly admissible model of \mathcal{D} . \square

2966 Appendix C. Proofs for Section 6 (Computational Complexity)

2967 **Lemma 6.1.** *Given an ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and a model v of \mathcal{D} , deciding*
2968 *whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ is in *coNP*.*

2969 *Proof.* This follows directly from Theorem 3.18 of (Strass and Wallner, 2015).
2970 Technically, in (Strass and Wallner, 2015) interpretations are represented as
2971 pairs (X, Y) with $X \subseteq Y \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. However, they can clearly be interchanged
2972 by mappings $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ into the set of truth values. A pair (X, Y)
2973 represents a three-valued interpretation v defined as follows

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } a \in X \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } a \in \mathcal{A} \setminus Y \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{if } a \in Y \setminus X \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

2974 In particular, they consider the problem of verifying for a pair (X, Y) whether
2975 $(X, Y) \leq_i \mathcal{O}(X, Y)$, where \mathcal{O} is an approximating operator on the consistent
2976 complete partially ordered set (\mathcal{A}^c, \leq_i) and \mathcal{A}^c is the set of all consistent
2977 pairs of sets of arguments. In other words, \mathcal{O} approximates the characteristic
2978 operator $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}$. They show that this problem amounts to verifying whether for
2979 the lower bound $\mathcal{O}'(X, Y)$ we have that $X \subseteq \mathcal{O}'(X, Y)$ and for the upper

2980 bound $\mathcal{O}''(X, Y)$ whether $\mathcal{O}''(X, Y) \subseteq Y$. Both of these checks are in **coNP**
 2981 as per Lemma 3.17 of (Strass and Wallner, 2015).

2982 It follows that deciding whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ is in **coNP**. \square

2983 **Lemma 6.2.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be an ADF and $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an inter-*
 2984 *pretation. The problem of deciding whether there exists a model $v' \in \mathbf{ad}(\mathcal{D})$*
 2985 *with $v' \leq_i v$ and $v'(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ is in $P_{\parallel}^{\mathbf{NP}}$.*

2986 *Proof.* To decide the above problem, consider the following polynomial time
 2987 algorithm with access to an **NP** oracle. Recall, that a **NP** oracle is equivalent
 2988 to a **coNP** oracle. First, we verify whether v is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} ,
 2989 which can be done in **coNP** (see Lemma 6.1). If v is not admissible we
 2990 consider the following construction: Let $v_0 = v$. We define v_i for $i \in \mathbb{N}$ as
 2991 follows

$$v_i(a) = \begin{cases} v_{i-1}(a) & \text{if } v_{i-1}(a) \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v_{i-1})(a) \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2992 Now, clearly we have $v_i <_i v_{i-1}$ for every i , otherwise v_{i_1} would have been
 2993 admissible. For every v_i we then verify the following:

2994 (1) If $v_i(a) = \mathbf{u}$, we have that a can never be assigned \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} in any $v' \leq_i v_i$
 2995 and thus it follows that no such model v' exists and we return *false*.

2996 (2) Otherwise, we have $v_i(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ and we verify whether v_i is admissible. If
 2997 yes, we return *true*, otherwise we continue with $i \rightarrow i + 1$.

2998 The set of arguments assigned \mathbf{t} or \mathbf{f} by v has the size $n = |\{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq$
 2999 $\mathbf{u}\}|$ and we have $v_i <_i v_{i-1}$ for every i . Thus, we will make at most n steps,
 3000 each making an independent check in **coNP**. It follows that the algorithm
 3001 runs in $P_{\parallel}^{\mathbf{NP}}$. \square

3002 **Proposition 6.1.** *VER_{iS} is in $P_{\parallel}^{\mathbf{NP}}$ and **coNP-hard**.*

3003 *Proof.* Membership follows from Lemmas 6.1 and 6.2. In particular, we first
 3004 verify in **coNP** whether v is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} . Then, for every pair
 3005 of arguments $a_1, a_2 \in \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}\}$ with $a_1 \neq a_2$ we verify whether for
 3006 the model v' with

$$v'(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{u} & \text{if } a = a_2 \\ v(a) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3007 there exists an admissible model v'' with $v'' \leq_i v'$ and $v''(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$. If one
 3008 such pair exists, then v is not an initial model of \mathcal{D} . If no such model exists,
 3009 then v is an initial model of \mathcal{D} . This amounts to a polynomial number of
 3010 independent checks, each in **coNP**, cf. Lemma 6.2, and thus the algorithm
 3011 runs in $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$.

3012 For **coNP**-hardness we utilise the reduction RED_1 from (Strass and Wall-
 3013 ner, 2015). Let ψ be a propositional formula over the vocabulary P , then
 3014 we define the ADF $\text{RED}_1 = (P \cup \{z\}, \mathcal{C})$ where $z \notin P$ is a variable and the
 3015 acceptance conditions defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_p &= \neg p && \text{for } p \in P, \\ \phi_z &= \psi. \end{aligned}$$

3016 Then, we have that ψ is unsatisfiable if and only if v with

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{f} & \text{if } a = z \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3017 is an initial model of RED_1 . We show both directions as follows.

3018 “ \Rightarrow ” We have that ψ is unsatisfiable. Per Lemma 3.9 of (Strass and Wallner,
 3019 2015) it follows that for any argument $a \in \mathcal{A}$ if $\phi_a = \neg a$, then we have
 3020 $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$ for any admissible model v . Thus, we know that $v(p) = \mathbf{u}$ for
 3021 any $p \in P$ for any admissible model v . Furthermore, per definition z
 3022 does not occur in $\phi_z = \psi$ and since ψ is unsatisfiable it follows directly
 3023 that $v(z) = \mathbf{f}$ for any model of RED_1 . Clearly, that means $v \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$.
 3024 The minimality of v follows immediately since the only model v' with
 3025 $v' \leq_i v$ is the model $v_{\mathbf{u}}$.

3026 “ \Leftarrow ” We have that v with

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{f} & \text{if } a = z \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3027 is an initial model of RED_1 . From $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\text{RED}_1}(v)$ and the fact that v
 3028 assigns \mathbf{u} to every $p \in P$ it follows directly that $\Gamma_{\text{RED}_1}(v)(z) = \mathbf{f}$ and
 3029 thus that every possible truth value assignment to the atoms of ψ yields
 3030 that ψ is false and thus unsatisfiable.

3031 It follows that $\text{VER}_{i\mathfrak{s}}$ is **coNP**-hard. □

3032 **Proposition 6.2.** EXISTS_{is} and $\text{EXISTS}_{is}^{-\emptyset}$ are Σ_2^P -complete.

3033 *Proof.* Both problems are clearly equivalent, since $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ can explicitly not be
 3034 an initial model of any ADF. Furthermore, the problem is equivalent to the
 3035 problem of deciding whether there exists a non-trivial admissible model for
 3036 \mathcal{D} , i. e., the problem $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{ad}}^{-\emptyset}$. Thus, the result follows directly from the
 3037 proof of Theorem 4.15 in (Strass and Wallner, 2015). \square

3038 **Lemma 6.3.** $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} = \Sigma_2^P$ and $\text{coNP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} = \Pi_2^P$.

3039 *Proof.* We only show $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} = \Sigma_2^P$, the other statement follows analogically.
 3040 We show $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \supseteq \Sigma_2^P$ and $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \Sigma_2^P$. Remember that $\Sigma_2^P = \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$.

3041 • $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \supseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$:

3042 Note that $\text{NP} \subseteq \text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ since any problem in NP can be solved by a single
 3043 call to an NP oracle (without any need for parallelism). It follows that
 3044 any problem in NP^{NP} can be solved by using $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ oracle calls instead
 3045 of NP oracle calls.

3046 • $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$:

3047 We show the stronger statement $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$ (which implies the
 3048 above statement due to $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} \subseteq \text{P}^{\text{NP}}$).

3049 Let $Q \in \text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}}$ be a problem and A_Q be an $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}}$ -algorithm for Q .
 3050 Let I be an instance for Q , then executing A_Q on I , written as $A_Q(I)$,
 3051 gives the following algorithm trace:

$$\begin{aligned} A_Q(I) = & \text{np}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \circ \text{np}_2 \circ O_2^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \circ \\ & \dots \circ \text{np}_{k-1} \circ O_{k-1}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \circ \text{np}_k \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

3052 with $k \in O(|I|^K)$ for some $K \in \mathbb{N}$, each np_i ($i = 1, \dots, k$) is a non-
 3053 deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time (wrt. $|I|$), and each
 3054 $O_i^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}}$ ($i = 1, \dots, k-1$) is a one-step call to a P^{NP} -oracle (and \circ denotes
 3055 concatenation of the sub-algorithms). Without loss of generality and
 3056 to ease notation, let us assume that each P^{NP} -oracle call in the above
 3057 trace can be realised by an P^{NP} -algorithm B that has the following
 3058 algorithm trace:

$$B = \text{p}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ \text{p}_{k'-1} \circ O_{k'-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ \text{p}_{k'}$$

3059 with $k' \in O(|I|^{K'})$ for some $K' \in \mathbb{N}$, each p_i ($i = 1, \dots, k'$) is a de-
 3060 terministic algorithm running in polynomial time (wrt. $|I|$), and each
 3061 O_i^{NP} ($i = 1, \dots, k' - 1$) is a one-step call to a NP-oracle. Substituting
 3062 each oracle call in (C.2) with B gives us a new algorithm A'_Q :

$$\begin{aligned}
 A'_Q(I) = & \text{np}_1 \circ [p_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ p_{k'-1} \circ O_{k'-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ p_{k'}] \\
 & \circ \dots \circ \\
 & \text{np}_{k-1} \circ [p_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ p_{k'-1} \circ O_{k'-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ p_{k'}] \\
 & \circ \text{np}_k
 \end{aligned}$$

3063 Note that $A'_Q(I)$ also solves Q (we only substituted oracle calls with
 3064 concrete algorithms for the corresponding problems). Observe that
 3065 each deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time can also be un-
 3066 derstood as a non-deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time
 3067 and concatenating a non-deterministic algorithm running in polyno-
 3068 mial time with a deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time
 3069 is just a non-deterministic algorithm running in polynomial time. So
 3070 we can write “np” for algorithms of type “p” and “np” for “np \circ p”.
 3071 Let $k'' = (k - 1) * (k' - 1)$, then the algorithm trace of $A'_Q(I)$ can be
 3072 written as

$$A'_Q(I) = \text{np}_1 \circ O_1^{\text{NP}} \circ \dots \circ \text{np}_{k''-1} \circ O_{k''-1}^{\text{NP}} \circ \text{np}_{k''}$$

3073 Note that $k'' \in O(|I|^{K''})$ for some $K'' \in \mathbb{N}$, so A'_Q is a NP^{NP} -algorithm,
 3074 showing $Q \in \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$ and therefore $\text{NP}^{\text{P}^{\text{NP}}} \subseteq \text{NP}^{\text{NP}}$. \square

3075 **Proposition 6.3.** CRED_{is} is Σ_2^{P} -complete.

3076 *Proof.* For membership, consider the following algorithm. Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be
 3077 the input ADF and $a \in \mathcal{A}$. We non-deterministically guess a model v with
 3078 $v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ and verify whether v is initial in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. Together with Lemma 6.3 it
 3079 follows then directly that CRED_{is} is in Σ_2^{P} .

3080 For Σ_2^{P} -hardness, we adjust the reduction RED_2 of Strass and Wallner
 3081 (2015) from the problem of deciding whether a quantified boolean formula
 3082 $\exists P \forall Q : \psi$ is true.

3083 Let P and Q be disjoint sets of variables and ψ is a formula over $P \cup Q$.
 3084 Let x, y and z be fresh variables and we define the set $-P = \{-p \mid p \in P\}$.

Figure C.26: The ADF \mathcal{D}_ψ for $\psi = (p_1 \wedge \neg p_2) \vee q_1$ from the proof of Proposition 6.3.

3085 Then we define the reduction as the ADF $\mathcal{D}_\psi = (\mathcal{A}_\psi, \mathcal{C}_\psi)$ with

$$\mathcal{A}_\psi = P \cup -P \cup Q \cup \{x, y, z\}$$

3086 and the acceptance conditions $\phi \in \mathcal{C}_\psi$ are defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_p &= \neg x \wedge \neg z \wedge \neg \neg p && \text{for } p \in P \\ \phi_{-p} &= \neg x \wedge \neg z \wedge \neg p && \text{for } -p \in -P \\ \phi_q &= \neg z \wedge \neg q && \text{for } q \in Q \\ \phi_x &= \neg x \wedge \neg \psi \\ \phi_y &= \neg x \\ \phi_z &= \neg y \end{aligned}$$

3087 The reduction is polynomial in the size of $P \cup Q$. First, we recall two
 3088 properties of the techniques used in the above encoding, shown in Lemmas
 3089 3.9 and 3.11 of Strass and Wallner (2015). All arguments $q \in Q$ will be
 3090 assigned \mathbf{u} in every admissible model of \mathcal{D}_ψ . Secondly, if x is assigned \mathbf{u} ,
 3091 then all arguments $p \in P$ and $-p \in -P$ are also assigned \mathbf{u} . Similarly, it
 3092 follows that if z is assigned \mathbf{u} then all $p \in P$, $-p \in -P$ and $q \in Q$ are also
 3093 assigned \mathbf{u} .

3094 Figure C.26 shows an example of the construction for $\psi = (p_1 \wedge \neg p_2) \vee q_1$.
 3095 The intuition behind the reduction is the following: If $\exists P \forall Q : \psi$ is false,
 3096 then $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ is the only admissible model of \mathcal{D}_ψ and thus we have no initial model

3097 and trivially no argument can be credulously accepted. On the other hand,
 3098 if $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true, then there exists at least one subset $P' \subseteq P$ that makes
 3099 ψ true for all $q \in Q$ and we have a corresponding admissible model where y
 3100 and all $p \in P'$ are assigned \mathbf{t} , all $q \in Q$ are assigned \mathbf{u} and the rest of the
 3101 arguments are assigned \mathbf{f} . We can then show that y is assigned \mathbf{t} in every
 3102 such admissible model and thus also in the initial models of \mathcal{D}_ψ .

3103 We will now show that this claim holds, i. e., if and only if $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$
 3104 is true, then y is credulously accepted wrt. initial models, i. e., there exists a
 3105 model $v \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}_\psi)$ with $v(y) = \mathbf{t}$.

3106 “ \Rightarrow ” Assume the QBF $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true. Then there exists some $P' \subseteq P$
 3107 such that for all $Q' \subseteq Q$ we have that $P' \cup Q' \models \phi$. We denote
 3108 $M = P' \cup \{-p \mid p \in P \setminus P'\}$. Consider the model v with

$$v(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{t} & \text{if } a \in \{y\} \cup M, \\ \mathbf{f} & \text{if } a \in \{x, z\} \text{ or } a \notin M, \\ \mathbf{u} & \text{if } a \in Q. \end{cases}$$

3109 We have to show that $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)$. Clearly, for all $q \in Q$ this holds
 3110 trivially. Now, for every $p \in P'$ it follows directly that $v'(\phi_p) = \mathbf{t}$ for
 3111 every $v' \in [v]_2$. and thus $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(p) = v(p) = \mathbf{t}$. Analogously, the
 3112 same follows for every $-p$ with $p \in P \setminus P'$. For every $p \in P \setminus P'$ it
 3113 is easy to see that we have $v'(\phi_p) = \mathbf{f}$ for every $v' \in [v]_2$ and thus
 3114 $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(p) = v(p) = \mathbf{f}$. Again, the same follows analogously for every
 3115 $-p$ with $p \in P'$. For y we have that $\phi_y = \neg x$, so clearly we have
 3116 $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(y) = \mathbf{t}$ since $v'(z) = \mathbf{f}$ for every $v' \in [v]_2$. Analogously it follows
 3117 for z that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(z) = \mathbf{f}$. Finally, for x we need to show that $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(x) = \mathbf{f}$.
 3118 By assumption we know that for any X with $M \subseteq X \subseteq M \cup Q$ we
 3119 have that $X \models \psi$. Therefore, we have that $X \not\models \phi_x$. It follows that ϕ_x
 3120 is unsatisfiable and thus $\Gamma_{\mathcal{D}_\psi}(v)(x) = \mathbf{f}$.

3121 We know now that v is an admissible model of \mathcal{D}_ψ and it remains to
 3122 show that we have $v'(y) = \mathbf{t}$ for any admissible model v' with $v' <_i v$
 3123 and $v' \neq v_{\mathbf{u}}$. Assume the contrary, i. e., there is an admissible model
 3124 v' with $v'(y) = \mathbf{u}$ and $v' \leq_i v$. Then it follows directly from the
 3125 acceptance condition ϕ_z of z that $v'(z) = \mathbf{u}$ and from the acceptance
 3126 condition ϕ_y of y that we must have $v'(x) = \mathbf{u}$. Recall that for every
 3127 $q \in Q$ we always assign \mathbf{u} in every admissible model. Furthermore,
 3128 recall that if x is assigned \mathbf{u} then every $p \in P$ and every $-p \in -P$ must

3129 also be assigned \mathbf{u} in every admissible model. Clearly, that directly
 3130 implies that $v' = v_{\mathbf{u}}$. Therefore, every non-trivial admissible model
 3131 of \mathcal{D}_ψ must at least assign \mathbf{f} to x and \mathbf{t} to y and it follows that y is
 3132 credulously accepted wrt. initial model if $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true.

3133 “ \Leftarrow ” Assume that y is credulously accepted wrt. initial models in \mathcal{D}_ψ . That
 3134 means there is some initial model v with $v(y) = \mathbf{t}$. We can infer that
 3135 we must have $v(x) = \mathbf{f}$ due to the acceptance condition $\phi_y = \neg x$.
 3136 Consider the acceptance condition $\phi_x = \neg x \wedge \neg\psi$. Per definition we
 3137 have that $v(\neg x) = \mathbf{f}$ or $v(\neg\psi) = \mathbf{f}$. Clearly $v(\neg x) = \mathbf{f}$ is impossible
 3138 since $v(x) = \mathbf{f}$. It follows that $v(\neg\psi) = \mathbf{f}$ and thus $v(\psi) = \mathbf{t}$. Therefore,
 3139 we have that $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true.

3140 It follows that CRED_{is} is Σ_2^P -hard. □

3141 **Proposition 6.4.** SKEPT_{is} is Π_2^P -complete.

3142 *Proof.* For membership, consider the complement problem, i.e., deciding
 3143 whether there exists an initial model $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ with $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$.
 3144 For that, we non-deterministically guess a model v with $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$ and verify
 3145 in $\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ that v is initial. Meaning, the algorithm runs in $\text{NP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}}$ and thus the
 3146 problem SKEPT_{is} is in $\text{coNP}^{\text{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}}$. It follows from Lemma 6.3 that this class is
 3147 equivalent to Π_2^P .

3148 For Π_2^P -hardness, we show that the complement problem, i.e. deciding
 3149 whether there exists an initial model $v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ with $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$, is Σ_2^P -
 3150 hard. For that, consider the reduction \mathcal{D}_ψ from the proof of Proposition 6.3.
 3151 In particular, we will show that if and only if $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true, then x is
 3152 not skeptically accepted, i.e., there exists an initial model v with $v(x) = \mathbf{u}$
 3153 or $v(x) = \mathbf{f}$.

3154 “ \Rightarrow ” We have that $\exists P\forall Q : \psi$ is true. As shown before, then in all initial
 3155 models the argument x will be assigned \mathbf{f} and there exists at least
 3156 one such model corresponding to an assignment of variables in P that
 3157 makes ψ true. Thus, x is not skeptically accepted.

3158 “ \Leftarrow ” Assume x is not skeptically accepted, i.e., there is some initial model
 3159 v in which x is assigned \mathbf{u} or \mathbf{f} . As discussed in the proof of Propo-
 3160 sition 6.3, from Lemma 3.11 of Strass and Wallner (2015) it follows
 3161 from $v(x) = \mathbf{u}$ that all arguments $p \in P$ and $q \in Q$ are assigned \mathbf{u} as

3162 well. Furthermore, it follows from the acceptance conditions of every
3163 $-p \in -P$ that $v(-p) = \mathbf{u}$ and thus we have $v = v_{\mathbf{u}}$ which cannot be an
3164 initial model, meaning there can be no initial model of \mathcal{D}_ψ that assigns
3165 \mathbf{u} to x . Therefore, the second case must apply, i. e., we have an initial
3166 model v with $v(x) = \mathbf{f}$. From $v(x) = \mathbf{f}$ it follows then directly, as
3167 shown in the proof of Proposition 6.3, that $\exists P \forall Q : \psi$ is true.

3168 Thus, the complement problem of SKEPT_{is} is Σ_2^P -hard and the problem
3169 SKEPT_{is} is then Π_2^P -hard. \square

3170 **Lemma 6.4.** *Given a bipolar ADF $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ and a model v of \mathcal{D} , deciding
3171 whether $v \leq_i \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$ is in P .*

3172 *Proof.* The claim follows from Lemma 6.1 and the fact that verifying whether
3173 $X \subseteq \mathcal{O}'(X, Y)$ and $\mathcal{O}''(X, Y) \subseteq Y$, for the upper and lower bound respec-
3174 tively, can be done in polynomial time, as per Lemma 3.17 and Proposi-
3175 tion 5.1 of Strass and Wallner (2015). \square

3176 **Lemma 6.5.** *Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{C})$ be a bipolar ADF, $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ is an
3177 interpretation and $a \in \mathcal{A}$. The problem of deciding whether there exists a
3178 model $v' \in \text{ad}(\mathcal{D})$ with $v' \leq_i v$ and $v'(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$ is in P .*

3179 *Proof.* We use the same algorithm as in the proof of Lemma 6.2. The only
3180 difference is that we now do not need an NP oracle. Instead, as follows from
3181 Lemma 6.4, it can always be checked in polynomial time whether any model
3182 v is admissible in \mathcal{D} . Thus, since we make at most $n = |\mathcal{A}|$ checks, since in
3183 each step at least one argument is removed, and all checks are in polynomial
3184 time, it follows that the algorithm runs in polynomial time. \square

3185 **Theorem 6.1.**

- 3186 1. VER_{is} is in P .
- 3187 2. $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$ and $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}^{-\emptyset}$ are NP-complete.
- 3188 3. CRED_{is} is NP-complete.
- 3189 4. SKEPT_{is} is coNP-complete.

3190 *Proof.* We proof each statement individually as follows.

3191 1. VER_{is} is in P.

3192 We consider the same algorithm used in the case of general ADFs, cf.
3193 Proposition 6.1. First, we verify that v is an admissible model of \mathcal{D} ,
3194 which can be done in polynomial time for a bipolar ADF according to
3195 Lemma 6.4. Then, for every pair of arguments $a_1, a_2 \in \{a \in \mathcal{A} \mid v(a) \neq$
3196 $\mathbf{u}\}$ with $a_1 \neq a_2$ we verify whether for the model v' with

$$v'(a) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{u} & \text{if } a = a_2 \\ v(a) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3197 there exists an admissible model v'' with $v'' \leq_i v'$ and $v''(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$. Each
3198 of these checks can be done in polynomial time for bipolar ADFs, cf.
3199 Lemma 6.5. If one such pair exists, then v is not an initial model of \mathcal{D} .
3200 If no such model exists, then v is an initial model of \mathcal{D} . Therefore, the
3201 algorithm runs in polynomial time for bipolar ADFs.

3202 2. $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$ and $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}^{-\emptyset}$ are NP-complete.

3203 Both problems are equivalent, since the empty model $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ cannot be
3204 an initial model. Moreover, the problem is equivalent to $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{ad}}^{-\emptyset}$,
3205 which is NP-complete for bipolar ADFs, cf. (Strass and Wallner (2015),
3206 Corollary 5.2).

3207 3. CRED_{is} is NP-complete. For membership, we non-deterministically
3208 guess an interpretation v with $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$ and verify in polynomial time
3209 that v is an initial model of \mathcal{D} , cf. item 1.

3210 NP-hardness follows directly from the fact that AFs are a special case
3211 of bipolar ADFs and that the corresponding problem for AFs in NP-
3212 complete.

3213 4. SKEPT_{is} is coNP-complete. For membership, consider the complement
3214 problem, i. e., deciding whether there exists an initial model v with
3215 $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$. For that, we non-deterministically guess a model v with
3216 $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$ and verify in polynomial time that v is an initial model of \mathcal{D} .
3217 The algorithm runs in NP, thus SKEPT_{is} is in coNP.

3218 coNP-hardness follows directly from the fact that AFs are a special
3219 case of bipolar ADFs and that the corresponding problem for AFs in
3220 coNP-complete. \square

3221 **Theorem 6.2.**

3222 1. VER_σ^S is in P for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.

3223 2. VER_{pr}^S is *coNP*-complete.

3224 3. VER_{uc}^S is $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -complete.

3225 *Proof.* We proof each statement individually as follows.

3226 1. VER_σ is in P for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$

3227 Let $\mathcal{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_n)$. Note first that verifying that S_i is an initial
 3228 set of $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ for each $i = 1, \dots, n$ can be done in polynomial
 3229 time, cf. Proposition 5 of Thimm (2022) or Table 3. The same holds
 3230 for verifying whether S_i is an unattacked initial set (Thimm (2022),
 3231 Proposition 10), which we need to do for **sa** and **gr**. Furthermore, it is
 3232 clear that calculating the reduct $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_i}$ for each $S_i \in \mathcal{S}$ can also be
 3233 done in polynomial time. Finally, all that remains is to verify whether
 3234 the termination criterion for each semantics is satisfied. For **ad** and **sa**
 3235 this is trivial. For **co** this amounts to checking whether there exists
 3236 no unattacked initial set in the reduct $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}$, which can be done
 3237 in polynomial time, cf. Proposition 10 of Thimm (2022). Finally, for
 3238 **st** we have to check whether $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$, which can obviously
 3239 also be done in polynomial time. Hence, we have that VER_σ is in P for
 3240 $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{st}, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.

3241 2. VER_{pr}^S is *coNP*-complete.

3242 For membership, we verify that each $S_i \in (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ is an initial set of
 3243 $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$ in polynomial time, analogously to the above item. Then,
 3244 we have to check whether there exists no initial set in $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}$. This is
 3245 the complement of the problem $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$, which is *NP*-complete. Thus,
 3246 VER_{pr}^S is in *coNP*.

3247 For hardness, we reduce from the *NP*-complete problem $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{ad}}^{-\emptyset}$,
 3248 cf. (Dvorák and Dunne, 2018). Then, \mathcal{F} has a non-empty admissi-
 3249 ble set if and only if the empty sequence is *not* a preferred serialisation
 3250 sequence of \mathcal{F} . It follows that VER_{pr}^S is *coNP*-hard.

3251 3. VER_{uc}^S is $P_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -complete.

3252 For membership, we verify for each $S_i \in (S_1, \dots, S_n)$ that S_i is an
 3253 unchallenged initial set of $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_{i-1}}$. This can be accomplished by a
 3254 NP-oracle, since this problem is coNP-complete (Thimm (2022), Propo-
 3255 sition 11). Thus, the algorithm makes n independent NP-oracle calls,
 3256 which means it runs in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. Finally, we also need to check that
 3257 $\mathcal{F}^{S_1 \cup \dots \cup S_n}$ possesses no unchallenged initial sets, which has been shown
 3258 to be in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ (Thimm (2022), Proposition 12).

3259 For $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -hardness, we reduce from the $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -complete problem of decid-
 3260 ing whether \mathcal{F} has an unchallenged initial set. Assume, w.l.o.g., that
 3261 \mathcal{F} has no unattacked arguments. Then, \mathcal{F} has an unchallenged initial
 3262 set if and only if the empty sequence is *not* an uc-serialisation sequence
 3263 of \mathcal{F} . Since $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ is closed under complements, it follows that VER_{uc}^S is
 3264 $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ -hard. \square

3265 **Lemma 6.6.** $\text{VER}_{i_s^{\neq}}$ is in coNP.

3266 *Proof.* Consider the following algorithm. First, we verify in linear time that
 3267 $|v^{-1}(\mathbf{t}) \cup v^{-1}(\mathbf{f})| = 1$. Let $a \in \mathcal{A}$ be the single argument such that $v(a) \neq \mathbf{u}$.
 3268 If $v(a) = \mathbf{t}$, we verify that $\phi_a \in \text{TAUT}_{\mathcal{A}}$. Otherwise, if $v(a) = \mathbf{f}$, we verify
 3269 that $\phi_a \in \text{UNSAT}_{\mathcal{A}}$. Both of these checks are in coNP, thus the algorithm
 3270 runs in coNP. \square

3271 **Theorem 6.3.**

- 3272 1. $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{val}_2, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.
- 3273 2. $\text{VER}_{pr}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is Π_2^P -complete.

3274 *Proof.* Let $\mathcal{Y} = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a sequence of model. We show each statement
 3275 individually as follows.

3276 1. We distinguish between ad, co, val₂ and sa, gr for the proof as follows.

- 3277 • $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{val}_2\}$.
 3278 For each $v_i \in (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ we need to verify that $v_i \in \text{is}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n})$.
 3279 According to Proposition 6.1 this problem is in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. This amounts
 3280 to a polynomial number of independent checks in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, i. e., this
 3281 process runs in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ which is clearly equivalent to $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. Note that
 3282 computing the reducts $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}$ can be done in polynomial time

3283 and is independent of all other computations. For $\sigma = \text{ad}$, we are
 3284 done. For $\sigma = \text{co}$ we also need to verify that for $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ it
 3285 holds that $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$, which is DP-complete (Strass and Wallner
 3286 (2015), Proposition 4.11). Since $\text{DP} \subseteq \mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, this algorithm runs in
 3287 $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ for complete semantics. Finally, for $\sigma = \text{val}_2$, we need to verify
 3288 that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$, which can clearly be done in polynomial
 3289 time, thus $\text{VER}_{\text{val}_2}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$.

3290 • $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$ for $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$. For each $v_i \in (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ we need
 3291 to verify that $v_i \in \text{is}^{\neq}(\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n})$. It follows from Lemma 6.6 that
 3292 this is in coNP . This then amounts to a polynomial number of
 3293 independent checks in coNP , i. e., the process runs in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$. For
 3294 $\sigma = \text{sa}$, we are done. For $\sigma = \text{gr}$ we still need to verify that for
 3295 $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ it holds that $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$. As stated already
 3296 in item 1, this problem is DP-complete and since $\text{DP} \subseteq \mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, it
 3297 follows that $\text{VER}_{\text{gr}}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$.

3298 2. $\text{VER}_{\text{pr}}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is Π_2^P -complete. First, we verify that \mathcal{Y} is a serialisation sequence
 3299 in $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}}$, cf. item 1. Then, we need to verify that the reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}$
 3300 possesses no further initial sets. This corresponds to the complement
 3301 problem of $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}$, which is Σ_2^P -c according to Proposition 6.2. Thus,
 3302 this runs in Π_2^P . Since $\mathbf{P}_{\parallel}^{\text{NP}} \subseteq \Pi^P$ it follows that $\text{VER}_{\text{pr}}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in Π_2^P .

3303 For hardness, we reduce from the Σ_2^P -complete problem $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{is}}^{-\emptyset}$.
 3304 Then, \mathcal{D} has an initial model if and only if the empty sequence is *not*
 3305 a **pr**-serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D} . It follows that $\text{VER}_{\text{pr}}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is Π_2^P -hard. \square

3306 **Theorem 6.4.**

3307 1. $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is *coNP-hard* for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{sa}\}$.

3308 2. $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is *DP-hard* for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}\}$.

3309 *Proof.* We show each statement individually as follows.

3310 $\text{VER}_{\sigma}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is coNP-hard for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{sa}\}$.

3311 We utilise the reduction from the proof of Proposition 6.1 for the coNP-
 3312 hard problem VER_{is} . Consider the interpretation $v : \mathcal{A} \mapsto \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}\}$ with
 3313 $v(z) = \mathbf{f}$ and $v(a) = \mathbf{u}$ for all other arguments $a \in \mathcal{A} \setminus \{z\}$. Then, we

3314 have that v is an initial model of \mathcal{D} if and only if $\mathcal{Y} = (v)$ is an ad-
 3315 serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D} . Note that v is an unattacked initial model,
 3316 since the acceptance condition $\phi_z = \psi$ of z is unsatisfiable iff $v(z) = \mathbf{f}$.
 3317 Thus, the statement also holds for strong admissibility.

3318 $\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is DP-hard for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}\}$.

3319 We reduce from the DP-complete problem VER_{co} , cf. Proposition 4.11
 3320 of Strass and Wallner (2015). Then, the empty interpretation $v_{\mathbf{u}}$ is a
 3321 complete model of the ADF \mathcal{D} if and only if the empty sequence is a
 3322 co-serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D} . Clearly, in this case the empty sequence
 3323 is then also a gr-serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D} . Hence, $\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is at least
 3324 DP-hard for $\sigma \in \{\text{co}, \text{gr}\}$. \square

3325 **Theorem 6.5.**

3326 1. $\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in P for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{val}_2, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.

3327 2. $\text{VER}_{\text{pr}}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is coNP-complete.

3328 *Proof.* We show each statement individually as follows.

3329 1. $\text{VER}_\sigma^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in P for $\sigma \in \{\text{ad}, \text{co}, \text{val}_2, \text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$.

3330 For each initial model $v_i \in (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ we verify in polynomial time
 3331 whether it is an initial model of $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}}$. For $\sigma \in \{\text{sa}, \text{gr}\}$ we also
 3332 verify in polynomial time that v_i is an unattacked initial model. It is
 3333 easy to see that constructing each reduct $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_{i-1}}$ can be done inde-
 3334 pendently and in polynomial time. Finally, we have to check whether
 3335 the termination criterion for each semantics holds for (v_1, \dots, v_n) . For
 3336 ad and sa this is trivial. For co and gr this amounts to checking that for
 3337 $v = v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n$ it holds that $v = \Gamma_{\mathcal{D}}(v)$, which can be done in poly-
 3338 nomial time (Strass and Wallner (2015), Corollary 5.2). Finally, for val_2 ,
 3339 we need to verify additionally need to verify that $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n} = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$.
 3340 Clearly, this can be done in polynomial time.

3341 2. $\text{VER}_{\text{pr}}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is coNP-complete. Analogously to item 1, we verify that (v_1, \dots, v_n)
 3342 is a serialisation sequence of \mathcal{D} in polynomial time. In addition to that,
 3343 we have to verify that there exists no further initial set in $\mathcal{D}^{v_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup v_n}$.
 3344 That is equivalent to checking the complement problem of $\text{EXISTS}_{\text{ad}}^{-\emptyset}$
 3345 for ADFs, which is NP-complete (Strass and Wallner (2015), Corol-
 3346 lary 5.2). Hence, $\text{VER}_{\text{pr}}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is in coNP.

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For hardness, the result carries over from AFs since AFs are a special case of bipolar ADFs. In Theorem 6.2 we have shown that this problem is **coNP**-hard. \square

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